

Biomanufacturing and Biotechnology in South America

*Growing a Leading Circular
Bioeconomy*

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While this white paper generally reflects the views of its contributors, not all contributors may agree with every perspective or conclusion presented. Furthermore, there is substantial diversity between different countries and regions in South America. Therefore, not all perspectives and conclusions will be applicable to every region.

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Executive Summary

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing have been identified by numerous South American countries as pivotal technologies for meeting sustainable development goals (SDGs), enhancing health security, promoting a knowledge-based economy, increasing product value, and reducing primary product dependency. The sector has exhibited robust growth in the region, with several South American countries emerging as global leaders in specific subsectors, such as agricultural biotechnology and bioenergy. The region's strengths, including its rich biodiversity, abundant and diverse biomass feedstocks, and an increasingly skilled labour force, provide a solid foundation for the advancement of the field.

However, despite these advantages, the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sector in South America is underperforming relative to other developing regions, with compound annual growth rates significantly lower than those observed in Asian economies. Though there is significant diversity between economies within the region, this underperformance can be attributed to several overarching factors, including lower investment in research and development, barriers to technology transfer, inadequate infrastructure, trade barriers, and regulatory and bureaucratic obstacles.

The white paper presents the following key policy recommendations to address these challenges and unlock the potential of biotechnology and biomanufacturing in South America:

- **Ensure stable and growing R&D financing** towards a combined public and private sector target of 2% of GDP, with government support for multiple stages of development and commercialisation, focusing on biotechnology startups, SMEs, and academic basic and translational biotechnology research.
- **Provide tax reliefs for the biotechnology sector**, focusing on academic researchers and SMEs, including R&D tax rebates, equipment amortization, and reduced VAT/import taxes for laboratory reagents.
- **Strengthen technology transfer** by setting impact-focused rather than volume-focused targets; updating innovation laws, regulations, and processes, to reduce bureaucracy and favour researchers and SMEs; and financing Technology Transfer Offices at academic institutions to hire staff with biotechnology expertise, develop computational systems, and foster academia-industry networks.
- **Reduce inequality in access to education and enhance its quality** by expanding financing mechanisms, and through an increased focus on practical, computational

and entrepreneurial skills in science, collaborating with industry to align courses with skill gaps and make placements available.

- **Develop customs and transport infrastructure and processes** to ensure rapid movement of hazardous, perishable, and temperature sensitive materials.
- **Develop scale-up infrastructure** to fill the gap in product development pipelines from small scale laboratory testing to full scale production, with a particular focus on the development of CDMOs (Contract Development and Manufacturing Organisations) with GMP/GLP certification, and support the implementation of quality assurance processes and certification.
- **Develop a comprehensive biomass supply chain strategy** to build the necessary infrastructure and expertise for utilising the range of primary feedstocks and waste products available as inputs to produce higher-value products.
- **Establish and update regulation and legislation**, including that for microbial biomanufacturing and chemicals, minimising bureaucracy, ensuring efficient and rapid approval processes, and pursuing cross-border harmonisation to support regional and international trade.
- **Protect biodiversity, and support local research** into the characterisation of organisms to support conservation and identify potential biotechnological applications.

Following a SWOT analysis and tabulated key policy recommendations, the white paper conducts a more detailed examination of the following areas: Biodiversity; Raw Materials; Labour, Skills and Education; Academic Research; Financing; Technology Transfer and Startup Ecosystems; Infrastructure; and Risks, Regulation and Legislation. Each section is explored in depth, examining successful examples from the region and internationally. The white paper concludes with an analysis of the region's poor reagent supply, a critical bottleneck and the culmination of the systemic issues outlined in the previous sections. For those seeking a more comprehensive overview of recent developments in biotechnology and biomanufacturing policy in South America and internationally, additional information is provided in the appendix.

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Introduction

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are pivotal fields which promise solutions to pressing global challenges while unlocking novel opportunities across multiple sectors, including agriculture and food production, energy, chemicals, and healthcare.

Biomanufacturing, in particular, holds the potential to achieve several critical objectives:

1. Fostering sustainable and carbon-neutral production methods, reducing reliance on fossil fuels
2. Introducing novel innovative properties through the utilisation of biological molecules and biotechnology
3. Enhancing stability and security by enabling production methods which harness local resources and waste products and reduce dependence on foreign products.

Figure 1: Biomanufacturing and biotechnology promises to deliver novel products, whilst supporting security and sustainability in a range of sectors, including Health, Agriculture, Food, Environment, Energy, and Industry.

Major global economies and regions, including the United States, Europe, and China, have made substantial investments and initiatives to promote biomanufacturing and biotechnology. South America is an emerging player that has the potential to become a hub for biomanufacturing and biotechnology. Many policies and initiatives have been successful in promoting biomanufacturing and biotechnology in the region. There are however also challenges for the sector as well as opportunities for change that will further promote biomanufacturing in the region.

Aims

The objective of this white paper is to provide a comprehensive overview of the strengths, advancements, challenges, and opportunities within the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sector in South America. By consolidating insights from industry stakeholders, academic experts, and research institutions across South America, this paper aims to serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, investors, and practitioners alike.

This white paper will:

- Identify and highlight recent advancements in biomanufacturing within South America.
- Showcase key strengths and successful policies that have contributed to the growth of biomanufacturing in the region.
- Address challenges hindering the growth of biomanufacturing within the region.
- Identify opportunities for further development and expansion of biomanufacturing.
- Offer broad policy recommendations to foster the advancement of biotechnology and biomanufacturing.
- Provide a valuable resource for policymakers, investors, and practitioners seeking to engage with the biomanufacturing sector in South America.

South America's exceptional diversity has led to each country and region having a distinct biotechnology and biomanufacturing landscape, with unique needs for the development and support of the sector. Nevertheless, certain overarching themes are evident across multiple states, provinces, and countries, and have been illustrated with examples and case studies. Consequently, the policy recommendations and guidelines provided in this white paper are broad and generalised, requiring adaptation to fit the specific context of each country.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

Biodiversity - A huge untapped resource of genes, proteins, chemicals and organisms that could be harnessed through biotechnology

Raw Materials and Biomass - A large variety of different feedstocks available in large quantities

Cost-effective Skilled Labour - Availability of highly educated and skilled employees and lower wages compared to other international locations

Basic Research - Strong research in local diseases, local environment and linked to local industries.

Weaknesses

Financing of R&D - Lack of financing from both public and private sector for biomanufacturing and biotechnology research

Technology Transfer - Low rates of technology transfer from academic research to the private sector; lack of expertise specific to biotechnology and biomanufacturing

Scale Up Infrastructure - Lack of scale up infrastructure to enable biomanufactured products to be taken to market

Trade Infrastructure - Weak infrastructure including for transport and customs

Regulation and Legislation - Lack of regulation in certain areas, and overly restrictive regulation and processes in other areas

Bureaucracy - Slow and inefficient processes

Targeted Policy - Lack of clear and implemented biotechnology and biomanufacturing policies and strategies

Opportunities

Pro-innovation Legislation - Improving innovation laws and legislation, and tech transfer processes

Private Capital - Increased interest in the region from private investors

Increasingly Skilled Workforce - Continued growth of skilled labour through education

Promoting Regional Trade - International partnerships and harmonisation of regulation within the region

Supportive Policy Framework - Development of Holistic Bioeconomy Strategy

Threats

Financial Instability - Rapidly fluctuating and unstable funding situation especially with political change which threatens progress

Misregulation - Lack of regulation in some areas and restrictive regulation in other areas both stifle innovation and risk environmental and other damage

Declining Biodiversity - Rapid loss of Biodiversity, which results in loss of the resource.

Economic and Political Instability - Mismanagement of the economy and political unrest hamper the development of novel industries

Policy Recommendations

	General Science Technology and Innovation	Specific to Biomanufacturing and Biotechnology
Financing R&D	<p>Gradually increase research and development (R&D) spending towards 2% of GDP, through a mixture of public sector and private sector funding</p> <p>Utilise government grants to support private sector R&D, in particular for startups and Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)</p> <p>Ensure a stable and sustainable long-term government funding landscape</p>	<p>Target the biotechnology and biomanufacturing academic sector with specific funds for both basic and translational research within the field</p> <p>Identify key strategy areas specific to the country's industry within biotechnology and Biomanufacturing when financing the sector</p> <p>Finance Start-ups and SMEs for multiple stages of research, including feasibility study, proof of principle, and scale up and commercialisation. Finance at multiple scales including small grants and seed funds, to larger grants</p>
Fiscal (Tax) Incentives for R&D and SMEs	<p>Utilise tax incentives to encourage the private sector to engage in R&D, as an alternative to increased direct financing</p> <p>Provide tax reliefs targeted at startups and SMEs in order to support their growth</p>	<p>Target biotechnology as a key target industry with specific incentives which could include amortisation of equipment and R&D tax rebates</p> <p>Reduce VAT and import taxes for biological reagents used in R&D, in particular for academic research, but also potentially for the private sector</p>
Technology Transfer	<p>Finance technology transfer offices (TTOs) sufficiently to enable employment of skilled expertise to meet increasing demand for services, and enable development of processes and systems.</p> <p>Set targets for technology transfer based on commercial and social impact, and not related to the number of patents registered.</p>	<p>Incorporate biotechnology and biomanufacturing specific expertise within TTOs, including both the business and legal expertise in the sector.</p> <p>Generate supportive technology transfer agreements for biotechnology which incentivise the process from the perspective of researchers and startups based on an understanding of the biotechnology market.</p>

	<p>Set targets for improving the speed of formation of technology transfer agreements and approval processes including that for patents, and aim to reduce bureaucracy</p> <p>Generate templates for tech transfer agreements and guidelines which increase transparency and aid both academics and industrial partners</p> <p>Modify and update patent, innovation, and technology transfer laws to support technology transfer</p>	<p>Increase communication and presence of technology transfer personnel within academic departments in the biological sciences, which have historically had little engagement, and create mechanisms for TTOs to assess research being conducted.</p> <p>Encourage the formation of networks between academia and the biotechnology industry which can also include TTOs to support communication and collaboration. Increase the presence of industrial speakers at conferences and talks.</p>
<p>Education</p>	<p>Continue to expand financing mechanisms to improve access to secondary and tertiary education and reduce inequality</p> <p>Maximise uptake of technology including computational skills in education</p> <p>Target the high dropout rates in higher education</p> <p>Improve business and enterprise education for those in science fields which includes technology transfer, patenting and licensing as well as ethics, open access and open source technology</p>	<p>Increase focus on practical skills, computational skills, critical thinking and creative thinking, in teaching and examination in biological sciences courses</p> <p>Continue to expand biotechnology and biomanufacturing courses both at undergraduate and postgraduate level</p> <p>Improve funding for practicals to enable undergraduates to access the latest equipment, and high school students to gain more practical experience</p> <p>Collaborate with industry to ensure courses fill the skill gaps, and enable industrial placements and internships within biotechnology companies</p>
<p>Infrastructure</p>	<p>Improve commercial and trade related infrastructure including that for customs and transportation</p>	<p>Support and finance development of scale-up infrastructure, including scale up plants which meet the latest manufacturing standards e.g. GMP and/or GLP certified. This includes supporting the formation of Contract Development and Manufacturing Organisations (CDMOs) both private and public.</p> <p>Support development of infrastructure and facilities for quality control, testing, and standards, accessible to both the private and public sector. Help finance and support private companies to acquire certification e.g. ISO certifications</p>

		<p>Improve customs and transport infrastructure to address significant hurdles in both import and export of biological materials. Include accelerated processes and infrastructure for identification and customs clearance of reagents and biological materials.</p>
<p>Regulation and Legislation</p>	<p>Improve Technology transfer and innovation laws and regulation (see above tech transfer)</p>	<p>Put in place and implement regulation and legislation for the field where it is missing, including that surrounding microbial biomanufacturing and chemicals.</p> <p>Readdress and discuss restrictive regulations and laws to reflect changes in understanding, and update regulation to deal with technological changes in the field.</p> <p>Implement regulation and legislation in a way that minimises bureaucracy with clear and efficient approvals processes as well as targets for approval times.</p> <p>Pursue cross-border harmonisation and agreements within South America.</p>
<p>Environment and biodiversity</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Support research into biodiversity and the characterisation of different organisms.</p> <p>Implement environmental and biodiversity policies to ensure maintenance of this resource. This includes protecting primary vegetation, preventing deforestation, and protecting vulnerable species. Policies can involve use of credits and other financial incentives.</p> <p>Support local research and provide benefits to local communities</p>
<p>Feedstocks and raw materials</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Form a plan for valorisation of the range of available feedstocks for biomanufacturing, through a national biomass supply plan. This includes a plan for the development of the infrastructure required.</p> <p>Support research into use of a range of feedstocks for different biomanufacturing applications.</p>

Biodiversity

Figure 2: Animal plant and microbial diversity in South America hosts a large untapped resource of DNA and genes, proteins and enzymes, chemicals, and organisms and strains, with application in health, agriculture, industry and other fields.

An Untapped Resource for Biotechnology

A great strength of South America lies in its biodiversity in all kingdoms, including microbial, plant and animal. This biodiversity provides an enormous untapped resource of genes, proteins, strains and species, as well as chemical compounds accessible through biomanufacturing, which can be harnessed for real world application. South America is reportedly home to 40% of the planet's biodiversity, 25% of its forests and 26% of its freshwater resources.¹

There are four major climatic zones in South America and five out of only seventeen megadiverse countries identified in 1998 are in South America, namely Brazil, Colombia, Venezuela, Peru and Ecuador. Each of these countries has more than 4,000 endemic plant species.^{2,3} Within the continent many habitats with extremely high biodiversity and unique species have been identified, including the Amazon Rainforest, Atlantic Forest, Cerrado, Chocó-Darién, Tumbes-Chocó-Magdalena, Patagonian Desert, Monte Desert,

¹ International Union for Conservation of Nature, 'South America | IUCN' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209103751/https://iucn.org/our-work/region/south-america>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

² Spotlight on South America', *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1.4 (2017), pp. 1–2, doi:10.1038/s41559-017-0129.

³ 'Biodiversity, Australia State of the Environment Report 2001 (Theme Report): The Meaning, Significance and Implications of Biodiversity (Megadiverse Countries)', 2008 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20081208141905/http://www.environment.gov.au/soe/2001/publications/theme-reports/biodiversity/biodiversity01-3.html>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

Gran Chaco, Pantanal, and Valdivian Temperate Forest, to name a few.⁴ The Atlantic Forest is one of the most diverse regions globally for soil fungi⁵ and the Amazon rainforest alone has been reported to host 10 % of the world's known biodiversity, with 1200 new species of plant and vertebrate discovered between 1999 and 2009, equating to one new species every three days.^{6,7}

Furthermore, the many extreme environments in South America provide habitats for the evolution of extremophiles with unique adaptations and genes which could have applications in biotechnology.^{8,9}

A resource down the drain: protection is a must

To ensure that this resource continues to be available, firstly it must be protected. According to the living planet report, there has been a 94% decline in the Living Planet Index value between 1970 and 2018 in Latin America and the Caribbean. This index utilises vertebrate population data to track the average change in population sizes over time.^{10,11} The decline of 94% in the index value for vertebrate species indicates a worrying underlying loss of habitat. Important species with possible genes and attributes of interest, many yet to be discovered and characterised, are at risk of going extinct.

Latin America ranks the region with the highest number of animals reported extinct since 1500.^{12,13} Indeed, although efforts have been made to reduce the loss of primary

⁴ Norman Myers and others, 'Biodiversity Hotspots for Conservation Priorities', *Nature*, 403.6772 (2000), pp. 853–58, doi:10.1038/35002501.

⁵ Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, 'State of the World's Plants and Fungi 2023' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241204113019/https://www.kew.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/State%20of%20the%20World%27s%20Plants%20and%20Fungi%202023.pdf>>.

⁶ WWF, 'About the Amazon' <https://web.archive.org/web/20241203065447/https://wwf.panda.org/discover/knowledge_hub/where_we_work/amazon/about_the_amazon/> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁷ WWF, 'Amazing Discoveries in the Amazon: New Species Found Every 3 Days Over Last Decade' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240519020534/https://wwf.panda.org/?196057/Amazing-Discoveries-in-the-Amazon-New-Species-Found-Every-Three-Days-Over-Last-Decade>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁸ National Geographic, 'South America: Physical Geography' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240803010203/https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/south-america-physical-geography/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁹ Armando Azua-Bustos and Carlos González-Silva, 'Biotechnological Applications Derived from Microorganisms of the Atacama Desert', *BioMed Research International*, 2014 (2014), p. 909312, doi:10.1155/2014/909312.

¹⁰ WWF, *Living Planet Report 2022: Building a Nature-Positive Society*, 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241009222134/https://www.wwf.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-05/WWF-Living-Planet-Report-2022.pdf>>.

¹¹ Hannah Ritchie and Max Roser, 'Living Planet Index: What Does It Really Mean?', *Our World in Data*, 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241113100323/https://ourworldindata.org/living-planet-index-decline>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

¹² International Union for Conservation of Nature, 'The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species', *IUCN Red List of Threatened Species* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240608194700/https://www.iucnredlist.org/statistics>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

¹³ Germán Vergara, 'Where the Wild Things Aren't Species Loss and Capitalisms in Latin America Since 1800 | ReVista' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240616155954/https://revista.drclas.harvard.edu/where-the-wild-things-arent/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

vegetation, protect ecosystems, and in some cases increase forest cover, many South American countries continue to see loss of primary vegetation. In Brazil for example, in 2022, almost 1.8 million hectares (18 000 km²) of tropical forest was lost.¹⁴ In many cases, the protection of local biodiversity relies on national and local governments, and changes in government can alter a country's outlook. In Brazil for example, deforestation accelerated under President Bolsonaro.¹⁵

In addition to threats from human land use, threats to local ecosystems also include those from invasive non-native species, and disease transfer to wild populations as a result of intensive agricultural practices. If governments can observe the direct economic benefits of preserving biodiversity through biotechnology and biomanufacturing, it could increase the incentive to preserve local ecosystems.

Harnessing Biodiversity

To fully leverage this biodiversity and its economic and societal benefits, it's essential to both collaborate with international partners as well as develop the infrastructure and expertise to enable local researchers and companies to handle the entire process, from discovery to bringing products to market. The latter process can be seen as having greater benefit to the local economy and society if successful, as it enables the creation of jobs and can maximise the access of products to local communities.

The transition from basic research to market application is discussed in more detail in the following sections, however the first step in the process is bioprospecting and the characterisation of the local organisms. Many areas within Latin America are under-investigated in terms of the species present and their diversity. In the state of the 'World's Plants and Fungi 2023' report, out of 32 "darkspots" globally, regions where there is a lack of information on the plant species present, 9 are in South America. North-Western South America is particularly under-investigated in terms of fauna, with Colombia having the largest knowledge gap on plant diversity and distribution internationally, with New Guinea in second. The report also indicates that 77% of undescribed species are predicted to be threatened with extinction, making primary research in this area even more important.¹⁶

There continues to be an over-representation of foreign researchers in biodiversity research in some countries in South America, however many countries are developing a

¹⁴ 'Tropical Forest Loss by Leading Country 2023', *Statista*
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240820120921/https://www.statista.com/statistics/1254554/tropical-forest-loss-global-by-country/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

¹⁵ Luciana Gomes Barbosa, Maria Alice Santos Alves, and Carlos Eduardo Viveiros Grelle, 'Actions against Sustainability: Dismantling of the Environmental Policies in Brazil', *Land Use Policy*, 104 (2021), p. 105384, doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105384.

¹⁶ Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, 'State of the World's Plants and Fungi 2023'.

strong local foundation for this research. Even within countries, local institutions in areas of biodiversity are often not the primary institutions conducting biodiversity research. In Brazilian biodiversity research in the Amazon for example, the state of Sao Paulo is highly represented, whereas local institutions within the region of the Amazon are less well represented (Figure 3). Action however is being taken to promote local and regional research, including in Brazil.¹⁷ Research led by local institutions aids local knowledge generation and local support for the preservation of diversity. Therefore, while maintaining the strengths of leading research institutions, further supporting research institutions in the locality must continue to be a priority.

Figure 3: Web of Science Query for the top 10 affiliations for Brazilian researchers researching biodiversity, ecology or conservation in the Amazon between 2019 and 2023. Universities in other regions, in particular Sao Paulo, dominate publications, however increasing local research within the area is represented (Universidade Federal do Pará and Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia).¹⁸

¹⁷ Institute of Man and Environment of the Amazon, 'Strengthening Environmental Management in the Amazon' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209115413/https://www.amazonfund.gov.br/en/projeto/Strengthening-Environmental-Management-in-the-Amazon/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

¹⁸ Clarivate Analytics, '28/05/2024 , Query Web of Science: Biodiversity (Topic) OR Ecology (Topic) OR Conservation (Topic) AND "Amazon" (All Fields); Document Type: Article , Countries/Regions: BRAZIL , Publication Years: 2019 or 2020 or 2021 or 2022 or 2023', 2024.

Nagoya Protocol

Where there is external benefit from genetic resources, including from foreign researchers and private entities, the 'Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit Sharing' seeks to ensure fair and equitable benefit sharing.¹⁹ The landscape of adoption and implementation of the Nagoya protocol varies considerably between different countries in South America.^{20,21} This landscape, and the benefits and concerns surrounding the protocol are not discussed further in this white paper. Nevertheless, it is evident that clear mechanisms for access and benefit sharing are key to ensure that local regions benefit from their biodiversity, while preserving collaborative research to prevent biodiversity loss.

Case Study: Fundación Biociencia, Swisssastral, Santiago Chile

Fundación Biociencia is a Chilean non-profit foundation dedicated to extremophile research and development. Chile is a country with some of the most diverse and extreme habitats, which include ice sheets, salt flats, geothermal springs and geysers, and deserts. Herein lies a large untapped resource of microbial diversity that has many potential biotechnological uses.

Fundación Biociencia conducts the whole process from identifying extremophilic microbes to investigating potential biotechnological uses and applications. This includes bioprospecting; microbe isolation, cultivation and characterisation; biochemical and genomic analysis; enzyme and protein identification, purification, characterisation and production; and searching for bioactive compounds. The foundation holds a large and diverse collection of extremophiles isolated in South America, with over 300 unique strains which include thermophiles, halophiles, acidophiles, alkaliphiles, aerobes, and anaerobes.

Swisssastral is the commercial arm, and provides services in the field for industry, as well as producing high quality extremophilic proteins in *E. coli*. These proteins, identified in extremophiles, have unique properties which include high activity, high stability, and varied pH and solvent tolerance to name a few. Biostabilisers, pigments and antioxidants are also under investigation.

¹⁹ Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 'The Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing' (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2024) <<https://www.cbd.int/abs/default.shtml>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

²⁰ Michael Heinrich and others, 'Access and Benefit Sharing Under the Nagoya Protocol—Quo Vadis? Six Latin American Case Studies Assessing Opportunities and Risk', *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11 (2020), p. 765, doi:10.3389/fphar.2020.00765.

²¹ 'Access and Benefit-Sharing Clearing-House | Access and Benefit-Sharing Clearing-House', *Country Profiles, Nagoya Protocol* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209125330/https://absch.cbd.int/en/countries>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

Fundación Biociencia holds partnerships with some of the largest pharmaceutical companies worldwide and has partnered with NASA to conduct extremophile experiments on the International Space Station. Furthermore, the foundation ensures that income generated from the unique biodiversity of the region benefits local research and development, and has supported the development of microbiological and biochemical research laboratories in the Chilean Antarctic Institute, as well as promoted the development of the Latin American Extremophile society.²²

²² Jenny Blamey and Giannina Espina, Interview at Fundación Biociencia.

Raw Materials

Figure 4: Processes involved in raw material valorisation. Feedstock genetic development, and sustainably production and management, enable primary feedstocks, like corn and sugarcane, and waste biomass and by-products from the agricultural, meat, and fish industries, to be optimally harvested and preprocessed into inputs for biomanufacturing. Infrastructure including that for transport and storage are required for this process.

South America is a Leading Agricultural Producer

Another major strength for biomanufacturing in South America, is the diversity and quantity of feedstocks and biomass available for fermentation or bio-transformation. South America is an agricultural powerhouse, the region being a major international exporter of soybeans, maize, sugar (from sugarcane), coffee, fruits, and vegetables, to name a few. The largest agricultural and food exporter in South America is Brazil, with exports of 79.3 billion USD in 2017, followed by Argentina (35 billion USD), Chile (17 billion USD), Ecuador (10.4 billion USD) and Peru (8.8 billion USD). Agriculture contributed a greater than 10% share of GDP in many countries in the region and employed more than 25% of the workforce in several countries including Bolivia, Ecuador and Peru.²³ Primary agricultural biomass as well as biomass from by-products

²³ OECD and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, *Latin American Agriculture: Prospects and Challenges* (OECD, 8 July 2019), pp. 70–124, doi:10.1787/b2b742eb-en.

of agriculture and other industries can be harnessed as feedstocks or starting materials for biomanufacturing and fermentation processes, enabling a sustainable and circular bioeconomy (Figure 4).

Case Study: Food Engineering at LEMeB

An academic example demonstrating the varied research into the use of different feedstocks for applications in Biomanufacturing and Biotechnology, can be seen at the LEMeB Bioprocess and Metabolic engineering Laboratory at Unicamp (Universidade Estadual de Campinas) in Brazil. Here, multiple plant feedstocks and by-products are being investigated including sugar cane bagasse, corn, rice, coco, peanut shells, soy, bamboo, and waste orange peel. Multiple bacterial and fungal species are being tested to determine pathways for biotransformation of the feedstocks and extraction of useful molecular components relevant to industry. Application areas include biofuels, foods, and other industrial processes. The laboratories are equipped with some of the latest equipment including high-performance liquid chromatography machines (HPLCs), and bioreactors. Researchers had varied backgrounds with expertise in bioprocess engineering, metabolic engineering (including recombinant DNA technology), microbial physiology, bioinformatics, computational modelling and simulation. Both local and international collaborations and that with industry have been established, with patents also produced through the research.^{24,25,26}

Case Study: Kura Biotech

Kura Biotech is a highly innovative company based in Puerto Varas, Chile, that started out by purifying beta-glucuronidase and Aryl-sulfatase enzymes from abalone by-products. These enzymes are utilised in drug screening and toxicology analysis. This valorisation of a by-product from the abalone industry utilising biotechnology demonstrates the way biotechnology and biomanufacturing can promote a circular bioeconomy for sustainable production. Furthermore, it shows that feedstocks and starting materials need not be limited to plant material.

From this starting point, the company has gone from strength to strength, developing recombinant Beta-glucuronidase in addition to the abalone purified enzymes which fall into their Finden product line, as well as expanding into two other product lines. Their Avenire product line produces enzymes for food testing and produced RT-qPCR and RT-LAMP

²⁴ 'LEMeB - Research'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209131754/https://sites.google.com/site/unicampfealemeb/our-research>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

²⁵ Ana Gabriela Rissato, Visit to LEMeB, 2024.

²⁶ 'LEMeB - 2022'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209135358/https://sites.google.com/site/unicampfealemeb/our-publications/articles/2022?authuser=0https://sites.google.com/site/unicampfealemeb/our-research>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

testing kits for Covid-19 during the pandemic. Finally their newest product line, Blikka, produces Genomics enzymes.

With a state of the art facility in Puerto Varas where both research and development as well as production is conducted, Kura employs over 70 highly skilled workers bringing together both business and scientific expertise. The company has a strong desire to support the growth of the biotechnology sector within the region.^{27,28}

Forming an Integrated Biomass Supply Chain

In South America, there is a need to invest and innovate to maximise use of available biomass as feedstocks to support biomanufacturing. This process of valorisation of low value biomass into high value products is a key opportunity to support the local economy, and promote sustainable and environmentally friendly production, thereby also supporting climate and environmental goals. The industry generated as a result, including that formed around residual collection, transportation, storage and preprocessing can provide jobs and income for local people, and possibly reduce the clearance of primary vegetation. This balancing of the need for land for crop production, including for feedstocks, and the need to maintain primary vegetation and biodiversity is key. The processing of agricultural produce and residues into higher value products can result in higher profitability and enable greater investment into increasing productivity of existing land use. As well as short term increases in productivity, analysis of the long term sustainability of agricultural strategies and effects on land quality etc. are also important.

In terms of feedstock genetic development, the agricultural sector in some South American countries is already well equipped to harness plant biotechnology, being leaders in GM crop production. The bioenergy sector in particular in Brazil and also in Argentina has put in place the expertise for residue collection, transportation, storage and preprocessing. Now diversification and expansion of these processes to enable other biomanufacturing processes utilising the existing expertise as a basis will be beneficial. Similarly, other South American countries can use this as a model for the potential ways to harness and maximise the use of agricultural resources available. National strategies and renewed policy work to promote and invest in infrastructure for valorisation of biomass for diverse biomanufacturing processes will aid this process.

²⁷ 'Kura Biotech | Home' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241125231847/https://www.kurabiotech.com/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

²⁸ Manuel Rozas and others, Visit to Kura Biotech, 2024.

Case Study: Biofuel production in Brazil

The development of the biofuel sector is a good example of where policy over a number of decades in Brazil has directed progress and development of a field in a holistic way resulting in the country emerging as a global leader. The development of biofuel production in Brazil took advantage of the country's capacity for sugarcane feedstock production, and recently more diverse residues and by-products have been the subject of further research. Brazil's development of biofuels can be a good model to develop policy for other biomanufacturing fields. The infrastructure, processes, legislation and incentives required, though different, can be directly related to the processes in many biomanufacturing and biotechnology sectors.

Brazil's first large scale biofuel program, "Próalcool", was launched in 1975 as a result of the oil crisis and a desire to reduce reliance on imported oil. It built upon technological progress in the previous decade, where both the private sector, through the CTC (Sugarcane Technology Center), as well as the public sector, through the the national Sugarcane Improvement Program (Planalsucar), contributed to agronomic research. A wide range of research covered many aspects of production including sugarcane field management, agricultural mechanisation, plant health and pest control. The initial implementation of Próalcool included both mandates and subsidies, which included low interest loans for creation of sugarcane plantations and new mills. In tandem, two new agencies, Conselho Nacional do Álcool (CNAL) and Comissão Executiva Nacional do Álcool (CENAL) were created, and the National Science and Technology Development Council (CNPq) and Research and Projects Financer (FINEP) supported research. Skills and training were also key to success of the endeavour with improved and updated professional courses, held by UDOP (National Bioenergy Union) Corporate University being an example. Collaboration between the automobile industry and the government, enabling use of government fleets for testing between 1978 and 1980, helped support the modification of cars to use ethanol as a fuel. Mandates and updated regulation over time has increased the ethanol in gasoline to 27 percent with proposals to increase this further to 30 percent.

Periods of stagnation in the field did occur, in particular due to political and policy changes from the mid 1980s, when the Proalcool programme ceased to exist due to the political regime changing. This demonstrates the importance of long term stability and policy. It is clear that long term policy and the coordination of Government, Academia and Industry have been vital in enabling Brazil to become a leader in the field.

More recently, Innovation, regulation and legislation have continued to be updated and modified to align with progress in the field, changes in climate policy and economic changes. The National Biofuels Policy, 'RenovaBio', implemented in 2019 seeks to enable Brazil to meet updated climate targets for reductions in Greenhouse gas emissions and carbon neutrality by 2050. The program sets annual carbon intensity reduction targets,

certifies biofuels by efficiency in reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and has set up a Decarbonization Credits (CBio) scheme, where by 2022, over 75 percent of biofuel plants were able to issue credits.^{29,30,31,32}

Case Study: US Policy drive to support Biomass Supply and Supply chain Infrastructure

The United States is heavily investing in and developing policy to support biomass supply and supply chain infrastructure. In 2022, the US government committed \$270 million investment over five years from the Department of Defence towards launching the “Tri-Service Biotechnology for a Resilient Supply Chain” program. Following this, in 2024 a key policy document titled “BUILDING A RESILIENT BIOMASS SUPPLY, A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America” was produced. In this report, bioproduct categories including medical products, personal care and cosmetics, enzymes, livestock feed, agricultural inputs, construction materials, paper and packaging, biobased polymers, and bioenergy and biofuels, were listed alongside example products and the feedstocks required.³³ The research needs in the area were also identified, and “Policies and Programs for Capacity Building and Market Development” reported. The system elements required for transformation of biomass, and opportunity areas identified in the report included: Feedstock Genetic Development; Sustainable Production & Management; Harvest and Residual Collection; Transportation; Storage; Preprocessing; and Supply Systems Sustainability.^{34,35} There is a need for the production of similar policy and strategy in South America.

²⁹ L. Cortez and others, ‘The 22nd International Symposium on Alcohol Fuels – 22 ISAF 40 Years of the Brazilian Ethanol Program (Proálcool): Relevant Public Policies and Events Throughout Its Trajectory and Future Perspectives’, 2016

<https://web.archive.org/web/20230127003718/https://bioenfapesp.org/gsb/lacaf/documents/papers/05_ISAF_2016_Cortez_et_al.pdf> [accessed 9 December 2024].

³⁰ Rubismar Stolf and Ana Paula Rodrigues de Oliveira, ‘THE SUCCESS OF THE BRAZILIAN ALCOHOL PROGRAM (PROÁLCOOL) - A DECADE-BY-DECADE BRIEF HISTORY OF ETHANOL IN BRAZIL’, *Engenharia Agrícola*, 40 (2020), pp. 243–48, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-4430-Eng.Agric.v40n2p243-248/2020>.

³¹ Marcelo Teixeira, ‘Higher Brazil Ethanol Blend Would Take Extra 3.5% Sugar from Market -Citi’, *Reuters*, 19 July 2023, section Business

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20230720182419/https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSL8N3955ZH>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

³² United States Department of Agriculture, Foreign Agricultural Service, ‘Biofuels Annual, Brazil’, 2024 <https://web.archive.org/web/20240929011650/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Biofuels%20Annual_Sao%20Paulo%20ATO_Brazil_BR2022-0047.pdf> [accessed 9 December 2024].

³³ USDA (U.S. Department of Agriculture), *Table 1: BUILDING A RESILIENT BIOMASS SUPPLY: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America*, March 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241217011343/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>>.

³⁴ U.S. Department of Agriculture, ‘Building a Resilient Biomass Supply: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America’ <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241128023655/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>>.

³⁵ The White House, ‘FACT SHEET: The United States Announces New Investments and Resources to Advance President Biden’s National Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Initiative’, *The White House*, 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241130010032/https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2022/09/14/fact-sheet-the-united-states-announces-new-investments-and-resources-to-advance-president-bidens-national-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-initiative/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

Labour, Skills and Education

Figure 5: Education toward a skilled workforce for biomanufacturing requires development of skills including practical laboratory skills, critical thinking, problem solving, creativity, leadership, and communication; as well as knowledge in scientific disciplines, business and entrepreneurship, computation, and engineering. A large skilled workforce and flow of individuals between academia and biomanufacturing industry optimally support the sector.

Overview

In the past two decades, great strides have been made in education in South America, resulting in a skilled workforce with great capacity to support biotechnology and biomanufacturing. This highly skilled and cost effective workforce of the region is consistently raised as a great strength of the region by biotechnology and biomanufacturing companies, and contributes to the region's ability to biomanufacture products cheaper than possible elsewhere in the world. There is still however much heterogeneity within the region with many areas for improvement. Further developing this workforce through continued strategic improvements to education and training will ensure that the sector flourishes.

Undergraduate Education - An Overview

A World Bank report on tertiary education in Latin America and the Caribbean reported that the gross enrollment rate in higher education increased more than two fold from 21 percent to 52 percent in the region, representing the third highest figure globally after 'North America', and 'Europe and Central Asia'. This has been attributed to higher secondary education completion rates, rising from 70 percent to 81 percent in 2018; an increase in the number and diversity of higher education programs with one quarter of higher education institutions and half of courses being new; and supportive financing policies including student loans, scholarships and reductions or removal of fees in public institutions for lower income students.³⁶ The landscape in South America however is considerably heterogeneous both between countries and within countries, and successful education policies seek to both improve education as well as reduce inequalities in access. Inequality in access and outcomes of education depending on socio-economic background remains one of the largest problems in the region.³⁷

The Covid-19 pandemic adversely affected both secondary and tertiary education and the governmental response of different countries in South America varied during the period.^{38,39,40} Many undergraduate science courses are longer in South America than in Europe or the US, with 5-6 years being the norm, and there is also a much higher dropout rate for undergraduate courses in the region with a completion rate of 46 percent which has also declined over time, made worse by the pandemic.⁴¹

While there have been negative effects as a result of the covid-19 pandemic, in other ways the pandemic has encouraged progress in education in the region, including through the uptake of technology and an increasing number of online courses and

³⁶ Marcelo Becerra, Juan Diego Alonso, and Micheline Frias, *Latin America and the Caribbean: Tertiary Education; COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS RESPONSE* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240911164841/https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/738931611934489480-0090022021/original/LACTEandCovidupdated.pdf>>.

³⁷ 'What Do We Know About Latin America's Lowest-Performing Education Systems? - The Dialogue', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240830001729/https://www.thedialogue.org/blogs/2019/04/latin-americas-lowest-performing-education-systems/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

³⁸ P. Attewell, K.S. Newman (editors) and Cristián Cox, 'EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY IN LATIN AMERICA. PATTERNS, POLICIES AND ISSUES.', in *Growing Gaps. Educational Inequality Around the World*. (Oxford University Press: Oxford, New York), p. Chapter 2 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240630102311/https://liderazgoeducativo.udp.cl/cms/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Educational-inequality-in-Latin-America-patterns-policies-and-issues.-Oxford-University-Press-New-York-2010..pdf>>.

³⁹ UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report, 'Latin America and the Caribbean - 2020 GEM Report' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240819001138/https://gem-report-2020.unesco.org/latin-america-and-the-caribbean/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁴⁰ Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 'Latin America and the Caribbean Must Address Crisis in Learning If It Wants to Move towards More Productive, Inclusive, Sustainable and Democratic Development' (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean) <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241002203140/https://www.cepal.org/en/news/latin-america-and-caribbean-must-address-crisis-learning-if-it-wants-move-towards-more>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁴¹ Marcelo Becerra, Juan Diego Alonso, and Micheline Frias, *Latin America and the Caribbean: Tertiary Education; COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS RESPONSE*.

resources.^{42,43} Increased use of technology can aid effective teaching and is key for a skilled workforce particularly in technology sectors like biotechnology and biomanufacturing.

Target Skill Areas for Improvement

To support biomanufacturing and biotechnology, key areas identified for improvement in both secondary and tertiary education in many South American countries are practical skills in science, as well as the development of creative design and critical thinking skills. The lack of resources for universities and schools can limit the scope of the practicals that can be offered, with students not exposed to the latest equipment and techniques at undergraduate level practicals until undertaking research projects in a specific area. Innovative and open source low cost solutions and collaborative efforts can be utilised alongside funding to help tackle this.

Computation is an increasingly integral part of biotechnology and biomanufacturing research, and therefore there is also a need to increase the computational, bioinformatics and mathematical skills for those in the biosciences. While the development of these skills is currently limited for those taking traditional biological courses, progress is being made in many universities through the provision of new modules and courses.

A focus on skills and critical thinking rather than content in science courses could increase the potential of the workforce in the biomanufacturing and biotechnology sectors. Examinations which also emphasise the importance of critical thinking rather than content is important in combination with teaching that develops these skills.⁴⁴

Case study: Protera - A Biotech Harnessing AI for protein Design

Protera, a biotech company founded in Santiago, Chile, in 2015, is a leader in protein design innovation, having developed madi™, an AI platform for protein engineering that leverages advanced large language models. Madi™ uses both unsupervised and supervised deep learning to generate embeddings of protein sequences, preserving critical sequence, chemical, and structural information for faster and more accurate searches. It can detect functional patterns in proteins with low sequence homology, enabling a deeper understanding of structure-function relationships. The platform can be used to develop candidate proteins for various applications, evaluating properties like solubility, stability,

⁴² 'Higher Education Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20231221055036/https://www.holoniq.com/notes/higher-education-digital-transformation-in-latin-america-and-the-caribbean-1>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁴³ Staff and students at Universities in Brazil, Argentina and Chile.

⁴⁴ 'Staff and Students at Universities in Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

and allergenicity to identify optimal options. As well as providing subscription to their platform, Protera has also developed their first product, “protera guard™”, an antifungal peptide alternative to the chemicals used to increase the shelf life of packaged bread.

Protera was initially supported by CORFO grants (Chilean Economic Development Agency) and joined the US based IndieBio accelerator in 2016, and has grown to over 30 employees. The decision was made to develop a pilot plant to scale up production near Paris in France in partnership with the French venture capital Sofinnova, due to the expertise in the region.

CTO and co-founder Leonardo Álvarez, noted that computation is becoming a core tool for the next generation of biologists, and traditional biological courses have not provided these skills. The majority of employees were noted to have come from mathematics and computer science backgrounds before learning the biology required, with the inverse process more difficult.⁴⁵

Entrepreneurship Training

The availability of business and entrepreneurship training for individuals within science courses, both undergraduate and postgraduate, is one area for improvement, and where courses are available, uptake can be low because of other pressures on students. Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are new and growing fields where entrepreneurship skills, and an understanding of business, intellectual property, regulation and ethics can be beneficial. This fact has been recognised by university teachers as well as technology transfer offices within universities, and progress is being made to offer and advertise more of these courses as well as spread information about infrastructure being put in place.⁴⁶ It is important to include information on open source technology, open access, community funding and ethics alongside information on patenting, different forms of licensing, venture capital and business to enable students and researchers to make appropriate decisions regarding their technology.

Case Study: Online Entrepreneurship Courses at Universidade de São Paulo

The University of Sao Paulo (USP) had developed many entrepreneurship courses prior to the covid-19 pandemic, and was reportedly offering over 100 different courses conducted by different departments. However, analysis at the AUSPIN innovation agency (Agência USP de Inovação), indicated that the uptake of courses by undergraduate and postgraduate students was in fact low with under 5% of all students taking such courses. During the

⁴⁵ ‘Home • Protera’, 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241002135606/https://www.proterabio.com/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁴⁶ Interviews with researchers and Technology Transfer offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile.

pandemic, a move to online and more flexible courses resulted in a large increase in uptake. Following this, novel consolidated courses were developed by AUSPIN, open to students from all departments with the majority of teaching online. Moreover, through bringing together individuals from multiple different courses and skill sets in one place, the group activities and ideas generated were reported to be much richer.⁴⁷

Courses in Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing

Specific courses on biotechnology and biomanufacturing, and modules within other courses like Biology and Chemical Engineering, are increasing the exposure of undergraduate students to biomanufacturing and better equipping students to enter the sector. Biomanufacturing and bioengineering are interdisciplinary and collaborative industries requiring a wide variety of skill sets and therefore exposure to the field in a wide range of STEM (Science Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) courses as well as collaborative projects between students on different courses could aid development of the skills required. There has also been a move in educators to try to better equip students for industry and other fields, in addition to preparing them for roles in academia.

From a postgraduate perspective, biotechnology and biomanufacturing masters courses are limited, but are also increasing in numbers. Postgraduate researchers are trained in more depth and develop the required skills to use the latest equipment independently. Many jobs in the sector worldwide require a postgraduate degree as a prerequisite, and within South America this is also often the case. For this reason, developing biotechnology and biomanufacturing courses further at the postgraduate level will aid the development of a skilled workforce that can be employed in the field.

Broader difficulties with funding and infrastructure of laboratories can also leave an impact on training particularly at the postgraduate level but also at the undergraduate level. A lack of funding can limit the ability of laboratories to host students for research projects, and also reduce access of students to equipment and training in the latest techniques.⁴⁸

Case Study: Biotechnology courses with practical content through the Covid-19 pandemic, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile

The Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile has developed multiple courses related to biomanufacturing and biotechnology in STEM subjects including modules within the biochemistry degree course, and the "Prototype Design in Bioengineering (IBM2026)"

⁴⁷ Luiz Catalani, Director of AUSPIN.

⁴⁸ 'Staff and Students at Universities in Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

taken by engineering students who major or minor in biomedicine. Topics and practicals covered in various courses range from DNA assembly and protein production to microscopy and open source hardware. In order to support students of the biochemistry course during the Covid-19 pandemic, Fernán Federici and colleagues developed a kit including open source hardware components, to enable students to conduct experiments from home. It was noted that despite not having in person support, students obtained critical thinking and problem solving skills that were often missing in traditional lab classes, where students follow protocols at the same time to come to a predefined goal. Taking forward and trying to develop these skills in more practicals will better equip students for jobs within the sector.^{49,50}

Collaborating with Industry to Address Skill Gaps

Many biotechnology companies do still report the difficulty in finding individuals with complete skill sets in regions in South America, and some companies reported the greater need to train staff for their requirements.⁵¹ Interaction with biotechnology industrial partners to help determine the skill shortfalls and collaboratively produce courses which fill those gaps, as well as programmes where students intern in industry as part of their course, are both methods that can ensure that skills generated fit well with the requirements of the private sector. One example of this joint training is the Doctorate in Engineering and Science with Industry programme at the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile.⁵²

Programmes for Training Abroad

Individuals training abroad and returning to South America have enabled many skills to be developed and brought to the region. The Science without borders programme in Brazil between 2011 and 2016, aimed to support training abroad and has had mixed reviews. The programme was also not continued long term. Many of the reported shortfalls of the programme can be addressed, and the lessons learnt implemented to maximise the benefits of such exchanges⁵³ (see Case Study: Science Without Borders, page 31). Other programs for overseas scholarships at present include "Becas Chile"

⁴⁹ 'Teaching Chemistry Labs from a Distance | ACS Central Science'

<<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscentsci.1c00539>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁵⁰ Ariel Cerda and others, 'Open Educational Resources for Distributed Hands-on Teaching in Molecular Biology' (bioRxiv, 2024), p. 2024.03.28.587173, doi:10.1101/2024.03.28.587173.

⁵¹ Interviews with SMEs in Brazil and Chile, 2024.

⁵² 'Doctorado En Ingeniería y Ciencias Con La Industria (Ex Doctorado En Ingeniería y Tecnología)', *Escuela de Graduados*

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209220344/https://doctorados.uc.cl/programa/doctorado-en-ingenieria-y-ciencias-con-la-industria/>> [accessed 9 December 2024].

⁵³ Concepta Mcmanus and Carlos A. Nobre, 'Brazilian Scientific Mobility Program - Science without Borders* - Preliminary Results and Perspectives**', *Anais Da Academia Brasileira de Ciências*, 89 (2017), pp. 773–86, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201720160829>.

scholarships for Master's and doctoral degrees outside Chile⁵⁴ and scholarships in Argentina⁵⁵. Many founders and leading personnel in biotechnology companies within the region have received some training abroad, indicating that the resultant broadening perspectives and exchange of new technologies can stimulate innovation and progress. Exchange programmes are also a successful part of the European and American education systems fostering exchanges of ideas, collaborations and broadening of horizons.⁵⁶ Particularly, a focus on postgraduate education and training abroad could support establishment of collaborations and development of skills. In addition, encouragement of foreign researchers to visit South America through promoting visiting faculty positions, short fellowships for foreign scholars, and other schemes, will help bring further expertise and development to the region.

Case Study: Science Without Borders, Brazil

Brazil's Science without Borders programme was launched in 2011, with the aim of supporting over 100,000 students in STEM subjects to study abroad over a period of four years. The programme's focus was on placing undergraduates and postgraduates in top foreign institutions. A large number of students benefited from this programme between 2011 and 2016 and following the exchanges have brought back new skills, contacts with foreign institutions and a different perspective.⁵⁷ Benefits for students in the programme included a six month optional language course, a one year sandwich year abroad, as well as a 2 month internship at a foreign university, laboratory or technology company. The undergraduate students who took up the programme were reported to have a more than 4 times greater rate of entrance into postgraduate education and lower income families were also reported to be well represented in the programme.⁵⁸ On the other hand criticisms of the programme included the fact that in particular undergraduates (79 percent of awards) had insufficient english proficiency for certain courses abroad, and that not enough thought was given to how courses abroad would fit in with students' degree programmes.⁵⁹ This resulted in sub-optimal learning abroad. Ultimately the programme was also financially unsustainable. Learning from this programme, targeted programmes for exchange which

⁵⁴ National Commission for Scientific and Technological Research CONICYT, *Chile: Opportunities for International Cooperation in STI*, 2015

<https://web.archive.org/web/20240701122916/https://www.conicyt.cl/pci/files/2015/08/OPORTUNIDADES_Aug-2015-completo_spreads.pdf>.

⁵⁵ 'Bec.Ar | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240529030741/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/becar/en>> [accessed 10 December 2024].

⁵⁶ 'Studying Abroad - Erasmus+'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241203045228/https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/opportunities/opportunities-for-individuals/students/studying-abroad>> [accessed 10 December 2024].

⁵⁷ SeTIC-UFSC, 'Science Without Borders, Secretaria de Relações Internacionais | Office of International Relations'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20211019083513/https://sinter.ufsc.br/programa-ciencia-sem-fronteiras/?lang=en>> [accessed 10 December 2024].

⁵⁸ Mcmanus and Nobre, 'Brazilian Scientific Mobility Program - Science without Borders* - Preliminary Results and Perspectives**'.

⁵⁹ Creso M. Sá, 'The Rise and Fall of Brazil's Science Without Borders', *International Higher Education*, 85, 2016, pp. 17–18, doi:10.6017/ihe.2016.85.9241.

are financially sustainable, for example focused on postgraduate education initially, along with clear support strategies and preparation for students will maximise benefits of such exchange programmes.

Workforce Mobility between Public and Private Sector

Mobility of the workforce between industry and academia can be difficult internationally, however in many South American countries it can be particularly difficult. In particular a return to academia from industry is often seen as not possible. This is in part due to the requirement for publications and an academic history when applying for academic roles. Furthermore in South America, where tenured positions are common and stable employment within academia, although the benefits of greater salaries are attractive, the risk involved in moving to the private sector from academia is seen as high for some academics. Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are fields where this inter-transfer of personnel and movement of expertise between industry and academia may be particularly beneficial, and therefore addressing this through changes to recruitment policies is key. Providing some capacity for intermittences in tenure to work in related industry, in particular for less senior members of academia, may provide some security and greater interest in movement between industry and academia with minimal cost to the state.⁶⁰

Outlook: A growing Biotech Sector Will Retain a Skilled Workforce

Overall in the region, the private biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors are still small. Many individuals have reported the lack of opportunities for employment within the sector. This results in trained and skilled labour moving abroad to or leaving the sector. As the private biotechnology sector grows, so will the pool of skilled labour. Similarly, the greater the diversity of companies, the greater the diversity of skills that will be developed.

⁶⁰ Academics and biotechnology industry members in Argentina, Brazil, and Chile, Interviews were conducted in 2024.

Academic Research

Alongside the development of an increasingly skilled science labour force, cutting edge academic research is developing in many South American institutions in a range of fields within the biosciences. Not only is the quantity of publications growing rapidly, but South American research also has an increasing international presence and impact with publications in leading journals increasing in number from year to year (Figure 6).⁶¹ Increasing collaboration within the region as well as internationally is also evident.

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing specific basic and translational research is also progressing in a similar way, with research in biomaterials, biosensors, metabolic engineering, bioprocess engineering, and protein engineering just a few fields where leading research groups can be found within the region. While there are significant differences from country to country, and institution to institution, in terms of infrastructure, availability of latest equipment, and financing, South American researchers find innovative ways to conduct valuable research with the resources available. The development of simple and innovative low cost and low resource biotechnological solutions in response to limitations in resources can be seen as a strength of South American Research. These innovative solutions can have significant advantages when taken to market, and can be competitive internationally.

Another particular strength of the region is both basic and translational research related to the local context, including research in tropical diseases, biodiversity and environmental research, and research related to local industries. Through harnessing biotechnology and biomanufacturing, there is the potential for this research to be translated into real world solutions to local problems. Continuing to support academic research, and building upon its strengths, is key to supporting biomanufacturing and biotechnology sectors.

Diverse Research of Increasing Quantity and Quality

A diverse range of biotechnology related research is being conducted in South America, as illustrated by the top ten Web of Science categories related to biotechnology articles with authors from the region (Figure 6A). Applied microbiology, biochemistry, agronomy, food sciences and plant sciences are all examples of fields where the region actively contributes. Academic interviewees for this report similarly researched diverse topics including bioprocess engineering, metabolic engineering, biosensors,

⁶¹ Jonathan Adams and others, *Global Research Report: Latin America: South and Central America, Mexico and the Caribbean*; (Institute for Scientific Information) <https://web.archive.org/web/20240812185033/https://clarivate.com/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2022/09/IS-I-GRR-Q3-2021-LatAm_Report_EN_Report_Digital_V5-1-1-2.pdf> [accessed 12 December 2024].

computational protein design, and low cost and open source hardware to name a few. The top 20 affiliations for research article authors, according to Web of Science analysis of biotechnology publications from the region, heavily features Brazilian institutions, however Chilean and Argentinian institutions are also represented (Figure 6B). This reflects the number of scientists and funding situation in the different countries, with these three countries being historically the largest players in the region. UK, French, US, and Spanish funders and institutions are also represented, indicating that international collaborations with these countries play an important role in biotechnology research by academics in the region. The number of biotechnology articles have increased (Figure 6C), and number of highly cited papers (*“papers that perform in the top 1% based on the number of citations received when compared to other papers published in the same field in the same year”*)⁶², one possible measure of the quality and influence of publications, generally seem to be increasing. Of note, is the peak number of highly cited papers in 2016 (Figure 6D).

Figure 6: Web of Science Query for Biotechnology Research articles with a South American country/region.⁶³ The data was used to display: A) The top 10 topics of biotechnology

⁶² Clarivate Analytics, ‘Researcher/Faculty - Essential Science Indicators - LibGuides at Clarivate Analytics’ <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240924033210/https://clarivate.libguides.com/c.php?g=593878&p=4107961>> [accessed 9 January 2025].

⁶³ Clarivate Analytics, ‘Web of Science; Search: Biotechnology (All Fields) and Article (Document Types) and BRAZIL or ARGENTINA or CHILE or COLOMBIA or PERU or BOLIVIA or ECUADOR or

research articles published by authors with South American affiliations as of 2025; B) The top 20 affiliations of biotechnology research articles with a South American affiliated author, displaying foreign institutes and funding bodies in dark blue; C) The number of biotechnology articles published by a South American author per year (2005-2024); D) The data was further filtered for highly cited papers and used to present the number of highly cited research biotechnology research articles published by a South America affiliated author per year (2014-2022).

Research Related to the Local Context and Environment

Research related to the local context and environment is a particular strength of South America. Two examples of fields where the region leads in research are:

Tropical Diseases and Their Therapeutics

South America has some of the leading research in tropical diseases and their therapeutics. Basic research into tropical diseases and their pathogenesis is a key foundation for the development of translational research in the field. Both this basic research and the subsequent translational research is a strength of South America. This research has the potential to directly benefit local people.

An example of this from Brazil is the basic and translational research into the Zika virus, a mosquito-borne virus, which caused an epidemic in Brazil from 2015-2016. This virus can cause infant microcephaly when pregnant women are infected. Much basic research into the virus has been conducted in Brazil, including at the University of Sao Paulo, and Instituto Butantan. Instituto Butantan has been developing a Zika vaccine, aiming to reduce the risk of future outbreaks.^{64,65} Similarly in Argentina there has been important research including at Instituto Leloir into the Dengue virus, an outbreak of which occurred in 2024.^{66,67}

Research into Biodiversity and the Environment

As discussed in the biodiversity section (page 14), South America has some of the most biodiverse habitats on the planet. A 2024 Elsevier report into biodiversity research

GUYANA or FRENCH GUIANA or FALKLAND ISLAND or PARAGUAY or URUGUAY or VENEZUELA or SURINAME (Countries/Regions) Date Run: Thu Jan 09 2025 16:32:43 GMT+0000 (Greenwich Mean Time) Results: 15384'.

⁶⁴ Danielle B. L. Oliveira and others, 'Persistence and Intra-Host Genetic Evolution of Zika Virus Infection in Symptomatic Adults: A Special View in the Male Reproductive System', *Viruses*, 10.11 (2018), p. 615, doi:10.3390/v10110615.

⁶⁵ Renata Gois de Mello and others, 'Zika Virus-like Particles (VLPs) Produced in Insect Cells', *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 14 (2023), doi:10.3389/fphar.2023.1181566.

⁶⁶ Diego E. Alvarez and others, 'Long-Range RNA-RNA Interactions Circularize the Dengue Virus Genome', *Journal of Virology*, 79.11 (2005), pp. 6631-43, doi:10.1128/jvi.79.11.6631-6643.2005.

⁶⁷ 'PAHO Highlights Increase in Dengue, Oropouche, and Avian Influenza Cases in the Americas, and Advises Control Measures - PAHO/WHO | Pan American Health Organization', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241211164744/https://www.paho.org/en/news/10-12-2024-paho-highlights-increase-dengue-oropouche-and-avian-influenza-cases-americas-and#:~:text=Dengue%3A%20Historic%20epidemic%20in%20the%20Americas&text=Countries%20have%20reported%20more%20than,Brazil%20having%20the%20argest%20share.>> [accessed 12 December 2024].

indicated that South America is a key player in biodiversity research, with the region having three times the global average activity for research in this sector.⁶⁸ This research is a great strength, and can form the foundation for protecting this vital resource, and for future translational research.

⁶⁸ Paola Barr and others, *Biodiversity Research in 2024; A Global Perspective with a Focus on Latin America* (Elsevier, 2024)
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241212161826/https://assets.ctfassets.net/zlnfaxb2lcqx/6G90mMrjWGpDpSoKQKaNRS/e59f74b825b235749c0d2231c26cdb63/Elsevier-biodiversity-research-report-2024.pdf>>.

Financing

Figure 7: Financing mechanisms for different stages of technology development split into government financing, Private sector financing, and government fiscal incentives.

Overview

Overall R&D spend including public and private sector spending in South American countries is significantly lower than in leading economies worldwide, though there is significant heterogeneity within the region. This is also the case for spending on biotechnology and biomanufacturing R&D. Gradually increasing government R&D spend and encouraging increased private sector investment to move towards a target of 2% of GDP, alongside targeted financial support for biotechnology, biomanufacturing and the life sciences, is key to supporting the sector. This sector specific government financing requires targeting basic and translational research in the life sciences as well as infrastructure to form a strong foundation for the sector. In addition, financing for biotechnology and biomanufacturing start-ups and SMEs (Small and medium enterprises) is vital at all stages of research, from feasibility study to proof of principle, scale up, and commercialisation, as well as all scales, from small grants and seed funds to larger funding. This can be met both by the public sector, as well as by encouraging private sector investment. In addition to direct financing, fiscal incentives are also a good strategy to support R&D. They are increasingly used worldwide, and can be specifically targeted at biotechnology and biomanufacturing.

Figure 8: Research and Development spending as a proportion of GDP in Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Chile, China, the Republic of Korea, and the United States from 2005-2021. R&D spending in South America has not increased and is significantly below a 2% of GDP target. In the same period R&D spending has increased significantly in all other countries represented, most notably in the Republic of Korea, where R&D spend in 2021 was 4.93% of GDP. Data from the Unesco institute for Statistics⁶⁹

Basic Research Financing

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are novel fields which often rely on basic research in the life sciences as a foundation. Foundational research in many fields including disease and pathogenesis, physiology, zoology, molecular and cell biology, and biochemistry, form the basis for identifying targets for translational research with real world implications. This research will not be funded by the private sector and therefore relies on strong public sector support to ensure continued development. Many South American countries do finance basic academic research in the life sciences and biotechnology, with individual countries' funding bodies and mechanisms discussed further in the country by country section (Appendix I). However, financing within many countries has fluctuated significantly depending on political and economic outlook, with Brazil and Argentina, the two largest economies, both experiencing funding cuts and

⁶⁹ UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). UIS.Stat Bulk Data Download Service. Accessed September 30, 2024., 'Research and Development Expenditure (% of GDP) - Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, United States, China, Korea, Rep. | Data | World Bank Group', 2025 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250109203431/https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/GB.XPD.RSDV.GD.ZS?end=2021&locations=AR-BR-CL-CO-EC-US-CN-KR&start=2008> ; <https://web.archive.org/web/20241202100550/https://api.worldbank.org/v2/en/indicator/GB.XPD.RSDV.GD.ZS?downloadformat=csv>>.

instability.^{70,71} This instability results in loss of benefits through incomplete research and loss of talent and expertise. Countries which have had increased financial stability have fared better, even with lower average spending. For this reason, not only is it important to gradually increase financing, but it is also essential to try to maintain stable and regular funding.

Translational Research Financing

Many countries in South America have insufficient funding for translational research meaning many potential innovations and solutions utilising biotechnology and biomanufacturing do not progress further. The comparative balance between funding for translational research and basic research varies from country to country (see Appendix 1 for country by country outlook). Financing schemes for translational research are however increasing in number and many countries in the regions have highlighted biotechnology as a target industry for translational research.

Many governmental translational research funding schemes in South America including those targeted at academic laboratories, require contributions from the private sector. This can range from 50% in match funding schemes, to as low as 10% in other schemes.^{72,73,74} These schemes can be effective in drawing private sector investment as well as in promoting technology transfer and the development of research towards commercialisation. In addition, it promotes communication between academia and industry, though a barrier to the success of these schemes in some regions can be the bureaucracy involved in setting up partnerships (discussed further in the technology transfer section).

On the other hand, within biomanufacturing and biotechnology, it can be difficult for academic labs to secure a private sector partner due to the lack of companies within the region involved in the sector, and also more specifically the subsector of the research. Biotechnology is still a relatively novel and growing sector within the region consisting of many startups which may not be in the position to partner in this way. It can also be very difficult, though not impossible, to draw investment from larger international players, as these companies focus R&D investment in other regions such as Europe and

⁷⁰ Alicia J. Kowaltowski, 'Brazil's Scientists Face 90% Budget Cut', *Nature*, 598.7882 (2021), pp. 566–566, doi:10.1038/d41586-021-02882-z.

⁷¹ Julian Reingold, 'Argentinian Scientists Condemn Budget Cuts Ahead of Protests', *Climate Home News*, 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240826024947/https://www.climatechangenews.com/2024/04/22/argentinian-scientists-condemn-budget-cuts-ahead-of-university-protests/>> [accessed 12 December 2024].

⁷² 'CORFO - Corporación de Fomento de la Producción', *CORFO* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241112221306/https://www.corfo.cl/sites/cpp/webingles>> [accessed 12 December 2024].

⁷³ 'Who We Are - Embrapii' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230207153600/https://embrapii.org.br/en/institutional/who-we-are/>> [accessed 12 December 2024].

⁷⁴ Sonia K. Guimaraes and Regis L.G. Barcelos, 'Brazilian Company for Industrial Research and Innovation: A New Generation of STI Policy Mechanisms for the Modernisation of the Productive Sector', *Science, Technology and Society*, 28.2 (2023), pp. 297–318, doi:10.1177/09717218221125925.

North America. In addition, biotechnology and biomanufacturing are relatively higher risk fields and have higher research costs than other fields, with much translational research still further away from being applicable to the market. This means there are lower incentives for private investment. For this reason, alongside translational research requiring private partners, it is important to also have more completely publicly funded mechanisms for early stage academic translational research in biotechnology and biomanufacturing. This publicly funded translational research must also have effective technology transfer mechanisms for generating spin-outs after the research is conducted. Currently, many researchers within biomanufacturing and biotechnology must generate startups and sometimes must even gain investment before conducting translational research, a significant hurdle which puts off many researchers, and also limits the risks undertaken. This can reduce the pace of developments in the region and prevent some of the most innovative ideas being taken forward. Smaller grants to fill the gaps in financing between larger grants, or complete additional stages are also important for translational research.

In the case of intellectual property arising as a result of translational research, many governments in South America do have financing mechanisms to support universities, companies, and researchers when applying for patents, however these can be limited and competitive in some locations.⁷⁵ Where there is no funding source for institutions to apply for and maintain patents, universities in many locations must utilise their own funds which are often under strain. This can prevent and delay patenting, and limit the movement from translational research in universities to real world application.

Financing Infrastructure

In addition to financing specific research projects, it is important for governments to also financially support the generation and maintenance of infrastructure required for biomanufacturing and biotechnology. This can include funds to ensure laboratory buildings are maintained, as well as funds specifically for purchasing and maintenance of expensive equipment which can be offered in shared facilities. This includes smaller equipment like HPLCS to Mass Spectrometers, Electron microscopes and NMR machines, all the way to synchrotron light sources at the other end of the scale. There is also a need for financing of Transport and customs infrastructure and scale up infrastructure which are discussed further in the infrastructure section.

⁷⁵ 'Finep Propriedade Intelectual'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214190741/http://www.finep.gov.br/apoio-e-financiamento-externa/programas-e-linhas/finep-propriedade-intelectual>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

Start-up and SME Financing

Start-ups and SMEs require funding for multiple stages of research, including feasibility study, proof of principle, and scale up and commercialisation. Financing is also similarly required at multiple scales from small grants and seed funds to large grants. Good ecosystems contain both private sector and public sector financing for this. There are multiple successful grant schemes for Startups and SMEs, one notable scheme being the phased grants provided by FAPESP in Sao Paulo.⁷⁶ Public sector financing need not be limited to grants, but can also include loans and investments.

Private sector seed funding and Series A funding from venture capital is still limited, however there is increasing interest in the region (see Zentyne case study, page 59). The Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent high inflation and interest rates have hampered this development due to the move towards lower risk investments, however renewed interest is likely in the foreseeable future. On the other hand, larger scale funding including Series-B and Series-C funding is very difficult to acquire within the region, and is not supported by the public sector. For this reason, many start-ups with this strategy for growth register their businesses in North America, and look to North American investors to provide this funding.⁷⁷

Case Study: FAPESP Innovative Research in Small Business Program, Phased Grants

FAPESP (Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo), is the state research foundation of the Brazilian State of Sao Paulo, which supports scientific and technological research through grants as well as scholarships for students. The constitution of the state stipulates that 1% of all state tax revenue be used to support research and these funds are distributed through FAPESP. FAPESP programmes include 'BIOTA', a programme to characterise and conserve biodiversity within the state, the 'Research Support Program in Partnership for Technological Innovation' (PITE), and the 'FAPESP Innovative Research in Small Businesses Program' (PIPE).⁷⁸

The PIPE Small business funding programme, originally created in 1997, supports innovative scientific and technological research in small businesses of under 250 employees within Sao Paulo. The grant system consists of three main phases. Phase 1 grants are for up to three hundred thousand reais (~60,000 USD in September 2024) and

⁷⁶ FAPESP, 'PROGRAMA FAPESP PESQUISA INOVATIVA EM PEQUENAS EMPRESAS - PIPE' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240804141600/https://fapesp.br/58/programa-fapesp-pesquisa-inovativa-em-pequenas-empresas-pipe>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁷⁷ Interviews with Startups in the region, University Technology Transfer Offices, and a venture capital firm.

⁷⁸ FAPESP, 'The São Paulo Research Foundation' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241008083745/https://fapesp.br/en/about>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

a period of up to 9 months and support research into technical-scientific feasibility. Phase 2 grants which can either be directly applied for or follow a phase 1 grant, are for up to 1.5 million reais (~225,000 USD in September 2024) and support development of the research innovation and market support activities for up to 24 months. PIPE invest provides additional funds for Phase 1 or 2 projects which have demonstrated success and attracted private investment. Phase 3 grants are for continued commercialisation and industrial development of innovative products and is supported by FINEP, the federal funding agency.^{79,80}

These phased grants have been reported by multiple biotechnology startups within Sao Paulo state to be effective support for R&D and product development. The phased system with different sizes of grant for SMEs at different research stages, maximises their impact.⁸¹

Case Study: Bioprocess Improvement

Bioprocess Improvement is a startup founded in 2018, based in Campinas, Brazil, and incubated at UNICAMP Universidade Estadual de Campinas. The company focuses on industrial biotechnological processes and develops platform-based projects applicable across various sectors. It has a global presence and multiple projects funded by FAPESP under the PIPE program. Key services provided by the company include biological control of industrial fermentations, contaminant monitoring, renewable bioproduct production, virtual process prototyping, AI-based virtual sensors, digital twins for industrial processes, and consulting and training services.⁸²

Fiscal Incentives

In addition to direct financing, fiscal incentives are an increasingly used mechanism internationally to promote research and development, in particular in the private sector. In the UK for example, direct government funding for BERD (Business enterprise expenditure on R&D) accounts for 0.15% of GDP, whereas BERD attributed to Tax reductions account for more than double this value at 0.33% of GDP. Brazil is one notable example in the South American region where Tax incentives account for a larger proportion of government support for BERD than direct investment.⁸³ Both general fiscal incentives, and those targeted to biomanufacturing and biotechnology,

⁷⁹ FAPESP, 'PROGRAMA FAPESP PESQUISA INOVATIVA EM PEQUENAS EMPRESAS - PIPE'.

⁸⁰ 'Finep e FAPESP Disponibilizam R\$ 30 Milhões Para Pesquisas Em Pequenas Empresas', *ABES*, 2018 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214192133/https://abes.com.br/en/finep-e-fapesp-disponibilizam-r-30-milhoes-para-pesquisas-em-pequenas-empresas/>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁸¹ Interviews with multiple Startups and academics in São Paulo State.

⁸² 'Vencemos o Prêmio Brasil Bioeconomia! – Bioprocess Improvement' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214192846/https://bioprocessimprovement.com/en/vencemos-o-premio-brasil-bioeconomia/>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁸³ 'R&D Tax Incentives', *OECD* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240411162656/https://www.oecd.org/innovation/tax-incentives-rd-innovation/>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

can aid increasing R&D spending and therefore innovation. In addition to reduced taxes for start-ups and SMEs, amortisation of equipment, and R&D tax rebates, can both be effective strategies to support biotechnology and biomanufacturing companies. For public sector academic research in particular, but also potentially for the private sector, reducing VAT and import taxes for biological reagents used in R&D could also support the sector. Due to the limited local production of reagents, R&D relies on imports, and import taxes in the region can be significantly higher than in other regions globally. Where tax rebates and reductions apply, effective infrastructure to enable rapid implementation is necessary. There have been reports from multiple regions where these incentives do exist, that either they cannot be taken advantage of due to limited infrastructure for implementation, or that the applications result in long delays reducing their effectiveness.⁸⁴

Case study: Argentina Law for Targeted Fiscal Benefits for Biotechnology and Nanotechnology

In Argentina, a law passed in September 2022 supports targeted tax relief for Biotechnology and Nanotechnology companies through accelerated amortisation of equipment, VAT refunds and tax credit bonds equivalent to 50% of the expenses for hiring research services from public science institutions.⁸⁵

⁸⁴ Interviews with Academics in Brazil, Argentina and Chile, 2024.

⁸⁵ Baker McKenzie, 'Argentina: Promotion of Modern Biotechnology and Nanotechnology' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20221130133523/https://insightplus.bakermckenzie.com/bm/tax/argentina-promotion-of-modern-biotechnology-and-nanotechnology>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

Technology Transfer and Startup Ecosystems

Overview

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are rapidly developing fields with many social, environmental and economic implications. Much research occurs within universities and public institutions. In order for this research to be applied for the benefit of society, in many cases (though importantly not all) the commercialisation of this research is necessary. Incentivising commercialisation of technology requires effective technology transfer processes which balances the complex interests of all parties involved. When effective, this process can create great benefits for the local economy, generating wealth and jobs, and can benefit society, health, and the environment through the application of beneficial technologies. However, when unsuccessful or inefficient, it can hamper the development of ideas beyond research and limit any benefits of the research for society.

Technology transfer involves many different components and processes including intellectual property and its transfer or licensing; material transfer including biological material, data, and software; and knowhow and expertise transfer including through consultancy.

Technology transfer and public private sector collaboration has long been seen as a weakness of South America. Whilst technology transfer from the public to the private sector has grown and improved significantly, it remains a hurdle described by academics, technology transfer offices (TTOs) as well as industrial players.

Legislation, Regulation and Processes for Filing Patents and Licencing

Patenting, enables the owner of Intellectual property (IP) to exclude others from profiting from the intellectual property in exchange for disclosure of the invention. This is a mechanism intended to foster innovation, collaboration, and commercialisation, while allowing development of the field by reducing secrecy and trade secrets.⁸⁶ This process of patenting followed by licensing or selling IP enables academic institutions including universities to benefit directly from the intellectual property generated as a product of research. Intellectual property protection is key to biotechnology and

⁸⁶ ALRC, 'Economic Benefits of the Patent System; Genes and Ingenuity: Gene Patenting and Human Health (ALRC Report 99)' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240715203425/https://www.alrc.gov.au/publication/genes-and-ingenuity-gene-patenting-and-human-health-alrc-report-99/2-the-patent-system/economic-benefits-of-the-patent-system/>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

biomanufacturing in the same way as in many other technology intensive fields, however due to the unique biological aspects, there has been considerable ongoing debate and discussion as to the standards and policy with regards to what is patentable.^{87,88} In part due to the high capital investment and risk, private investors in biotechnology start-ups often look for held IP, licences, or the potential for IP.

Both the transfer of IP as well as the primary use of IP generated by industry is limited by inefficient and slow patent processes. In many countries in South America, there have been updates to the regulations aiming to address this and reduce bureaucracy and backlogs. South American countries are also rapidly modernising patent law to align more closely with international standards, becoming members of the PCT (Patent Cooperation Treaty), and implementing the best practices recommended in international agreements including TRIPS (Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights). Brazil, Uruguay and Chile are all examples of countries which have recently or are in the process of reforming patent laws and processes, with Uruguay moving to join the PCT.^{89,90} A notable country which is not a member of the PCT is Argentina, which also has quite restrictive patent laws applied to pharmaceuticals and biotechnology.^{91,92}

While local companies with sufficient capital can and often do pursue patents in foreign markets including the US, unfavourable local intellectual property landscapes hamper the technology transfer from foreign entities to local entities, as well as can hamper the activity of local institutions that may be unable to finance direct applications in overseas markets. Holding international intellectual property can be particularly beneficial within biomanufacturing and biotechnology where access to global markets can significantly improve prospects. Here, membership of the PCT is beneficial, and collaboration between technology transfer offices and private investors, and funding from

⁸⁷ World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), 'Patent Expert Issues: Biotechnology' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230528095935/https://www.wipo.int/patents/en/topics/biotechnology.html>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁸⁸ Emma Barraclough, 'What Myriad Means for Biotech', *Wipo-Magazine*, 2013 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214195238/https://www.wipo.int/en/web/wipo-magazine/articles/what-myriad-means-for-biotech-38556>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁸⁹ Carlos Casado, 'Uruguay and the PCT: A Strategic Step towards Global Patent Protection - European Commission', 2023 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241211011153/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/uruguay-and-pct-strategic-step-towards-global-patent-protection-2023-12-22_en> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁹⁰ Robert Pocklington, 'New IP Law in Chile (I): Main Changes in the Patent System - European Commission', 2022 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241211011332/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-ip-law-chile-i-main-changes-patent-system-2022-09-16_en> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁹¹ Verónica Canton, 'The Main Challenges When Applying for a Patent in Argentina for EU SMEs - European Commission', 2021 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241021005142/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/main-challenges-when-applying-patent-argentina-eu-smes-2021-11-23_en> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁹² 'Patentes: Integrarnos al Mundo - LA NACION', 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230619071548/https://www.lanacion.com.ar/editoriales/patentes-integrarnos-al-mundo-nid13062023/>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

government grants can support acquisition of international patents. Many governments in South American countries offer grants towards the filing of patents.

Implementation of fair and rapid patent prosecution and litigation processes according to regulation and legislation, in combination with awareness of the laws and processes in both the public (government and academic) and private sectors is also key. Purely legal and regulatory change without application and enforcement is insufficient in boosting innovation through patents. There is still considerable variation in all aspects between countries within South America.

Alongside the patenting process, the regulation of licensing processes by public institutions is also important. Different countries have different regulations concerning technology transfer for public or non profit institutions. By law in many Latin American countries, intellectual property generated as a result of research conducted in government institutes or public universities is public property and is subject to procedures which may in some cases hamper technology transfer processes. This is particularly the case for IP generated initially at a public institution without partnership with a private entity. Changes to innovation laws are taking place to address this.⁹³

Legislation surrounding the capacity of scientists employed by public universities to engage with technology transfer to private entities through consulting and knowledge transfer also varies, with this being restricted by institutional rules and bureaucracy for individuals employed by public institutions in many countries. In some ways, this hampers one strong method of technology transfer to local industry.

Case Study: INPI patent, Brazil

In Brazil, INPI (Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial)⁹⁴ is responsible for the regulation and issuing of patents. INPI has put in place multiple process changes aiming to increase efficiency and streamline the process of issuing patents to reduce the chronic backlog. In 2018 INPI had 207,195 patent applications pending, and the processing of a patent application on average took just over 10 years.⁹⁵ In order to address this, multiple changes have been made and in 2019, a backlog combat plan was introduced, a successful

⁹³ Fabio F. Kujawski and others, 'New Science, Technology And Innovation Act', 2016 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103113254/https://www.mondaq.com/brazil/government-contracts-procurement-ppp/467024/new-science-technology-and-innovation-act8203>> [accessed 14 December 2024].

⁹⁴ Andre Tortato Rauen, *Strengthening Brazil's Innovation Policy through Public Procurement* (ipea - Institute for Applied Economic Research, July 2023), p. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.38116/td2895-eng> <https://web.archive.org/web/20241218160953/https://repositorio.ipea.gov.br/bitstream/11058/12169/1/dp_2895.pdf>.

⁹⁵ Pedro Moreira, 'Updated Landscape on Expedited Protection of "Green" Inventions in Brazil', 2021 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222112822/https://www3.wipo.int/wipogreen/en/news/2021/news_0016.html> [accessed 3 January 2025].

endeavour which reportedly reduced the backlog by 83% by mid 2022.^{96,97} The changes included using technical examinations conducted by foreign patent offices, increasing staff and resources, as well as providing the options for fast tracking of patents in certain fields including for example green technologies with the green patents program.^{98,99,100,101} In addition, regulatory process changes including the elimination of the role of ANVISA, the Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency in pre-approval of patents related to pharmaceuticals and health biotechnology will support this sector in particular.^{102,103}

The time taken for approval of patents is still however significantly longer than in other locations, with Chemistry patents which include applications in the pharmaceutical and biotechnology fields particularly affected and accounting for 46 percent of the backlog in 2022. This is in part due to a shortage of examiners in these technical fields.¹⁰⁴ Patents in biotechnology commonly have taken more than 10 years for approval, and have an average examination time of 7-8 years.^{105,106} In addition, the 2021 removal of the ten-year minimum patent term means that patent holders in the biotechnology field may effectively have one of the shortest periods of protection.¹⁰⁷

Progress is ongoing in the field and incremental changes and improvements to support innovation will continue to require discussion and development. In 2023 a “ Dialogue on the

⁹⁶ Pedro Moreira, ‘Updated Landscape on Expedited Protection of “Green” Inventions in Brazil’.

⁹⁷ Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial, ‘Backlog Combat Plan — Instituto Nacional Da Propriedade Industrial’, 2020

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222113442/https://www.gov.br/inpi/en/services/patents/backlog-combat-plan>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

⁹⁸ ‘INPI Updates Examination Rules in Order to Drive down the Patent Backlog - IAM’, 2022

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20231202085440/https://www.iam-media.com/article/inpi-updates-examination-rules-in-order-drive-down-the-patent-backlog>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

⁹⁹ Anjam Aziz, ‘The Time Is Now to Address Brazil’s Notorious Patent Backlog’, 2022

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222114354/https://phrma.org/Blog/the-time-is-now-to-address-brazils-notorious-patent-backlog>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰⁰ KRISTAL TONINI LIBERMAN, YURI C. R. SCHRAMM, and GABRIEL BERETTA DE OLIVEIRA MATTOS, ‘INPI Publishes New Strategic Plan’, 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222114937/https://www.machodomeyer.com.br/en/recent-publications/publications/intellectual-property/inpi-publishes-new-strategic-plan>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰¹ INPI, ‘Activity Report’, 2017

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240216190451/https://www.gov.br/inpi/pt-br/composicao/arquivos/relatorio-de-atividades-inpi-2017-english-version.pdf>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰² Pedro Moreira, ‘Updated Landscape on Expedited Protection of “Green” Inventions in Brazil’.

¹⁰³ Rana Gosain, ‘Recent Reform on Brazilian Pharmaceutical Patents Showing Results | FICPI’, 2022

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222115737/https://ficpi.org/blog/recent-reform-brazilian-pharmaceutical-patents-showing-results>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰⁴ Anjam Aziz, ‘The Time Is Now to Address Brazil’s Notorious Patent Backlog’.

¹⁰⁵ Gabriela Salerno, Clarissa Jaegger, Ana Paula Brito, Stephany Araújo e Maria Eduarda Junqueira, sócias do escritório Montauray Pimenta, Machado & Vieira de Mello, ‘Principais Desenvolvimentos Na Área de Propriedade Intelectual No Brasil Em 2022’, *Análise Editorial*

<<https://en.analise.com/opiniao/principais-desenvolvimentos-na-area-de-propriedade-intelectual-no-brasil-em-2022>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰⁶ Tarso Mesquita Machado, ‘BPTO Now Orders Patent Examinations Based on Date of Submission of Examination Request | FICPI’, 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222120803/https://ficpi.org/ip-news/bpto-now-orders-patent-examinations-based-submission-examination>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁰⁷ PROF. VLADIMIR FERNANDES MACIEL, *The Status of Intellectual Property Rights in Brazil* (CENTRO MACKENZIE DE LIBERDADE ECONÔMICA, BRAZIL, 21 April 2024)

<https://web.archive.org/web/20240421031410/https://pifazacotecer.com.br/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/IPRI_2021_CaseStudy_Brazil_v1_compressed.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025].

Regulation of Biotechnology Patents " took place in Brazil organised by the Ministry of Development, Industry, Trade and Services, INPI and the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, with support from the European Union.^{108,109}

Technology Transfer Offices (TTO)

Technology transfer offices have become key components of the technology transfer ecosystem of universities. They are responsible for:

- overseeing the process of registering intellectual property
- forming and negotiating technology transfer agreements
- publicising research and engaging with industry to facilitate commercialisation of intellectual property through licensing of existing IP or formation of partnerships
- funding university spin-outs or partnering with venture capitalists to promote spin-outs

They are also:

- increasingly involved in the education of students and researchers regarding business and technology transfer processes
- Increasingly involved in making technology transfer decisions that benefit society rather than from a purely economic perspective

The number of South American Universities with TTO's has grown rapidly, such that currently most universities have established TTO's. In some countries like Brazil, universities are mandated to have a TTOs (or TIC - Technology Innovation Centre).¹¹⁰ Alongside the growth in number of TTO's, their experience in the process of technology transfer is also growing. There are however still many challenges faced by TTOs to maximise the effectiveness of technology transfer. It is key to assess effectiveness of technology transfer facilitated by TTOs, not by the number of patents registered, but instead by the commercial success and socio-economic benefits produced as a result.

¹⁰⁸ PROF. VLADIMIR FERNANDES MACIEL, *The Status of Intellectual Property Rights in Brazil*.

¹⁰⁹ 'New Report Presents a Comparative International Study on Biotech Patentability Standards and Criteria | CEPAL', 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222134109/https://www.cepal.org/en/notes/new-report-presents-comparative-international-study-biotech-patentability-standards-and>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹¹⁰ Janaina Aparecida da Silva and Rejane Sartori, 'Motivations and Barriers of University-Industry Cooperation: A Comparison between Brazil and Ireland', *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 17.2 (2022), pp. 49–58, doi:10.4067/S0718-27242022000200049.

Communication

Communication between TTOs and researchers is key to their function. This includes TTO's effectively communicating to researchers and industrial partners the processes in place for technology transfer. In addition, TTO's must be aware of the research going on at their institution and engage with industry to disseminate this information. Both members of industry and academics in some regions have demonstrated hesitancy to engage with technology transfer. This is in part due to the lack of perceived benefits and the limited number of successful examples in biotechnology, but also due to uncertainties surrounding the process. Though much progress is being made through varying publicity initiatives, a lack of interaction between TTOs, researchers, and industry, remains a key issue at many South American institutions. This is exacerbated by the lack of computational infrastructure at some institutions. For example, there is a lack of centralised databases or repositories used by TTOs to document what research is going on, and TTOs often do not have up to date web pages documenting procedures. There is also a lack of more general communication and updates, and long term relationships between TTOs and university researchers and departments at many institutions. Consistent communication between TTOs and researchers raises awareness and lowers the barrier to initiation of contact. Many TTOs are aware of these issues, and are putting in place mechanisms to foster communication, however part of the difficulty of supporting communication is linked to the shortage and regular turnover of staff at many TTOs (see later section).¹¹¹

Bureaucracy

Technology transfer processes conducted by TTOs are slow in part due to the bureaucracy involved and requirement for centralised authorisations through multiple intermediaries. This can particularly be the case in very large institutions where there are both central and sector specific TTOs. Here again, the lack of computational systems integrating multiple departments and offices can also be a factor in prolonging process times.¹¹² Both TTOs and researchers alike have acknowledged the need to accelerate technology transfer processes. Technology transfer and business agreements in rapidly evolving fields like biomanufacturing and biotechnology are highly time sensitive, and the average time required to form and complete agreements has been described by many sources as several months. Where there is international competition, this can be a deciding factor in the success of technology transfer. Pre-templated agreements with scope for some change within boundaries, that can be both disseminated to industry and researchers, and fast-tracked for approval, may also help speed up the process.

¹¹¹ 'Interviews with Researchers and Technology Transfer Offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

¹¹² 'Interviews with Researchers and Technology Transfer Offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

Expertise and Staff Shortages

Many of the issues aforementioned are partly due to staff shortages, high staff turnover, and a lack of specific expertise in rapidly evolving sectors like biomanufacturing and biotechnology. Implementing changes, building relationships with researchers and industry, creating computational infrastructure, creating documentation and efficient processes, and maintaining expertise, is very difficult without the resources required. It is vital to ensure positions within technology transfer offices are attractive for staff to reduce staff turnover and ensure there is employment of a diverse skilled workforce. Investing in the legal and business expertise specific to biotechnology within TTO's will pay dividends in the growing field and sharing expertise between institutions can also be beneficial.¹¹³

Decision to Patent

Industry and technology specific expertise is required by TTO's in order to understand both if holding IP is in fact financially beneficial, and the licensing and technology transfer terms required for that technology to be a success (see next section). Filing patents is expensive, and a global push to register as many patents as possible, can be less effective in generating income than selective patenting of technologies and technology clusters, with associated selective filing of international patents based on an understanding of international markets. Having a strategy for patenting, and identifying the links between IP held to form clusters of IP which can be licenced together, can maximise benefits.

While holding and licensing IP can aid successful commercialisation of technologies and encourage private investment, patenting can also hamper the spread of information and is not required for commercialisation (see open source section). The decision to patent therefore must be rooted in maximising socio-economic benefit. Measures like the number of patents filed and held, are not good indicators of the success of TTOs and research in general. However, due to their ease of reporting, these measures are widely prevalent in the region. TTO's should be encouraged to release information including the number of successful start-ups and licenced technologies, return on investments, and the research taken to market including through non-profit enterprises, and use these as measures of success. Sector specific reporting would also be beneficial. As noted in the previous section (see expertise and staff shortages), TTO's must be better equipped with the expertise to make these decisions in the fields of biotechnology and biomanufacturing.

¹¹³ 'Interviews with Researchers and Technology Transfer Offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

In addition, the patenting process and decisions made by TTOs must be rapid in order to encourage researchers to disclose inventions rather than publishing. This together with grant applications accepting filed patents as evidence of research output can simplify decisions surrounding patenting for researchers where research publications are also necessary.

To patent or not to patent

Figure 9: Considerations for whether to patent or not to patent. On the left the reasons for not patenting, including patenting costs, the resultant prevention of free distribution of information, and the fact that patenting is not always required for commercialisation. On the right, benefits of patenting, including to protect intellectual property, and to encourage private investment for commercialisation.

Case Study: Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile TTO

At the Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, the technology transfer office invites experts from Industry and NGOs as well as researchers to a roundtable prior to filing a patent. The inventors present their innovation in broad terms without specifics and care is taken when choosing invitees to ensure they do not have vested interests. Through this process, feedback is given on whether the innovation fits with market needs, and is worthwhile patenting. This has been reported as an effective way of ensuring experts are consulted when decisions are made surrounding whether or not to apply for patents.¹¹⁴

Technology Transfer and Start-up Agreement Conditions

While it is evident that there will always be conflicts of interest between industry and public institutions, there is a perceived mismatch in favorability of transfer agreements

¹¹⁴ Interview with Javiera Espoz, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Technology Transfer Office.

between the public institution, private investors or companies, and individual researchers at many institutions. Creating incentives for researchers, as well as negotiating deals which are favourable to growth of local industry, will long term generate benefits for both society and financial benefits for public institutions. Template agreements and open discussion of optimal conditions can form a good foundation to narrow this perceived gap and ensure all parties are willing to engage with technology transfer processes.

In order to successfully market IP and negotiate deals with companies interested, licensing conditions must be negotiated such that the technology can be taken to market. Negotiations must take into account the differing positions of licensees and requires an understanding of the market. Rapid negotiation is also key. Providing researchers with a fair share of the royalties generated as a result of successful licensing of IP produced from their research can also incentivise translational research and technology transfer.

In addition to royalty benefits for researchers as a result of licences, it is of key importance that agreement conditions for researchers intending to spin-out a start-up based on their research are favourable for researchers. Researchers are often the best placed to ensure the technology reaches the market as they have a good understanding of the technology and can be emotionally and intellectually invested in it. When combined with a good understanding of the target market and commercial side, this can produce teams capable of successfully growing businesses. Whilst research may be completely publicly funded, unless technologies successfully reach the market, they are of limited benefit to the institution, funder, or state. If business growth is successful, holding equity in spin-outs can generate far greater returns than licensing technologies. When investing in spinouts private investors often look for good equity positions such that both founders and investors can maintain stakes as the business grows. For this reason, negotiable equity and licensing deals which are favourable to researchers can often be a good strategy for maximising benefits for public institutions and society in the long term by maximising the chance for spin-outs to succeed. It is key for TTOs not only to be willing and have the leeway to negotiate agreements when making deals, but to have the expertise in the biomanufacturing and biotechnology sector in order to know what appropriate conditions are. Simple Agreements for Future Equity (SAFE), and agreements to acquire future equity at a discount can be effective alternatives to more traditional royalty and equity schemes.¹¹⁵ Finally, public institutions require expertise to look beyond financial gain, and form agreements which will support society locally and nationally. This can include supporting social enterprises and other incentives within agreements beyond financial return.

¹¹⁵ Adam Hayes, 'What Is a Simple Agreement for Future Equity (SAFE)?', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142038/https://www.investopedia.com/simple-agreement-for-future-equity-8414773>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

Building Relationships with Industry: Building a Culture of Technology Transfer

In order to engage with industry, a greater presence of industry within the academic environment is necessary. There are many ways to foster this including the presence of greater numbers of industrial speakers at academic conferences, networking events, and networking platforms. Much of the primary contact with industry in many South American public institutions relies on independent academics. Furthermore, long term contact with industrial partners is often not maintained by TTOs. TTOs that are better able to market their IP and establish contacts with industry can play a role in the formation of partnerships. TTO's also need to be aware of the research at their institution and understand its applications for this process to be successful. In addition, schemes where startups or companies can work in the same space alongside academic groups can also help foster start-ups and encourage collaboration and industry investment.

It is important to build a culture of interaction between industry, academia and the government to help foster technology transfer, with industry not viewed in a negative light by academia and vice versa. Much progress has been made on this front with younger generations of researchers in particular, however there is still room for improvement. Forums and open exchange of ideas is important, as well as highlighting success stories on an institutional, regional, and national scale. Further mobility of workforce between industry and academia may also support this change in attitude.¹¹⁶

Collaborative Partnerships and Technology Transfer

Implementing collaborative partnerships between governments and government institutions, industry, and academia, can be a great way to drive innovation, support technology and knowledge transfer, and encourage private investment in research and development from local and international partners. Many policies, frameworks, financing schemes, and initiatives, have been put in place, and have demonstrated success in enabling collaborations between stakeholders in biotechnology and biomanufacturing in South America. PDP partnerships (see case study, page 62) and EMBRAP II units (case study below) in Brazil, are examples of successful schemes. Grants and funds which score applicants highly for demonstrating collaboration in all forms, including academic, academic-industry, regional, and international, can help promote a culture of collaboration and knowledge transfer and thereby support the biotechnology and biomanufacturing industries. In addition, promoting the formation of social networks, and facilitating interaction between stakeholders can further support the formation of collaborative partnerships in the sector.

¹¹⁶ 'Interviews with Researchers and Technology Transfer Offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

Continued development and growth of existing technology transfer schemes and frameworks, in addition to specific international agreements made by governments, will promote local growth in targeted biomanufacturing sectors. Encouraging long term partnerships as well as the short term partnerships is important, as these long term partnerships can drive sustained changes and benefits to the ecosystem.

Where there are partnerships or government contracts with foreign companies, it is key to include technology transfer within agreements. An important concept is that of improving technology readiness levels through technology transfer agreements.

Case Study: EMBRAPii, Brazil

Embrapii (the Brazilian Company for Industrial Research and Innovation - Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa e Inovação Industrial) is an organisation started in 2013 by the federal government through support from the National Manufacturing Confederation, the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, and the Ministry of Education. In the EMBRAPii model, based on the Fraunhofer Institute, specialised units for translational science in a specific topic are created through a competitive public call, and are largely housed within research institutes with the latest infrastructure and expertise. The units are responsible for their own finances, decision-making and contract formation, with the R&D projects being funded with private investment from a company, input from the host institution Embrapii unit, and public investment from the EMBRAPii. This allows much greater flexibility and reduced bureaucracy compared to the traditional funding model through funding agencies. In addition there is a continuous process of evaluation through a monitoring system with reporting and monthly meetings, which is quite different to previous grant models in Brazil.^{117,118} By 2020, there were over 60 Embrapii units, many of which specialise in biotechnology and biomanufacturing related R&D. This includes units specialising in biopharmaceuticals and drugs, biomass transformation, biotechnological processes, and agribusiness bioeconomy, to name a few.

Between 2014–2020, the first six year contracting period (later extended to ten years), companies funded an average of 48.6% of research expenses; with 32.0% provided by EMBRAPii and 18.0% by the Embrapii units, demonstrating that the scheme was successful in drawing private investment towards collaborative partnerships.¹¹⁹ Successful completion of projects and increasing registration of intellectual property as a result of EMBRAPii projects further present the effectiveness of the scheme. While the EMBRAPii model is widely considered successful, private sector innovation investment remains low and a challenge facing Brazil.

¹¹⁷ Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa e Inovação Industrial, 'MANUAL DE OPERAÇÃO DA EMBRAPii', 2024 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142406/https://embrapii.org.br/wp-content/images/2021/07/Manual_EMBRAPii_UE_versao-6.0-de-20.10.20.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹¹⁸ 'Who We Are - Embrapii'.

¹¹⁹ Guimaraes and Barcelos, 'Brazilian Company for Industrial Research and Innovation'.

Open Source and Open Access Science Initiatives: Transferring Technology Freely

It is important to note that not all technology should be patented, and even when protected not all technology should be licensed for commercial benefit of the holders of IP. Furthermore, the lack of patent protection does not preclude commercialisation, rather it can enable healthy competition and lowering of prices, promoting access to the technology in regions that require it. Products of public funding in particular, aim to maximise benefit to society in the region and country. Therefore, within public institutions, there is a responsibility to enable the spread of some technologies without barriers. Different technologies and information require the use of different strategies for dissemination, including use of different licensing agreements.

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are fields which promise wide ranging benefits to society with implications from health and diagnostics to the environment and sustainability. Within the field, the generation of open source enzymes, reagents, hardware and other technologies have enabled transfer of technologies to South America from the global north as well as between institutions within the region. These have enabled initiation of local biomanufacturing in multiple academic and industrial contexts, lowering costs and barriers to access. The benefits have been evident, enabling production of low cost products to support academic research and for teaching purposes, as well as enabling local and low cost production of biotherapeutics and diagnostics. The Covid-19 pandemic in particular has highlighted the importance of these initiatives.

Another separate but linked topic is that of Open Access research. Encouraging or mandating publishing of research in open access journals enables researchers and the wider public to access the latest literature and information without financial barriers. In particular, this enables researchers in South America to be aware of the latest progress in biotechnology and biomanufacturing and develop their research based on this. This is critical for equitable research in particular in regions or institutions without the financial capacity to subscribe to all journals. Publishing in open access journals however can be expensive for researchers, and therefore in order to ensure open access publication, grants need to include funding for open access publication, or take appropriate steps to ensure content that would particularly benefit researchers in the region is published in an open access format.

From an education perspective, it is important to spread awareness of open science and technology alongside business and entrepreneurship, and foster a collaborative environment in which ideas are exchanged rather than hidden. Not only does this foster

academic progress, but as a highly interdisciplinary field, collaboration is often the foundation of innovation, and rapid industrial progress.

The open science roadmap 2022 in Argentina is an example of a key policy document recognising the importance of open science to innovation.¹²⁰ Implementing policies which promote and provide recognition for open technology transfer can support the sector further.

Case Study: Reclone and the CPPR Recombinant Protein Production Centre, Universidad de Buenos Aires

Reclone is an international network of researchers who develop and share open source biological materials and protocols to enable equitable access of this technology globally. Reclone hubs, several of which are situated in South America, including Argentina (Mendoza and Buenos Aires) and Chile (Santiago), distribute open source plasmids in the region including for the production of open source enzymes. These have been used by South American institutions to produce enzymes for research purposes and teaching, reducing costs often to below a fifth of the current commercial cost when importing from abroad. This has enabled cost effective research to be carried out, grown local expertise in biomanufacturing, and enabled improved teaching and practicals. Long-term, this transfer of technology serves to improve technology readiness levels, and reduce dependence on foreign goods in particular from the global north. In addition to public institutions, the private sector including start-ups have used the open source biological materials and protocols to develop products for the local market. The importance of this was observed during the Covid-19 pandemic, where open source enzymes allowed local biomanufacturing companies and institutions to produce products to meet local demand, when the international products were unavailable and directed towards the developed world.

The CPPR (Centro de Producción de Proteínas Recombinantes) at the University of Buenos Aires is one such hub of the Reclone community that has utilised local open source enzyme production to produce common enzymes for research including DNA polymerases. These have proved essential in supporting research amidst skyrocketing inflation and reduced funding, and have also supported production of enzymes for teaching purposes. In addition to open source enzymes, the facility works with researchers and industry to produce proteins required for R&D projects. The CPPR was first conceptualised in 2019, and fully

¹²⁰ MINCYT Argentina and Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, 'DIAGNOSIS AND ROADMAP FOR AN OPEN SCIENCE POLICY IN ARGENTINA', 2022
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142921/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/2023/01/cac_final_document_-_english_version.pdf> [accessed 5 January 2025].

functional by 2023, and houses some of the latest equipment for bioproduction and purification of enzymes.^{121,122}

Bringing many components together: Start-up ecosystems

Successful start-up ecosystems contain multiple components and organisations that come together to enable the region to be a hotspot for incubation of start-ups. Generating start-ups in the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sector has its own unique difficulties and requirements.

Innovative research, often with significant interdisciplinary collaboration, is the foundation which generates the ideas and technology that can be commercialised. For this reason biotechnology start-up ecosystems often surround regions with leading research institutions. Research in this sector often requires significant public funding and infrastructure in the form of laboratories and equipment which often cannot be provided by the private sector alone. For commercialisation from public institutions, there is a need for TTOs and efficient technology transfer processes with significant legal and business expertise specific to biotechnology and biomanufacturing. Furthermore, academics must navigate this process and therefore education for founders in these aspects is also important.

Securing private investment from venture capital is important in providing the required capital to grow the business beyond the initial stage. In addition, input from private investors can also bring in legal, technological and organisational expertise as well as experience in navigating the process of commercialisation which gives start-ups greater chances of success. Furthermore, private investors can also aid in marketing start-ups for subsequent rounds of funding, which in South America often requires attracting foreign investment. In this way, private investors can be an important component of the ecosystem. However, Venture Capital investment in particular often comes along with the final goal of exit. In this model, start-ups are often encouraged to sell their business to larger foreign companies. These companies may be more interested in acquiring intellectual property rather than maintaining the component of the company within South America. This can be potentially detrimental to developing the biomanufacturing ecosystem within the region. On the other hand, acquisition from a larger company can bring greater investment into the region. Institutional seed funds and public grants targeted at start-ups, or local individual investors can also help provide the financial aid to move from a concept and technology, to proof-of-principle and a marketable product

¹²¹ Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales - Universidad de Buenos Aires, 'Proteínas Hechas En Casa', 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230401180033/https://exactas.uba.ar/proteinas-hechas-en-casa/>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹²² Interviews at CPPR, Universidad de Buenos Aires.

which has the potential to generate profit. These forms of investment can also come with the expectation to generate returns. To encourage biotechnology start-ups to remain and grow within the region, favourable fiscal climates with incentives for R&D and reductions in corporation tax can be beneficial.

Small and medium stage startups in the biotechnology sector have a specific need for high quality lab spaces, and therefore industrial science parks and institutes or alternatively provisions for startups to use academic infrastructure is important. Having startups develop in connection with academia can be beneficial, and networking and generating collaborations with other startups in the region can also be effective and explain why successful startup ecosystems often contain clusters of companies working in connected fields.

A major hurdle for start-ups within biotechnology and biomanufacturing can be scaling up of their processes and technology to a commercial scale which often requires significant scale-up infrastructure (discussed in the infrastructure section). Furthermore, entering the international market with differing regulations and import and export processes can also be a major hurdle for developing startups requiring both know-how and good infrastructure. Another hurdle can be in effectively employing the required expertise to form a successful team, and this is where a highly skilled and ready labour market and attractive location can be beneficial.

Overall creating an optimal ecosystem for fostering biotechnology and biomanufacturing companies requires bringing together many different aspects previously discussed including innovative technologies, private and public capital, good infrastructure, clear regulations, a supportive fiscal climate, and good education.

Case Study: Patagonia Biotech Hub (#PatagoniaBiotechHUB)

Patagonia Biotech Hub is an initiative to build a biotech hub in the Patagonia region of Chile. #PatagoniaBiotechHUB is a non-for-profit organisation, and was founded and funded by a group of biotechnology companies and users of biotechnology solutions, in order to work towards this vision. The group identified key components of a successful biotechnology hub, including an entrepreneurial environment, talent and innovation development, capital, and life quality. With support from the local government and recognition of the importance of financing as well as legal expertise, they aim to bring all these components together to form a local specialised ecosystem for biotechnology start-ups within Patagonia to enable them to overcome the barriers faced.¹²³

¹²³ Interview with Eduardo Wallach, Kura Biotech.

Case Study: Zentynel

Zentynel is a venture capital fund which specialises in investing in biotechnology, and has supported start-ups in many different countries and regions in South America. Some examples of companies that Zentynel have supported include Xeptiva Therapeutics in Uruguay, and Biomakers in Argentina, Brazil and Mexico.

Zentynel supports companies through Series A investment up to 5-7 million US dollars, and helps the companies supported to grow and acquire funding from subsequent rounds in Series B and C which often comes from investors in the US. Zentynel is formed from experts in the field within South America, who have the knowledge to navigate the ecosystem and identify promising companies.

Venture capital funds and private investors form a key part of the ecosystem without which it would be difficult for start-ups in the region to grow. They also help market start-ups for foreign higher value investments. Government funding and grants support projects and companies through initial development, however strong private sector investments are key for companies to grow in the long term. Attracting greater private investment for continued growth was seen as a priority by multiple start-ups in the region, with private investors and venture capitalists specifically targeting the biotechnology sector still very limited in the region. The growth of biotechnology in the region however, is beginning to attract more attention.

Key strengths of South America in biomanufacturing from Zentynel's perspective include the skills and ideas of founders, and the capacity for businesses developed in the region to quickly generate revenue. In addition, the potential for far lower cost of production than in the US for example was identified as a key strength of the region. It was noted though that compared to other regions like the US, higher risk ideas which cannot generate revenue quickly are less likely to successfully acquire funding in South America.

Collaboration between countries for scaling up resources, with specialisation of infrastructure, as well as convergence of legislation were noted as potential areas to support biomanufacturing.^{124,125}

¹²⁴ Interview with Christian Hernandez Zentynel, 2024.

¹²⁵ 'Home - Zentynel', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240613145917/https://zentynel.com/en/>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

Infrastructure

Overview

The development of the required infrastructure is key to supporting biomanufacturing and biotechnology within South America. In this section three different infrastructure shortfalls in supporting the industry are discussed. The first two, scale-up infrastructure and testing and quality control infrastructure, are specific to biotechnology and biomanufacturing. The third, customs and transport infrastructure, is more general and affects many fields, however has a disproportionate impact on the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sector. A number of challenges for the process of implementing improvement to infrastructure have been reported by the IMF. These include: weak planning, project appraisal, and preparation capacity; overly rigid or myopic budgeting; difficulties with budget execution; procurement problems; and unclear project sustainability. These must also be addressed to enable optimal infrastructure improvements for the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors.¹²⁶

Figure 10: Bottleneck in Scale-up infrastructure from technology readiness levels 5-7, means that the process of scale-up prototyping and optimisation is usually conducted abroad and technology transfer must occur back to the region for final production.

¹²⁶ Marianne Fay and others, *Rethinking Infrastructure in Latin America and the Caribbean, Spending Better to Achieve More* (The World Bank, 22 December 2024) <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222143243/https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/pt/676711491563967405/114110-REVISED-Rethinking-Infrastructure-Low-Res.pdf>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

Scale-up has been identified by many partners as a major hurdle for the development of biomanufacturing processes in the region. Scale-up of bioreactor fermentation systems within research labs can be conducted up to approximately 10 L scale, though this is not readily available everywhere. In some specific biomanufacturing research institutes in the region, scale-up can be conducted to 100 to 200 L fermentation, and companies within the region do offer scale-up optimisation to this production scale.¹²⁷ However, while the biomanufacturing capacity for large scale production does exist, it is often owned by individual manufacturers for their processes or large government production facilities for health bioproducts. The R&D capacity for scale-up to this scale is very limited in the region. This can result in promising research not progressing beyond initial research. Instead, the products of foreign research and processes from foreign companies are often implemented in place of local solutions, irrespective of their relative strengths. Alternately, many innovative companies and start-ups must outsource scale up and sometimes production overseas, often to Europe or America. This comes at significant expense.

The South American region is particularly limited in Contract Development Manufacturing Organisations (CDMOs) or Contract Research Organisations (CROs) that have scale-up plants to facilitate the development of products to manufacturing scale. Furthermore, GMP (Good Manufacturing Practice), GLP (Good Laboratory Practice), and other certification of facilities, is also limited, meaning research plants do not meet the current standards needed for approval by the regulatory bodies in the region.¹²⁸

Similarly, organisations that specialise in conducting clinical trials are also uncommon in the region, and clinical trials are either done in house through developing the skills and expertise, and collaborating with clinical institutions, or clinical trials are also conducted abroad. Outsourcing scale-up, clinical trials and regulatory approval overseas is not only often prohibitively costly, but may sometimes not be ideal for optimising production or application within the region. This is due to it not reflecting the local environment and population. Furthermore, conducting scale-up optimisation and clinical-trials locally will boost the local economy through generating a novel industry and providing employment.

Productive Development Partnerships (PDP) and other similar schemes for technology transfer from international players to local partners or government institutes within the region (see case study below), aim to move manufacturing capacity and technology to the region from abroad. This can facilitate the transfer of manufacturing capacity and infrastructure to the region and increase technology readiness to implement biomanufacturing processes. The skills and infrastructure required for scale-up

¹²⁷ Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with members of academia involved in biomanufacturing research, biomanufacturing industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz.

¹²⁸ Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with Members of Academia Involved in Biomanufacturing Research, Biomanufacturing Industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz.

optimisation however, are significantly different to those required for implementation of already optimised processes. For this reason, the whole process from R&D to large scale manufacture is unlikely to ever be supported by this form of technology transfer agreement alone.

Putting in place this scale-up infrastructure requires considerable investment and building up of the associated expertise, and therefore needs targeted support and financing from the government. Steps are beginning to be taken to address this shortfall, by both the private sector and government in some countries in the region. Examples include Brazil for biotherapeutics, (see Biotimize case study) and Chile for microbially derived inputs for agriculture.¹²⁹ Clear strategy plans and policies to support and finance the building of scale-up infrastructure, as well as potential for collaboration between countries to enable specialisation and sharing of scale-up infrastructure within the region, could further help form the foundation for conducting the whole scale-up process within the region.

Case Study: Fiocruz (Bio-Manguinhos), Instituto Butantan and PDPs

Fiocruz and Instituto Butantan are together the two largest Brazilian Public Institutes related to public health in Brazil and are world renowned with over 100 years of history. In addition to conducting research, both institutes are responsible for the biomanufacture of products to support the Brazilian National Health System (SUS - Sistema Único de Saúde) which include vaccines, serums, immunobiologicals and biopharmaceuticals. This ranges from conducting fill and finish processes, to the full biomanufacturing process. PDPs, “Productive Development Partnerships”, were launched in 2009 as a way of stimulating technology transfer to enable local production of medicines for cost effective supply to the Brazilian Health System. Under the scheme, one or more public institutions and one or more private entities are responsible for transfer of technology for the production of a therapeutic to the public institution, with local pharmaceutical or critical components producers also required to participate. As part of the agreement, the SUS commits to purchase of the therapeutic produced for a given period and the pharmaceutical transferer of the technology usually benefits through royalties.¹³⁰

PDPs have been reported successful in implementing technology transfer, with 66 active PDPs in 2022 mainly related to antivirals, anticancer medicines and immunosuppressants, generating and estimated savings for the SUS of more than \$500 million between

¹²⁹ ‘AgroPages-Chile Launches National Center of Bioinputs to Reduce Agrochemicals Use-Agricultural News’ <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222143457/https://news.agropages.com/News/NewsDetail---48156.htm>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³⁰ Kellen Rezende, Maria Sueli Soares Felipe, and Carlos Augusto Grabojs Gadelha, ‘Challenges for Innovation in Health: The Brazilian Experience of Public-Private Partnerships for Productive Development in the Economic Industrial Health Complex and Universal Health Coverage Context’, 2021, doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-958902/v1.

2011-2018.^{131,132} Through the technology transfer, PDPs have been instrumental in developing biomanufacturing technology readiness levels and have supported both public institutions as well as local private biomanufacturers. One example demonstrating this, is that previous partnerships were said to be effective in developing the expertise to enable implementation of the Covid19 vaccine production pipeline at Fiocruz within approximately six months. There have however also been multiple unsuccessful PDPs suspended at different stages and also concerns regarding the handling of intellectual property.¹³³

PDPs, although enabling transfer of biomanufacturing technology and capacity, have had limited success in supporting the transfer of local research and development, including that conducted at Fiocruz and Instituto Butantan, through to scale-up and products supplied to the market. PDPs often start with fill and finish processes, and can progress to the implementation of more and more of the manufacturing chain by the recipient moving towards the whole process. However, as PDPs largely implement preexisting biomanufacturing processes, the pharmaceutical partners, which are often large international companies, are responsible for the research, development and scale-up optimisation. This scale-up optimisation is therefore usually conducted abroad. There remains a limited capacity and expertise for scale up optimisation within Brazil and this is often outsourced to CDMOs overseas at considerable expense. This means many potentially viable developments as a result of local research do not progress, and instead internationally developed technologies are transferred in. Focusing on the development of this scale-up infrastructure and expertise will bridge the gap to enable the whole pipeline from research and development to production to be conducted within the country.

Case Study: Biotimize

Biotimize is a “Biotechnology as a Service” company, founded in Sao Paulo in 2016, that provides biotechnology and bioprocess engineering services to other companies and institutions to develop monoclonal antibodies and biosimilars. The company recognises the challenges faced by companies in Brazil and South America due to the lack of availability of Contract Development Manufacturing Organisations (CDMOs) that can aid in the scale up and optimisation from the research scale. The company plans to build a GMP (Good Manufacturing Practices) certified (FDA, EMA, ANVISA) facility to become the first CDMO in South America to offer end to end product development from cell line

¹³¹ Morgan Pincombe , Anthony McDonnell and Javier Guzman, ‘Leveraging Brazilian Leadership and Procurement Arrangements in the Fight Against Antimicrobial Resistance, Centre for Global Development’, 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240620050222/https://www.cgdev.org/publication/leveraging-brazilian-leadership-and-procurement-arrangements-fight-against>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³² Anna Rose Welch, ‘A Deep Dive Into Brazil’s Biosimilar PDPs’, 2017 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222170856/https://www.biosimilardevelopment.com/doc/a-deep-dive-into-brazil-s-biosimilar-pdps-0001>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³³ Ricardo Campello, ‘Brazilian Government Resurrects Its Partnership for Productive Development (PDP) Program. A New Threat to Pharma IP Rights?’, 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222144819/https://www.lickslegal.com/articles/brazilian-government-resurrects-its-partnership-for-productive-development-pdp-program-a-new-threat-to-pharma-ip-rights>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

development to fill and finish. A 32,000 square-foot parcel of land was reportedly donated to Biotimize by the City of Piracicaba for this facility. The GMP certified facility will focus on production of monoclonal antibodies and biosimilars from mammalian cells, and will have three upstream suits (USP) two of which with a 200-500L capacity and one with a 2000L-5000L capacity (Single use), and a downstream suit (DSP).^{134,135,136}

Testing and Quality Control Infrastructure: Support for Implementation of Manufacturing Standards and Certification

A hurdle faced by some start-ups and SMEs within the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors in South America, is the ability to demonstrate adherence to quality standards as well as convince consumers and customers locally and internationally of the quality of products. Biomanufacturing and biotechnology products often require high standards and quality control, in particular in the medical biotechnology sector, but also in other sectors. The number of ISO and GMP certified production facilities in the region are relatively low, and standards requirements have evolved rapidly, with many Latin American countries also adopting international standards. Especially for smaller start-ups in biomanufacturing, acquiring international ISO and GMP certification can be a barrier, and quality control facilities and the testing equipment required can be prohibitively expensive, depending on the product in question.¹³⁷ For this reason, financial support and expertise towards acquiring international quality standards certifications, and fiscal or financial support towards testing and quality control equipment may aid the sector. In addition, third party testing and quality control facilities provide further support. One international example is the NIBISC in the UK, which helps companies through conducting contract proof of concept testing for early-stage development of biological medicines, as well as helping companies validate in-house assays or reference materials.^{138,139}

¹³⁴ Millie Nelson, 'Biotimize Looks to Build First Biological CDMO in Brazil - BioProcess Insider', 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240725102645/https://www.bioprocessintl.com/facilities-capacity/biotimize-looks-to-build-first-biological-cdmo-in-brazil>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³⁵ 'Biotimize' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222145533/https://www.biotimize.com.br/cdmo/>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³⁶ Yahoo Finance read, 'Biotimize Announces the Opening of a Fundraising Round to Build the First Biological CDMO in Brazil', 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222145643/https://finance.yahoo.com/news/biotimize-announces-opening-fundraising-round-123000346.html>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³⁷ 'Interviews with SMEs in Brazil and Chile'.

¹³⁸ 'NIBSC - Contract Testing' <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222151904/https://nibsc.org/expert_services/contract_testing.aspx> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹³⁹ 'NIBSC - About Us' <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222152118/https://nibsc.org/about_us.aspx> [accessed 3 January 2025].

Commercial Infrastructure: Transport and Customs

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing are sectors which are heavily dependent on commercial infrastructure including transport and customs infrastructure due to the sector's integration with global value chains. The lack of this infrastructure in the region, and importance of improvements in this area, has been highlighted in an IMF blog post in 2023 which emphasises the positive impact changes could have on trade and growth.¹⁴⁰

Many biotechnology companies and researchers rely on import of specific foreign inputs from multiple locations globally for R&D and production. Similarly many companies also rely on export of products to international markets. Biological products including enzymes and samples can be both temperature sensitive requiring cold chain transport, and time sensitive. They can also often be expensive, and are subject to significant regulation. This makes poor transport and customs infrastructure a particular barrier for the sector.¹⁴¹

Supply chain issues also significantly reduce efficiency of production and result in the holding of greater stock at considerable expense to counteract this. This in turn reduces the resilience of companies to respond to global disruptions due to geopolitical issues, as well as the capacity to flexibly adapt to changes in the market. Ultimately, the poor supply chain integration has been reported by some startups in the region to raise costs sufficiently in some cases to negate the benefit of cheaper labour, in particular in R&D.

Transport Infrastructure: Improving transport infrastructure including roads, rail infrastructure, ports, and airports with increased integration between different modalities has been shown to have the potential to significantly boost trade. Infrastructure varies significantly in different countries and different regions within countries. In particular for cold-chain transport, good transport infrastructure is vital. In addition to physical infrastructure, policies targeted at increasing the competition in transport sectors in the region, has been proposed to be a way to reduce transport costs and increase efficiency.¹⁴²

Customs infrastructure: Complex regulation surrounding products of biomanufacturing and biotechnology require good customs infrastructure and processes to implement effectively. Multiple startups and researchers have reported

¹⁴⁰ Flavien Moreau, Rafael Machado Parente, 'How Latin America Can Use Trade to Boost Growth', *IMF*, 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222152238/https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2023/11/16/how-latin-america-can-use-trade-to-boost-growth>> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁴¹ Interviews with Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing companies in Brazil, Argentina and Chile, including enzyme manufacturers.

¹⁴² Marianne Fay and others, *Rethinking Infrastructure in Latin America and the Caribbean, Spending Better to Achieve More*.

regularly having to deal with products being held at customs both when importing and exporting. The delays involved in processing these products, and sorting problems can cause significant costs to businesses and researchers, especially when perishable goods are involved.

Clear customs clearance processes for biological and chemical goods, with standardised procedures and training for customs staff regarding biological and chemical goods could improve processes. All stakeholders should be aware of the processes, with clear documentation in place. In addition, separate specialised accelerated processes and infrastructure for perishable, biological, and chemical goods as well as identification systems for verified suppliers, distributors and recipients could also accelerate customs clearance for these goods. When dealing with biological and chemical goods, infrastructure for rapid testing and verification of materials where necessary is also important. Enhanced use of technology, computational systems, and automation including for data exchange and tracking, would accelerate import and export whilst also reduce the delays associated with goods being incorrectly held up. International harmonisation of standards, regulations and processes surrounding biological goods would streamline documentation, greatly reduce the burden on biotech and biomanufacturing companies, and also aid customs clearance processes. Furthermore, improved communication between different agencies in the region may also help promote security as well as efficiency.

Risks, Regulation, and Legislation

Overview

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing offer numerous benefits to society and hold the potential to drive advancements across various fields, but they also come with significant risks. This was identified internationally and resulted for instance in the production of the The Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety in 2003, a supplement to the Convention on Biodiversity which many South American Countries have signed, named after the first extraordinary meeting of the Conference of the Parties, in Cartagena, Colombia.¹⁴³ For this reason, the sector is highly regulated. To maximise the potential positive impacts and minimise risks, it is essential that legislation, regulation and approval processes are clear, transparent, efficient, and up to date. Furthermore, it is key that the processes in place to approve products are rapid, limited in bureaucracy and minimises costs to the industry. Both overly restrictive regulation and bureaucratic processes, as well as a lack of or incomplete regulation can hinder progress in the field.

The regulation and legislation surrounding the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors mainly stem from agricultural and health sectors, with some regulation also stemming from food and chemicals. While regulation has developed, streamlining of processes to improve efficiency is necessary. There is also some incomplete legislation, and a lack of transparent regulations and approval processes in many countries especially in some sectors, for example microbial biomanufacturing unrelated to health. In some countries in the region, drafted or incomplete legislation has been awaiting completion and ratification for many years or even decades. Often in these cases, even with incomplete legislation, regulation processes do exist, however there can be considerable uncertainty and difficulties as a result of the gaps. Another complexity of the region is the lack of harmonisation of regulation and approval process between countries and the lack of reciprocal agreements for approval. This however is starting to change. International partnerships and collaboration can not only aid the efficiency of approval processes, but also promote safety. Many biomanufacturing and biotechnological companies look to the US for regulatory approval, for example gaining FDA approval, not only in order to access international markets, but also due to the greater efficiency and clarity with respect to approval processes, as well as the benefits it can have in aiding approval locally.

¹⁴³ Biosafety Clearing-House, 'The Cartagena Protocol |About the Protocol' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241121024415/https://bch.cbd.int/protocol/background>> [accessed 21 November 2024].

Agricultural Biotechnology Regulation

Plant biotechnology is a strength in many South American Countries, and has formed the historical basis for much of the biotechnology and biomanufacturing regulations related to Genetically Modified Organisms and biosafety. Many countries in the region have legislation, regulation, regulatory bodies, and approval processes to enable the growth of GM crops. Argentina and Brazil, the two largest economies, led the way in implementing regulation and legislation, however other countries were close behind. There are however relatively restrictive laws in some countries, for example in Chile, where planting gene edited crops for GM seed production is allowed, however planting gene edited crops for other purposes is generally not. In some countries, complete restrictions on GM crops exist including Ecuador.^{144,145} Regulatory bodies have been established which are responsible for the approval of GM crops. These bodies have often been co-opted to be responsible more widely for GMOs in research, GMOs in other sectors, and environmental release of GMOs (For more details of regulatory bodies in different countries refer to Appendix I).

There has been much debate surrounding the use of modern and precise gene editing technologies like CRISPR for gene editing in crops and organisms, and to what extent genetic changes which could occur naturally through breeding should be regulated in comparison with use of exogenous genes. Countries including Brazil and Argentina have approved the first crops and animals produced using CRISPR technologies.¹⁴⁶

Medical Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Regulation

In addition to agricultural biotechnology, the other main driver for regulation in the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors is the rapidly expanding use of biotherapeutics. This regulation generally regards ensuring the safety of these products when used in humans and involves regulations surrounding quality and manufacturing standards often including regulation surrounding the use of GM organisms. The approval process for these products has generally been aligned with pharmaceutical industry regulations, and broadly speaking follow the same processes. Separate approval for the use of GMOs used in manufacturing is also generally required

¹⁴⁴ M.A. Sánchez and H Campos, 'Coexistence of Genetically Modified Seed Production and Organic Farming in Chile', *GM Crops & Food*, 12.1, pp. 509–19, doi:10.1080/21645698.2021.2001242.

¹⁴⁵ Nelson Ramirez, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Chile, USDA', 2023 <https://web.archive.org/web/20231203051130/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Santiago_Chile_CI2023-0025.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁴⁶ Maria Eugenia Segretin, Gabriela Cynthia Soto, and Christian Damian Lorenzo, 'Latin America: A Hub for Agrobiotechnological Innovations', *Annals of Botany*, 2024, p. mcae191, doi:10.1093/aob/mcae191.

depending on the country. Another aspect is the approval of biosimilars, biological products highly similar to another already approved biotherapeutic. The approval process and requirements in terms of evidence and testing of these products varies from country to country, however generally countries have adopted the requirements for the latest international standards including for GMP production, and approval in foreign leading countries like the US FDA can aid local approval.¹⁴⁷

Microbial Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Regulation

The regulation and approval process for products derived from microbial genetic engineering and biotechnology for commercial, industrial, or food uses varies significantly between different regions, and in some regions there is a large gap in this regulation which results in uncertainty. In these cases companies resort to certification overseas, e.g. through the FDA in the US. Brazil is one country with a robust and clear mechanism for these products. Since 2010, microbial biotechnology products in Brazil have been certified by CTNBio, the same approver as for agricultural products.¹⁴⁸ In Chile on the other hand, there does not seem to be clear regulation or a regulatory framework for the use of biotechnology derived or genetically engineered microbes and microbial products for food ingredients, with the ministry of health responsible for the ultimate approval of food ingredients.¹⁴⁹

Regional Harmonisation of Regulation

The lack of harmonisation of regulation in different South American countries results in significant barriers to trade for biotechnology companies in the region. Separate approvals and different documentation may be required in multiple countries and on import and export. This results in increased costs for biomanufacturing and biotechnology companies, and slow approvals can prevent access to markets. Harmonising regulation and inter-country partnerships can therefore support the sector, whilst also fostering discussion and collaboration to maximise safety. There has been progress in this regard with Argentina and Brazil signing a Cooperation Agreement on Biosafety of Modern Biotechnology Products, joined by Paraguay and Uruguay in 2023. The creation of the Bio Innovation Group for South-South Cooperation in 2023 further demonstrates the drive for international cooperation. The Southern common market, MERCOSUR, aims to integrate the market in South America and was initially

¹⁴⁷ Anurag S. Rathore and Ankita Bhargava, 'Regulatory Considerations in Biosimilars: Latin America Region', *Preparative Biochemistry & Biotechnology*, 51.2 (2021), pp. 201–6, doi:10.1080/10826068.2021.1876729.

¹⁴⁸ Camila Aquino, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Brazil, USDA', 2022 <https://web.archive.org/web/20240723030121/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Brasilia_Brazil_BR2022-0064.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025].

¹⁴⁹ Nelson Ramirez, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Chile, USDA'.

established by Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay and Uruguay, and subsequently joined by Venezuela with Bolivia also in the process of joining. Associate States include Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guyana, Peru and Surinam.^{150,151} MERCOSUR has been important in driving increased access and trade in the region including in the biotechnology sectors, and has supported the harmonisation of regulation.^{152,153} Trade Agreements, including that with the European common market, and development frameworks to support harmonisation of regulations for biotechnology and biomanufacturing, for example the BIOTECSUR initiative, have the potential to further support the sector.¹⁵⁴ There are however considerations to be made to ensure that the local Bioeconomy, including research and development in South American countries and regions benefit from these agreements.¹⁵⁵ Support for the sector including financial during regulatory change is also important.

Streamlining Processes and Reducing Bureaucracy

A significant barrier for Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing companies within the South American region is the time and bureaucracy involved in regulatory processes and gaining approval for products. Streamlining processes for approval, simplifying documentation, and using computational infrastructure to aid submission, modification, and approval of documents will further support the biomanufacturing and biotechnology industry. Improvements are being made, for example the Chilean Institute of Public Health (ISP) has adopted the CTD (Common Technical Document) international standard format for new drug registration, and both Chilean and Colombian authorities have created new timelines for review and approval of drugs.¹⁵⁶ The setting of time targets for approvals and working to achieve them can help streamline processes.

¹⁵⁰ 'MERCOSUR Countries - MERCOSUR', 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241231051802/https://www.mercosur.int/en/about-mercursosur/mercursosur-countries/>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁵¹ 'MERCOSUR in Brief - MERCOSUR', 2025

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103110403/https://www.mercosur.int/en/about-mercursosur/mercursosur-in-brief/>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁵² Rosario Silva Gilli, 'Genetically Modified Organisms in MERCOSUR', in *The Regulation of Genetically Modified Organisms: Comparative Approaches*, ed. by Luc Bodiguel and Michael Cardwell (Oxford University Press, 2010), p. 0, doi:10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199542482.003.0012.

¹⁵³ Nidia Benítez Candia and others, 'Paraguay's Approach to Biotechnology Governance: A Comprehensive Guide', *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 12 (2024), doi:10.3389/fbioe.2024.1373473.

¹⁵⁴ 'BIOTECSUR - Primera Plataforma de Biotecnologías Del MERCOSUR'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250104164408/https://www.recyt.mercosur.int/biotecsur/en/biotecsur.php>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁵⁵ Lilliana Terradas-Cobas, Carlos Céspedes-Payret, and Estanislao Luis Calabuig, 'Expansion of GM Crops, Antagonisms between MERCOSUR and the EU. The Role of R&D and Intellectual Property Rights' Policy', *Environmental Development*, 19 (2016), pp. 49–58, doi:10.1016/j.envdev.2016.06.003.

¹⁵⁶ Aicha Otmani and Flavia Firmino, 'CMC Requirements for New Drug Registration in Latin America | Pharmaceutical Engineering', 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153540/https://ispe.org/pharmaceutical-engineering/may-june-2023/cmc-requirements-new-drug-registration-latin-america>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

Chemicals Regulation

Chemicals regulation is also key to the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors. The region has historically been slow to implement effective chemicals regulation, however there has been much recent progress. Brazil is in the process of developing a chemicals law, whilst Colombia and Chile have also made recent progress in developing chemicals and chemical waste management frameworks.¹⁵⁷

Case study: Xeptiva Therapeutics, Uruguay

Founded in 2021, Xeptiva Therapeutics is a biotech startup based in Montevideo, Uruguay. The company was established following over a decade of dedicated research and development focused on chronic neuroinflammation at the Neurodegeneration Laboratory of the Institut Pasteur in Montevideo. Xeptiva's vision is to provide long-term solutions for challenging conditions in companion animals, focusing particularly on chronic diseases and inflammatory conditions associated with ageing. Xeptiva has been supported by multiple Venture Capital firms, including the South American Venture Capital, ZentyneL.

Xeptiva has over five products in its pipeline aimed at addressing these chronic conditions. Currently, clinical studies are underway for its leading products, which target chronic pain and atopic dermatitis in dogs. Central to Xeptiva's approach are its recombinant multi-target immunogens. These immunogens are designed to elicit an immune response to specific immunogenic structural epitopes, without possessing the biological activity of the endogenous inflammatory mediators they target. Vaccination generates neutralising antibodies against multiple endogenous inflammatory mediators, which play a crucial role in chronic inflammation, pain, and tissue damage. Through this approach, Xeptiva aims to reduce chronic inflammation, thereby providing a long-term therapeutic effect that facilitates tissue regeneration and significantly improves the quality of life for affected animals.

Xeptiva's clinical studies have been conducted within Uruguay and the first GMP batch of the vaccine is being produced in a local CMO, not certified for by the FDA or EMA. This means approved products will be marketed in the South American market initially. International CMOs were investigated, however were comparatively extremely expensive. Accessing certain markets in the region was noted to be difficult due to regulatory and other hurdles.^{158,159}

¹⁵⁷ Global Product Compliance Group, 'The New Regulatory Landscape in Brazil, Colombia, and Chile', 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153720/https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/new-regulatory-landscape-brazil-colombia->> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁵⁸ Interview with Emiliano Trias, Xeptiva Therapeutics, 2024.

¹⁵⁹ 'Xeptiva Therapeutics - Home' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241118080115/https://www.xeptiva.com/>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

Cross-sector challenge: Laboratory Reagent Supply and Cost

Poor Supply Hampering Growth of the Sector

A significant challenge faced by both academic institutions and industry in South America, is the procurement of laboratory reagents and equipment. This truly cross-sector challenge is the culminating result of multiple factors identified in the previous sections, and can therefore be used as an effective example to demonstrate the changes needed in policy to drive growth in biotechnology and biomanufacturing. Furthermore, the measurable nature of reagent lead times and cost, means that SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) targets can be set and used as a measure of the efficacy of policy changes.

The efficient and cost-effective procurement of laboratory reagents and equipment is essential both for R&D, and for commercial production, and is consistently raised as one of the largest barriers to rapid development and growth by both members of industry and academia. Our interviews with academics and industry members indicate that the lead time for obtaining standard reagents and equipment used in biotechnology and biomanufacturing, ranging from enzymes to culture media, typically varies from two to three weeks to three months. In some cases, lead times even exceed six months. Likewise, the procurement of DNA primers and other genetic materials also often takes several weeks, as does DNA sequencing. In contrast, laboratory reagents can usually be obtained within one to two days in Europe and North America, and DNA sequencing takes just one to three days from sample submission to obtaining results. In addition to longer lead times, the cost of some laboratory reagents and services including enzymes and DNA sequencing services remain significantly higher than those abroad, in some cases by a factor of 5 or more. An added complication in regards to equipment lies in the capacity for maintenance and repairs, for which manufacturer support is severely limited and expensive in South America when compared with Europe and North America. This adds to the problem of limited funds for repair and maintenance in many South American labs.¹⁶⁰

To mitigate these challenges, both academia and industry often maintain higher stock levels and redundant processes, which ultimately prove inefficient and costly in the long term. The limited ability to rapidly purchase different reagents and need to maintain higher stock levels, restricts the ability to swiftly pivot research direction and innovate, and results in a tendency to conduct lower-risk experiments. As a consequence, the region is less competitive compared to other developing regions including Asia.

¹⁶⁰ Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with Members of Academia Involved in Biomanufacturing Research, Biomanufacturing Industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz'.

Additionally, the delays to research and production complicate the capacity to respond promptly to changing situations and research demands, as highlighted by the recent COVID-19 pandemic.

The multiple factors contributing towards poor reagent supply, from inadequate commercial infrastructure to inefficient regulation, are analysed below and presented alongside potential solutions.

Figure 11: Factors contributing towards poor reagent supply in South America: Import and export delays; Institutional bureaucracy with spending; limited distributors and exclusivity deals; Limited local production and low trust in the quality of local products

1. Import and Export Delays

Cumbersome regulations and inefficient processes can lead to significant delays in both the certification of products for import or export, and the import and export processes themselves. New biotechnological and chemical products like reagents often are the subject of lengthy approval processes. In addition, numerous administrative requirements associated with transportation of hazardous materials further contribute to the inefficient movement of laboratory reagents, increasing costs and resulting in delivery delays. The lack of harmonisation in regulation across the region only serves to add to this bureaucratic burden. Moreover, even when products are certified, a lack of understanding among import staff and lack of processing infrastructure often impedes the import and export of reagents. While it is essential to identify and regulate biological and chemical materials entering and exiting the country, there must be an efficient and streamlined system in place to facilitate the movement of scientific products, particularly those that are time and temperature sensitive. The limited customs infrastructure, in addition to the lack of transport infrastructure and high bureaucratic

burden, are compounding factors that severely delay import and export of laboratory reagents and increase the costs associated.^{161,162}

Solutions:

It is essential to review regulations to minimise unnecessary bureaucracy and streamline both the approval and import and export processes for laboratory reagents. Establishing cross-border agreements and harmonising standards and protocols would significantly facilitate the import and export of laboratory reagents within the region. Creation of specific expedited pathways for scientific goods, particularly for verified research institutions such as universities, government agencies, and accredited private companies, could further enhance this process. This would however require significant investment in commercial infrastructure. While policy changes and legislative measures are being implemented—such as Brazil's regulatory reforms and cross-border agreements in biotechnology—rapid advancements in this area would greatly benefit both academia and industry. Accelerating the approval, import, and export of reagents represents a straightforward, effective, and measurable objective that could substantially support the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors.

2. Institutional Bureaucracy with Spending Funds

In particular within public universities, research institutions, and government institutes, researchers in some regions face internal delays when trying to receive, access and utilise funds. Regulation, traceability, and control of the utilisation of funds is very important, however excess and inefficient bureaucracy can delay research and have significant costs.¹⁶³

Solutions:

In order to better tackle this problem, targets must be set and enforced for the turnaround of funds. This could possibly be set by funding agencies. Different institutions in different countries have significantly different rules and processes, however some examples of this could be:

1. setting targets for the time taken from a researcher raising a purchase request that requires approval, and approval being granted
2. Targets for the time from acquisition of a grant to the researcher receiving funds at their institution.

¹⁶¹ 'Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with Members of Academia Involved in Biomanufacturing Research, Biomanufacturing Industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz'.

¹⁶² Flavien Moreau, Rafael Machado Parente, 'How Latin America Can Use Trade to Boost Growth'.

¹⁶³ 'Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with Members of Academia Involved in Biomanufacturing Research, Biomanufacturing Industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz'.

Where administration is required, aiming to streamline processes through the use of technology to track purchases and movement of money is essential. Furthermore, relaxation of certain rules, and enforcement based on clear traceability of funds through streamlined documentation rather than prior approval, may aid processes. It is essential that approvers of purchases have the required biotechnology and scientific expertise to make these decisions.

3. Limited Distributors and Exclusivity Deals

In some regions and fields, small and large foreign suppliers of laboratory reagents are unable to deliver goods without a local subsidiary, distributor or agent. Even where suppliers have the capacity to supply directly, or are large enough to form a local subsidiary, suppliers often choose to use third party distributors and agents. This is often due to the complexities of navigating the local environment in many South American countries, as well as potentially the relative lack of importance placed on the South American market compared to the supplier's other main markets in Europe, North America, and Asia. Many suppliers utilise exclusivity contracts with third party local distributors. Exclusivity deals significantly limit price competition and distributors rarely hold local stock to meet demand in part due to the lack of competition. This can significantly add to the lead time for procurement as local distributors must order and receive the required goods themselves before passing them on to the researcher.¹⁶⁴

Solutions:

Discouraging exclusivity deals and encouraging suppliers to distribute directly or form local subsidiaries is possible in different ways:

Through raising the profile and awareness of the market size and potential for growth, as well as reducing the legislation and simplifying the processes for registering local subsidiaries, it is possible to encourage more suppliers to deliver directly or form local subsidiaries. As South America is a growing market in biotechnology and biomanufacturing, it follows that more and more suppliers will seek to improve direct contact with researchers. Through further streamlining this process by also improving commercial, customs, and transport infrastructure, in addition to simplifying regulation, it will encourage suppliers to enter the South American market at an earlier stage. Government support for foreign suppliers seeking to enter the market, including administrative help, would further help more foreign suppliers to engage with the South American market.

¹⁶⁴ 'Interviews with Academics in Brazil, Argentina and Chile'.

From a customer's perspective, by leveraging economies of scale, through forming larger collectives to negotiate with suppliers, it is possible to attract direct supply and reduce costs. In many South American research institutions, each lab procures reagents independently. Many reagents and goods are however used widely in multiple labs. By forming systems where institutions can act as single consumers and internally distribute products, it can ease the distribution process for suppliers, and can therefore enable negotiation of better deals with suppliers. Furthermore, regular deliveries for a collective group can significantly reduce turnaround time. In cases where regulations on spending make this difficult, modification of these regulations may be beneficial.

Case Study: Socialab, Brazil

SociaLab is a reagent sharing network in Brazil that seeks to reduce waste and accelerate research through supporting the sharing and exchange of biological reagents in Brazil. Lucio Freitas Junior, a founder of the network, is a group leader conducting translational research on neglected tropical diseases including Chagas disease, Leishmaniasis, Dengue and Chikungunya, at the University of Sao Paulo.

Having experienced research both abroad in South Korea and in Brazil, Lucio Freitas identified that one of the debilitating difficulties for researchers in Brazil and more widely in South America, is the inability to acquire reagents. This has been reported to derail research projects, particularly in smaller institutions, and reduce the competitiveness of Brazilian research. In addition, due to the limited shelf-life of many reagents, there is large scale waste, and reagents must be destroyed at high cost to institutions. In order to tackle both problems, the SociaLab network aims to provide an online platform to support tracking of inventories and exchange of excess reagents.

In addition to supporting researchers, the network has even supported school students with reagents and materials for practicals, thus inspiring the next generation of scientists in Brazil.^{165,166}

4. Limited Local Production and Lack of Trust in Quality Standards for Local Products

South America has some of the lowest production levels of laboratory reagents globally, and relies heavily on foreign imports of laboratory reagents. The gross exports of Diagnostic and Laboratory Reagents (3822 HS92) was \$57.3 million USD (0.11% of global

¹⁶⁵ Interview with Lucio Freitas, Universidade de São Paulo, EMBRAPA node, SociaLab.

¹⁶⁶ ICB-USP, Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas, 'Laboratório virtual: pesquisador do ICB-USP lança plataforma de compartilhamento de reagentes', 2019
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20211201214612/https://ww3.icb.usp.br/laboratorio-virtual-pesquisador-do-icb-usp-lanca-plataforma-de-compartilhamento-de-reagentes/>>.

share) compared to imports of \$1.48 billion USD (2.94% of global share) in 2021. This displays the extent of reliance on imports, with imports being 26.7 fold higher than exports.¹⁶⁷

Nevertheless, due to the reduced requirement for expensive transport, and lower labour costs, laboratory reagents produced locally in South America do have the potential to compete with international products. This is evidenced by the successful biotechnology companies who produce reagents for the local market as well as export. The lack of local production of laboratory reagents contributes to lower competition and thereby results in higher prices. It also results in shortages when there is increased international demand for these products, as was evident during the covid-19 pandemic. It is therefore also beneficial from a national perspective to maintain capacity for local biomanufacturing and foster a local circular bioeconomy.

Even where there are firms locally producing reagents for the local market, there are challenges in convincing local users of the quality when compared to international products. This can reduce the ability of local producers to gain traction.¹⁶⁸

Solutions:

There is the potential for both direct financial support and fiscal support (tax benefits) to be utilised to promote local reagent production by local companies (see financing section). Further supporting tech transfer partnerships focused around local reagent production would significantly benefit local production as evidenced by the benefit these partnerships have had in the therapeutics field (see technology transfer section). Aid and grants tailored at helping local suppliers meet ISO/GMP certification standards and implement quality control processes, as well as provision of facilities for quality control testing that can be accessed by industry will enable local producers to demonstrate adherence to international quality standards. Scale up infrastructure, with these certifications are also required to support local producers in optimising manufacturing processes (see Infrastructure section). Furthermore, increased education, discussion, and awareness of local production and the standards and quality control processes, will aid SMEs improve quality of products and help convince consumers to purchase local products.

¹⁶⁷ The Atlas of Economic Complexity by @HarvardGrwthLab, Visualize global trade data and economic growth opportunities for every country, 'Product: Diagnostic or Laboratory Reagents (3822 HS92), in 2021' <<https://atlas.hks.harvard.edu/explore/treemap?exporter=group-1&productClass=HS92&product=product-HS92-1092&year=2021&view=markets>> [accessed 8 January 2025].

¹⁶⁸ 'Interviews with Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Companies in Brazil, Argentina and Chile, Including Enzyme Manufacturers'.

Case Study: NexVitro, Local Production of Enzymes in Campinas, Brazil

NexVitro is a Brazilian start-up based in Campinas that produces enzymes, reagents and kits for Research, Genomics and Testing. Through collaboration and initially use of open source enzymes as a startpoint, they have developed new and innovative reagents and kits that can be supplied to the local market at lower costs and with far lower turnaround times than possible through international suppliers.

During the covid-19 pandemic the company also used its expertise in the field to pivot and release products to aid diagnostics including a Sars Cov positive control. NexVitro strives to ensure their products meet the highest international quality standards with their CEO Robson Tramontina contributing towards international discussions surrounding engineering biology metrics and technical standards, and the company for example being ISO 9001 certified and striving to follow all biomanufacturing best practices.

The company's team is currently small, but is growing and provides an alternative avenue for employment for researchers in Brazil, for whom current options outside academia that value their skills can be limited. The company helps staff train and develop skills and expertise in protein manufacture which are highly valued within the biomanufacturing industry. Demonstrating the quality and effectiveness of local alternatives to international products and forming close relationships with academics is key to growing the business.^{169,170,171}

¹⁶⁹ Interviews at NexVitro, 2024.

¹⁷⁰ 'NexVitro Biologics – Produtos de Alta Tecnologia de Biologia Molecular', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241114225211/https://nexvitrobiologics.com/>> [accessed 8 January 2025].

¹⁷¹ Freemont, P.S. and others, 'Engineering Biology Metrics and Technical Standards for the Global Bioeconomy', 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.25561/110822>.

Conclusion

South America has the potential to emerge as a global leader in biotechnology and biomanufacturing. Achieving this vision requires the implementation of holistic bioeconomy policies that address existing challenges and maximise the region's strengths. By drawing inspiration from the successful regional and international examples presented within this white paper, targeted policy initiatives can bridge existing gaps, foster innovation, and drive growth in biotechnology and biomanufacturing. Many recent developments in the region are promising, including progress towards harmonising regulations, the development of international agreements, and updates to innovation laws. However, governments must act with greater urgency to remain competitive in the rapidly evolving global landscape. There is an urgent need to increase R&D financing, both public and private, which remains below global norms. It is also essential to support technology transfer, address deficiencies in trade and scale-up infrastructure, review legislation and regulations to keep pace with rapid advancements, and reduce inefficiencies caused by bureaucracy. With strategic action, the region can fully realise its potential and position itself as a frontrunner in the global bioeconomy.

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References

- '1 ° Censo Argentino de Empresas y Startups Bio y Nano', 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163705/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/presentacion_resultados_censo_bionano_28.11.23.pptx.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Academics and biotechnology industry members in Argentina, Brazil, and Chile, Interviews were conducted in 2024
- 'Access and Benefit-Sharing Clearing-House | Access and Benefit-Sharing Clearing-House', *Country Profiles, Nagoya Protocol*
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209125330/https://absch.cbd.int/en/countries>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Adam Hayes, 'What Is a Simple Agreement for Future Equity (SAFE)?', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142038/https://www.investopedia.com/simple-agreement-for-future-equity-8414773>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Adrián G. Rodríguez, Mónica Rodrigues, and Octavio Sotomayor, *Towards a Sustainable Bioeconomy in Latin America and the Caribbean: Elements for a Regional Vision, Natural Resources and Development Series, N°193* (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), 2019)
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155749/https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/a5bb120f-925a-4d8d-bcf4-68883a44d6b0/content>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- AgbiInvestor GM Monitor, 'Global GM Crop Area Review', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155147/https://fundacion-antama.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Global-GM-Crop-Area-Review.pdf>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo, 'Consolidación de Las Oficinas de Transferencia y Licenciamiento (OTL) 2024 - ANID'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152329/https://anid.cl/concursos/consolidacion-de-las-oficinas-de-transferencia-y-licenciamiento-otl-2024/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'AgroPages-Chile Launches National Center of Bioinputs to Reduce Agrochemicals Use-Agricultural News'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222143457/https://news.agropages.com/News/NewsDetail---48156.htm>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Aicha Otmani and Flavia Firmino, 'CMC Requirements for New Drug Registration in Latin America | Pharmaceutical Engineering', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153540/https://ispe.org/pharmaceutical-engineering/may-june-2023/cmc-requirements-new-drug-registration-latin-america>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- ALRC, 'Economic Benefits of the Patent System; Genes and Ingenuity: Gene Patenting and Human Health (ALRC Report 99)'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240715203425/https://www.alrc.gov.au/publication/genes-and-ingenuity-gene-patenting-and-human-health-alrc-report-99/2-the-patent-system/economic-benefits-of-the-patent-system/>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Alvarez, Diego E., María F. Lodeiro, Silvio J. Ludueña, Lía I. Pietrasanta, and Andrea V. Gamarnik, 'Long-Range RNA-RNA Interactions Circularize the Dengue Virus Genome', *Journal of Virology*, 79.11 (2005), pp. 6631–43, doi:10.1128/jvi.79.11.6631-6643.2005
- Ana Gabriela Rissato, Visit to LEMeB, 2024
- Andre Tortato Rauen, *Strengthening Brazil's Innovation Policy through Public Procurement* (ipea - Institute for Applied Economic Research, July 2023), p. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.38116/td2895-eng>
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241218160953/https://repositorio.ipea.gov.br/bitstream/11058/12169/1/dp_2895.pdf>
- Andrea Yankelevich, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Argentina, USDA', 2023

- <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153433/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Buenos%20Aires_Argentina_AR2023-0016> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Andrés Couve, 'Columna de Andrés Couve: Transferencia Tecnológica: Capturar Oportunidades Del Alto Impacto - La Tercera', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240816164620/https://www.latercera.com/opinion/noticia/columna-de-andres-couve-transferencia-tecnologica-capturar-oportunidades-del-alto-impacto/MUF5YEBO6VHZHIW6YTBLKA5TJM/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Andrés Engler, 'GRIDX: Argentina Is Leading Latin America's Bright Future in Biotech', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240616093307/https://agfundernews.com/gridx-ceo-on-why-argentina-is-leading-latin-americas-boom-in-biotech-innovation>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Anjam Aziz, 'The Time Is Now to Address Brazil's Notorious Patent Backlog', 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222114354/https://phrma.org/Blog/the-time-is-now-to-address-brazils-notorious-patent-backlog>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Anna Rose Welch, 'A Deep Dive Into Brazil's Biosimilar PDPs', 2017
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222170856/https://www.biosimilardevelopment.com/doc/a-deep-dive-into-brazil-s-biosimilar-pdps-0001>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- ANTONY SGUAZZIN, 'Top Vaccine Maker Seeks Growth by Selling Shots to Globetrotters - The Japan Times', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240510185701/https://www.japantimes.co.jp/business/2023/10/05/companies/india-vaccine-maker-growth/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Ayesha Siddiqui, 'How Asia Is Emerging As Biomanufacturing Powerhouse | Biospectrum Asia Edition', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241008062247/https://www.biospectrumasia.com/analysis/25/24981/how-asia-is-emerging-as-biomanufacturing-powerhouse-.html>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Azua-Bustos, Armando, and Carlos González-Silva, 'Biotechnological Applications Derived from Microorganisms of the Atacama Desert', *BioMed Research International*, 2014 (2014), p. 909312, doi:10.1155/2014/909312
- Baker McKenzie, 'Argentina: Promotion of Modern Biotechnology and Nanotechnology'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20221130133523/https://insightplus.bakermckenzie.com/bm/tax/argentina-promotion-of-modern-biotechnology-and-nanotechnology>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Barbosa, Luciana Gomes, Maria Alice Santos Alves, and Carlos Eduardo Viveiros Grelle, 'Actions against Sustainability: Dismantling of the Environmental Policies in Brazil', *Land Use Policy*, 104 (2021), p. 105384, doi:10.1016/j.landusepol.2021.105384
- 'Bec.Ar | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240529030741/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/becar/en>> [accessed 10 December 2024]
- Benítez Candia, Nidia, María Gabriela Ulke Mayans, Pablo Hernán Sotelo, Eva Nara Pereira, Andrea Alejandra Arrúa Alvarenga, and Danilo Fernández Ríos, 'Paraguay's Approach to Biotechnology Governance: A Comprehensive Guide', *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 12 (2024), doi:10.3389/fbioe.2024.1373473
- 'Biodiversity, Australia State of the Environment Report 2001 (Theme Report): The Meaning, Significance and Implications of Biodiversity (Megadiverse Countries)', 2008
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20081208141905/http://www.environment.gov.au/soe/2001/publications/theme-reports/biodiversity/biodiversity01-3.html>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- 'Bioeconomía | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163902/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura/bioeconomia>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Bioeconomy Strategy - European Commission'
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160737/https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Biomanufacturing Global Series: Europe's Opportunity to Grow - Europabio', 2024

- <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103172805/https://www.europabio.org/biomanufacturing-global-series/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Biosafety Clearing-House, 'The Cartagena Protocol |About the Protocol'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241121024415/https://bch.cbd.int/protocol/background>> [accessed 21 November 2024]
- 'Biología Argentina al Año 2030: Llave Estratégica Para Un Modelo de Desarrollo Tecno-Productivo.' (Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Productiva, 2016)
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163754/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/est_bio_biologia-argentina-al-2030-documento-final.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'BIOTECOSUR - Primera Plataforma de Biotecnologías Del MERCOSUR'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250104164408/https://www.recyt.mercosur.int/biotecosur/en/biotecosur.php>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- 'Biotimize'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222145533/https://www.biotimize.com.br/cdm0/>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Acerca de Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103143936/https://www.cabiotec.com.ar/acerca-de-la-cab>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- , 'Se Presentaron Los Resultados Del Primer Censo Biotecnológico y Nanotecnológico', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163554/https://www.cabiotec.com.ar/post/se-presentaron-los-resultados-del-primer-censo-biotecnol%C3%B3gico-y-nanotecnol%C3%B3gico>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Camila Aquino, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Brazil, USDA', 2022
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240723030121/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Brasilia_Brazil_BR2022-0064.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Carlos Casado, 'Uruguay and the PCT: A Strategic Step towards Global Patent Protection - European Commission', 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241211011153/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/uruguay-and-pct-strategic-step-towards-global-patent-protection-2023-12-22_en> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Carolina Castro, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Brazil, USDA', 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240627224402/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Brasilia_Brazil_BR2023-0027.pdf> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- Cerda, Ariel, Alejandro Aravena, Valentina Zapata, Anibal Arce, Wladimir Araya, Domingo Gallardo, and others, 'Open Educational Resources for Distributed Hands-on Teaching in Molecular Biology' (bioRxiv, 2024), p. 2024.03.28.587173, doi:10.1101/2024.03.28.587173
- Clarivate Analytics, '28/05/2024 , Query Web of Science: Biodiversity (Topic) OR Ecology (Topic) OR Conservation (Topic) AND "Amazon" (All Fields); Document Type: Article , Countries/Regions: BRAZIL , Publication Years: 2019 or 2020 or 2021 or 2022 or 2023', 2024
- , 'Researcher/Faculty - Essential Science Indicators - LibGuides at Clarivate Analytics'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240924033210/https://clarivate.libguides.com/c.php?g=593878&p=4107961>> [accessed 9 January 2025]
- , 'Web of Science; Search: Biotechnology (All Fields) and Article (Document Types) and BRAZIL or ARGENTINA or CHILE or COLOMBIA or PERU or BOLIVIA or ECUADOR or GUYANA or FRENCH GUIANA or FALKLAND ISLAND or PARAGUAY or URUGUAY or VENEZUELA or SURINAME (Countries/Regions) Date Run: Thu Jan 09 2025 16:32:43 GMT+0000 (Greenwich Mean Time) Results: 15384'
- 'CONABIA | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222164310/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura/bioeconomia/biotecnologia/conabia>> [accessed 6 January 2025]

- Consejo Asesor Ministerial 2022, 'Documento de Trabajo N°1, Una Propuesta de Crecimiento Del Ecosistema de Ciencia, Tecnología, Conocimiento e Innovación En Chile', 2022
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20220718160021/https://minciencia.gob.cl/uploads/filer_public/6b/af/6baf786c-44b6-4120-90a2-563bb3e3d53e/consejo_asesor_ministerial_dt01-crecimiento_del_sistema_ctci.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- CONSEJO NACIONAL DE CIENCIA, TECNOLOGIA, CONOCIMIENTO E INNOVACIÓN, 'SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, KNOWLEDGE & INNOVATION NATIONAL STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILE - 2022', 2022
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250103150423/https://docs.consejocctci.cl/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/CTCI_Estrategia-2022-ingles.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- CORFO, 'CORFO - Corporación de Fomento de La Producción', 2018
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250106115853/https://corfo.cl/sites/cpp/sala_de_prensa/nacional/09-03-2017_estrategia_de_biotechnologia> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'CORFO - Corporación de Fomento de la Producción', CORFO
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241112221306/https://www.corfo.cl/sites/cpp/webingles>> [accessed 12 December 2024]
- Cortez, L., L. Nogueira, M. Leal, Ricardo, and Baldassin Junior, 'The 22nd International Symposium on Alcohol Fuels – 22 ISAF 40 Years of the Brazilian Ethanol Program (Proálcool): Relevant Public Policies and Events Throughout Its Trajectory and Future Perspectives', 2016
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20230127003718/https://bioenfapesp.org/gsb/lacaf/documents/papers/05_ISAF_2016_Cortez_et_al.pdf> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- da Cunha Bustamante, Mercedes Maria, Juliana Hipólito, Pedro Gabriel Godinho Delgado, Lucas Ferrante, and Mariana M. Vale, 'The Future of Brazilian Science', *Nature Human Behaviour*, 7.6 (2023), pp. 825–27, doi:10.1038/s41562-023-01597-7
- Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, Government of India, 'National Biotechnology Development Strategy Document for 2021-2025, Knowledge and Innovation Driven Bio-Economy'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230811150255/https://dbtindia.gov.in/sites/default/files/National%20Biotechnology%20Development%20Strategy%202021-25.pdf>>
- Di Cross, Simon Thomson, and Alexandra Sinclair, 'Research in Brazil, A Report for CAPES by Clarivate Analytics', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230716164843/http://www.gov.br/capes/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/17012018-capes-incitesreport-final-pdf>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), *European Bioeconomy Policy: Stocktaking and Future Developments : Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/997651>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Doctorado En Ingeniería y Ciencias Con La Industria (Ex Doctorado En Ingeniería y Tecnología)', *Escuela de Graduados*
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209220344/https://doctorados.uc.cl/programa/doctorado-en-ingenieria-y-ciencias-con-la-industria/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean, 'Latin America and the Caribbean Must Address Crisis in Learning If It Wants to Move towards More Productive, Inclusive, Sustainable and Democratic Development' (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean)
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241002203140/https://www.cepal.org/en/news/latin-america-and-caribbean-must-address-crisis-learning-if-it-wants-move-towards-more>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Emma Barraclough, 'What Myriad Means for Biotech', *Wipo-Magazine*, 2013
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214195238/https://www.wipo.int/en/web/wipo-magazine/articles/what-myriad-means-for-biotech-38556>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Empresa Brasileira de Pesquisa e Inovação Industrial, 'MANUAL DE OPERAÇÃO DA

- EMBRAPII', 2024
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142406/https://embrapii.org.br/wp-content/images/2021/07/Manual_EMBRAPII_UE_versao-6.0-de-20.10.20.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'Engineering Biology - Committees - UK Parliament'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240419082135/https://committees.parliament.uk/work/8377/engineering-biology/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- European Commission, 'Brazil (CNPq)-Italy (CNR) Call for Joint Projects | EURAXESS', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162750/https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/worldwide/lac/news/brazil-cnpq-italy-cnr-call-joint-projects>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- , 'Building the Future with Nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160243/https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52024DC0137>>
- , 'Questions and Answers on the Communication on Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing', 2024
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250106163823/https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/qanda_24_1571/QANDA_24_1571_EN.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- European Council of Bioregions (CEBR) and European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), 'Together for Tackling the Biomanufacturing & Breakthrough Technologies Challenges in Europe', 2021
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241220142503/http://eithealth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Executive-summary-07102021.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Executive Office of the President, President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, 'REPORT TO THE PRESIDENT Biomanufacturing to Advance the Bioeconomy', 2022
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241128021238/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/PCAST_Biomanufacturing-Report_Dec2022.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Fabio F. Kujawski, Maria Fernanda De Almeida Prado, Ana Candida Sammarco, and Juliana Gebara De Sene, 'New Science, Technology And Innovation Act', 2016
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103113254/https://www.mondaq.com/brazil/government-contracts-procurement-ppp/467024/new-science-technology-and-innovation-act8203>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales - Universidad de Buenos Aires, 'Proteínas Hechas En Casa', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230401180033/https://exactas.uba.ar/proteinas-hechas-en-casa/>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- FAPESP, 'PROGRAMA FAPESP PESQUISA INOVATIVA EM PEQUENAS EMPRESAS - PIPE'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240804141600/https://fapesp.br/58/programa-fapesp-pesquisa-inovativa-em-pequenas-empresas-pipe>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- , 'The São Paulo Research Foundation'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241008083745/https://fapesp.br/en/about>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos (Finep), Brazil, 'Our Programs', 2024
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162221/http://finep.gov.br/aceso-a-informacao-externo/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=4723&Itemid=500> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- , 'Sobre a Finep', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222161927/http://www.finep.gov.br/a-finep-externo/sobre-a-finep>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- 'Finep e FAPESP Disponibilizam R\$ 30 Milhões Para Pesquisas Em Pequenas Empresas', ABES, 2018
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214192133/https://abes.com.br/en/finep-e-fapesp>>

- disponibilizam-r-30-milhoes-para-pesquisas-em-pequenas-empresas/> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- 'Finep Propriedade Intelectual'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214190741/http://www.finep.gov.br/apoio-e-financiamento-externa/programas-e-linhas/finep-propriedade-intelectual>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Flavien Moreau, Rafael Machado Parente, 'How Latin America Can Use Trade to Boost Growth', *IMF*, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222152238/https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2023/11/16/how-latin-america-can-use-trade-to-boost-growth>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Freemont, P.S., Ni, C., Aurand, E., Chang, M.W., Hook-Barnard, I., Malley, J., and others, 'Engineering Biology Metrics and Technical Standards for the Global Bioeconomy', 2024, doi:<https://doi.org/10.25561/110822>
- Gabriela Salerno, Clarissa Jaegger, Ana Paula Brito, Stephany Araújo e Maria Eduarda Junqueira, sócias do escritório Montaury Pimenta, Machado & Vieira de Mello, 'Principais Desenvolvimentos Na Área de Propriedade Intelectual No Brasil Em 2022', *Análise Editorial*
<<https://en.analise.com/opiniao/principais-desenvolvimentos-na-area-de-propriedade-intelectual-no-brasil-em-2022>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Gale Business: Insights, 'Brazil - Biotechnology.' *Biotechnology in Brazil*, 29 Sept. 2023. *Gale Business: Insights*, 29 September 2023
<link.gale.com/apps/doc/A770793292/GBIB?u=cambuni&sid=bookmark-GBIB&xid=c617a474>
- Gilli, Rosario Silva, 'Genetically Modified Organisms in MERCOSUR', in *The Regulation of Genetically Modified Organisms: Comparative Approaches*, ed. by Luc Bodiguel and Michael Cardwell (Oxford University Press, 2010), p. 0, doi:[10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199542482.003.0012](https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199542482.003.0012)
- Global Product Compliance Group, 'The New Regulatory Landscape in Brazil, Colombia, and Chile', 2022
<[https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153720/https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/new-regulatory-landscape-brazil-colombia->](https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153720/https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/new-regulatory-landscape-brazil-colombia-) [accessed 4 January 2025]
- 'Global Startup Ecosystem Ranking 2023 (Top 30 + Runners-Up)| Startup Genome'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103170739/https://startupgenome.com/article/global-startup-ecosystem-ranking-2023-top-30-plus-runners-up>>
- Gomes, Cristiano M., Giovanni Marchini, Jose de Bessa, Gustavo Carvalhal, Marina P. R. Caldeira, Paulo Hilario Saldiva, and others, 'The Landscape of Biomedical Research Funding in Brazil: A Current Overview', *International Brazilian Journal of Urology: Official Journal of the Brazilian Society of Urology*, 50.2 (2024), pp. 209–22, doi:[10.1590/S1677-5538.IBJU.2024.9905](https://doi.org/10.1590/S1677-5538.IBJU.2024.9905)
- 'Government Presents the First National Policy on Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation - Gob.Cl', 2020
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240910085436/https://www.gob.cl/en/news/government-presents-first-national-policy-science-technology-knowledge-and-innovation/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Grand View Research, *Biotechnology Market Size, Share & Growth Report, 2030*
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250106141038/https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/biotechnology-market>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'GSER 2023| Startup Genome', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103162504/https://startupgenome.com/report/gser2023>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Guimaraes, Sonia K., and Regis L.G. Barcelos, 'Brazilian Company for Industrial Research and Innovation: A New Generation of STI Policy Mechanisms for the Modernisation of the Productive Sector', *Science, Technology and Society*, 28.2 (2023), pp. 297–318, doi:[10.1177/09717218221125925](https://doi.org/10.1177/09717218221125925)
- Heinrich, Michael, Francesca Scotti, Adolfo Andrade-Cetto, Monica Berger-Gonzalez, Javier Echeverría, Fabio Friso, and others, 'Access and Benefit Sharing Under the Nagoya

- Protocol—Quo Vadis? Six Latin American Case Studies Assessing Opportunities and Risk', *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 11 (2020), p. 765, doi:10.3389/fphar.2020.00765
- 'Higher Education Digital Transformation in Latin America and the Caribbean' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20231221055036/https://www.holoniq.com/notes/higher-education-digital-transformation-in-latin-america-and-the-caribbean-1>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- 'Home | OBN', *OBN* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103013741/https://obn.org.uk/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Home • Protera', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241002135606/https://www.proterabio.com/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- 'Home - Zentyne1', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240613145917/https://zentyne1.com/en/>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'How Brazil's Resilient Research Ecosystem Weathered Funding Cuts' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162941/https://www.nature.com/articles/d42473-023-00323-1>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- IBIS World, 'Performance - L6724-GL Global Biotechnology - MyIBISWorld', 2024 <<https://my-ibisworld-com.cjbs.idm.oclc.org/gl/en/industry/l6724-gl/performance>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- ICB-USP, Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas, 'Laboratório virtual: pesquisador do ICB-USP lança plataforma de compartilhamento de reagentes', 2019 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20211201214612/https://ww3.icb.usp.br/laboratorio-virtual-pesquisador-do-icb-usp-lanca-plataforma-de-compartilhamento-de-reagentes/>>
- INPI, 'Activity Report', 2017 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240216190451/https://www.gov.br/inpi/pt-br/composicao/arquivos/relatorio-de-atividades-inpi-2017-english-version.pdf>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'INPI Updates Examination Rules in Order to Drive down the Patent Backlog - IAM', 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20231202085440/https://www.iam-media.com/article/inpi-updates-examination-rules-in-order-drive-down-the-patent-backlog>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Institute of Man and Environment of the Amazon, 'Strengthening Environmental Management in the Amazon' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209115413/https://www.amazonfund.gov.br/en/projeto/Strengthening-Environmental-Management-in-the-Amazon/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Instituto Nacional da Propriedade Industrial, 'Backlog Combat Plan — Instituto Nacional Da Propriedade Industrial', 2020 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222113442/https://www.gov.br/inpi/en/services/patents/backlog-combat-plan>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Interagency Working Group and THE WHITE HOUSE, 'Building the Bioworkforce of the Future Expanding Equitable Pathways into Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Jobs', 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241228020212/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Building-the-Bioworkforce-of-the-Future.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, 'Report for Selected Countries and Subjects', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222154457/https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/weo-database/2023/October/weo-report?c=213,218,223,228,233,248,336,288,293,366,298,299,&s=NGDPD,PPPGDP,&sy=2022&ey=2023&ssm=0&scsm=0&sc=0&ssd=1&ssc=0&sic=0&sort=country&ds=.&br=1>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- International Science Council, 'Support for the Integrity of Argentina's Science System - International Science Council', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103145812/https://council.science/blog/support-for-the-integrity-of-argentinascience-system/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]

- International Trade Administration, U.S. Department of Commerce, 'Japan Bioeconomy Strategy', 2021
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103165143/https://www.trade.gov/market-intelligence/japan-bioeconomy-strategy>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- International Union for Conservation of Nature, 'South America | IUCN'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209103751/https://iucn.org/our-work/region/south-america>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- , 'The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species', *IUCN Red List of Threatened Species*
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240608194700/https://www.iucnredlist.org/statistics>>
 [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Interview with Christian Hernandez Zentynel, 2024
- Interview with Eduardo Wallach, Kura Biotech
- Interview with Emiliano Trias, Xeptiva Therapeutics, 2024
- Interview with Javiera Espoz, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Technology Transfer Office
- Interview with Lucio Freitas, Universidade de São Paulo, EMBRAPA node, SocialLab
- Interviews at CPPR, Universidad de Buenos Aires
- Interviews at NexVitro, 2024
- Interviews in Brazil, Argentina and Chile with members of academia involved in biomanufacturing research, biomanufacturing industry, and the Brazilian Government Research Institutes, Instituto Butantan and Fiocruz
- Interviews with Academics in Brazil, Argentina and Chile, 2024
- Interviews with Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing companies in Brazil, Argentina and Chile, including enzyme manufacturers
- Interviews with multiple Startups and academics in São Paulo State
- Interviews with researchers and Technology Transfer offices, Brazil, Argentina and Chile
- Interviews with SMEs in Brazil and Chile, 2024
- Interviews with Startups in the region, University Technology Transfer Offices, and a venture capital firm
- Jenny Blamey and Giannina Espina, Interview at Fundación Biociencia
- Jonathan Adams, David Pendlebury, Martin Szomszor, and Ross Potter, *Global Research Report: Latin America: South and Central America, Mexico and the Caribbean*; (Institute for Scientific Information)
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20240812185033/https://clarivate.com/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2022/09/ISI-GRR-Q3-2021-LatAm_Report_EN_Report_Digital_V5-1-1-2.pdf> [accessed 12 December 2024]
- Jonathan Smith, 'France's Grand Plan to Lead Europe's Biotech Innovation Landscape | LABIOTECH', 2022
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103162211/https://www.labiotech.eu/in-depth/france-biotech-innovation-2030/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Jorge Lima, 'Startup Genome, Brazil Sao Paulo'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152922/https://startupgenome.com/ecosystems/sao-paulo>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Kowaltowski, Alicia J., 'Brazil's Scientists Face 90% Budget Cut', *Nature*, 598.7882 (2021), pp. 566–566, doi:10.1038/d41586-021-02882-z
- KRISTAL TONINI LIBERMAN, YURI C. R. SCHRAMM, and GABRIEL BERETTA DE OLIVEIRA MATTOS, 'INPI Publishes New Strategic Plan', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222114937/https://www.machadomeyer.com.br/en/recent-publications/publications/intellectual-property/inpi-publishes-new-strategic-plan>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'Kura Biotech | Home'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241125231847/https://www.kurabiotech.com/>>
 [accessed 9 December 2024]
- 'LEMeB - 2022'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209135358/https://sites.google.com/site/unicampfealemeb/our-publications/articles/2022?authuser=0https://sites.google.com/site/unicampfealemeb/our-research>> [accessed 9 December 2024]

- 'LEMeB - Research'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241209131754/https://sites.google.com/site/unicamp/ealemeb/our-research>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Luiz Catalani, Director of AUSPIN
- Maloney, William, Pablo Garriga, Marcela Meléndez, Raúl Morales, Charl Jooste, James Sampi, and others, *Latin America and the Caribbean Economic Review, April 2024: Competition: The Missing Ingredient for Growth?* (The World Bank, 2024), doi:10.1596/978-1-4648-2111-0
- Manuel Rozas, Eduardo Wallach, Isa Marx, María José Nuñez, and Felipe Cárdenas Santana, Visit to Kura Biotech, 2024
- Marcelo Becerra, Juan Diego Alonso, and Micheline Frias, *Latin America and the Caribbean: Tertiary Education; COVID-19 CORONAVIRUS RESPONSE*
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240911164841/https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/738931611934489480-0090022021/original/LACTEandCovidupdated.pdf>>
- Marianne Fay, Luis Alberto Andres, Charles Fox, Ulf Narloch, Stephane Straub, and Michael Slawson, *Rethinking Infrastructure in Latin America and the Caribbean, Spending Better to Achieve More* (The World Bank, 22 December 2024)
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222143243/https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/pt/676711491563967405/114110-REVISED-Rethinking-Infrastructure-Low-Res.pdf>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Marley Brocker, L6724-GL ; *Global Business Activities; Global Biotechnology - IBISWorld*, October 2024
- Mcmanus, Concepta, and Carlos A. Nobre, 'Brazilian Scientific Mobility Program - Science without Borders* - Preliminary Results and Perspectives**', *Anais Da Academia Brasileira de Ciências*, 89 (2017), pp. 773–86, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-3765201720160829>
- de Mello, Renata Gois, Thaissa Consoni Bernardino, Luis Giovanni Oliveira Guardalini, Renato Mancini Astray, Marta Maria Antoniazzi, Simone Gonçalves Silva Jared, and others, 'Zika Virus-like Particles (VLPs) Produced in Insect Cells', *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 14 (2023), doi:10.3389/fphar.2023.1181566
- 'MERCOSUR Countries - MERCOSUR', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241231051802/https://www.mercosur.int/en/about-mercosur/mercosur-countries/>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- 'MERCOSUR in Brief - MERCOSUR', 2025
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103110403/https://www.mercosur.int/en/about-mercosur/mercosur-in-brief/>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- MILEUSNIC MARIN and RAGONNAUD Guillaume, 'Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP), Briefing', 2024
 <[https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160136/https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/754547/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)754547_EN.pdf](https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160136/https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/754547/EPRS_BRI(2023)754547_EN.pdf)>
- Millie Nelson, 'Biotimize Looks to Build First Biological CDMO in Brazil - BioProcess Insider', 2022
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240725102645/https://www.bioprocessintl.com/facilities-capacity/biotimize-looks-to-build-first-biological-cdmo-in-brazil>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- MINCYT Argentina and Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, 'DIAGNOSIS AND ROADMAP FOR AN OPEN SCIENCE POLICY IN ARGENTINA', 2022
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222142921/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/2023/01/cac_final_document_-_english_version.pdf> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Brazil, 'Plano de Ação Em Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação', 2016
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222161739/https://antigo.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/ciencia/SEPED/Publicacoes/ENCTI/PlanosDeAcao.html%20>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovações, Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos, 'Subvenção Econômica à Inovação – 18/2022 Biotechnology Aplicada Aos Temas

- Atuais de Saúde Humana, Agropecuária, Meio Ambiente e Indústria’
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240804110931/http://www.finep.gov.br/images/chamadas-publicas/2022/19_09_2022_Bio_Edital_Rerratificado.pdf> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI), Japan, ‘Investing in Biotech, From Plastics That Melt in the Sea to Cultured Foie Gras, Japan Is Pushing Innovative Technologies Forward with Government Support’, *The ACCJ Journal*, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240921054552/https://journal.accj.or.jp/content/2023/1/investing-in-biotech>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Morgan Pincombe , Anthony McDonnell and Javier Guzman, ‘Leveraging Brazilian Leadership and Procurement Arrangements in the Fight Against Antimicrobial Resistance, Centre for Global Development’, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240620050222/https://www.cgdev.org/publication/leveraging-brazilian-leadership-and-procurement-arrangements-fight-against>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Myers, Norman, Russell A. Mittermeier, Cristina G. Mittermeier, Gustavo A. B. da Fonseca, and Jennifer Kent, ‘Biodiversity Hotspots for Conservation Priorities’, *Nature*, 403.6772 (2000), pp. 853–58, doi:10.1038/35002501
- National Commission for Scientific and Technological Research CONICYT, *Chile: Opportunities for International Cooperation in STI*, 2015
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240701122916/https://www.conicyt.cl/pci/files/2015/08/OPORTUNIDADES_Aug-2015-completo_spreads.pdf>
- National Geographic, ‘South America: Physical Geography’
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240803010203/https://education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/south-america-physical-geography/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Nelson Ramirez, ‘Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Chile, USDA’, 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20231203051130/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Santiago_Chile_CI2023-0025.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- ‘New Report Presents a Comparative International Study on Biotech Patentability Standards and Criteria | CEPAL’, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222134109/https://www.cepal.org/en/notes/new-report-presents-comparative-international-study-biotech-patentability-standards-and>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- ‘NexVitro Biologics – Produtos de Alta Tecnologia de Biologia Molecular’, 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241114225211/https://nexvitrobiologics.com/>> [accessed 8 January 2025]
- ‘NIBSC - About Us’
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222152118/https://nibsc.org/about_us.aspx> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- ‘NIBSC - Contract Testing’
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222151904/https://nibsc.org/expert_services/contract_testing.aspx> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- OECD, and Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, *Latin American Agriculture: Prospects and Challenges* (OECD, 8 July 2019), pp. 70–124, doi:10.1787/b2b742eb-en
- OHNO Takahiro, ‘Japan’s Bioeconomy Strategy’s Featuring Points, G20 OECD-BNCT WORKSHOP, Bioeconomy in the OECD Countries, Presidency of Council of Ministers, July 16, 2021’
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103165312/https://cnbbsv.palazzochigi.it/media/2419/ohno-japan-panel1.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Oliveira, Danielle B. L., Giuliana S. Durigon, Érica A. Mendes, Jason T. Ladner, Robert Andreato-Santos, Danielle B. Araujo, and others, ‘Persistence and Intra-Host Genetic Evolution of Zika Virus Infection in Symptomatic Adults: A Special View in the Male Reproductive System’, *Viruses*, 10.11 (2018), p. 615, doi:10.3390/v10110615
- ‘PAHO Highlights Increase in Dengue, Oropouche, and Avian Influenza Cases in the Americas, and Advises Control Measures - PAHO/WHO | Pan American Health

- Organization', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241211164744/https://www.paho.org/en/news/10-12-2024-paho-highlights-increase-dengue-oropouche-and-avian-influenza-cases-america-as-and#:~:text=Dengue%3A%20Historic%20epidemic%20in%20the%20Americas&text=Countries%20have%20reported%20more%20than,Brazil%20having%20the%20largest%20share.>> [accessed 12 December 2024]
- Paola Barr, Dr. Michiel Kolman, Valeria Rinaudo, and Dr. Carlos Henrique, *Biodiversity Research in 2024: A Global Perspective with a Focus on Latin America* (Elsevier, 2024)
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241212161826/https://assets.ctfassets.net/zlnfab2lqx/6G90mMrjWGpDpSoKQKaNRS/e59f74b825b235749c0d2231c26cdb63/Elsevier-biodiversity-research-report-2024.pdf>>
- 'Patentes: Integrarnos al Mundo - LA NACION', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230619071548/https://www.lanacion.com.ar/editoriales/patentes-integrarnos-al-mundo-nid13062023/>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- P.Attewell, K.S.Newman (editors) and Cristián Cox, 'EDUCATIONAL INEQUALITY IN LATIN AMERICA. PATTERNS, POLICIES AND ISSUES.', in *Growing Gaps. Educational Inequality Around the World*. (Oxford University Press: Oxford, New York), p. Chapter 2
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240630102311/https://liderazgoeducativo.udp.cl/cms/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Educational-inequality-in-Latin-America-patterns-policies-and-issues.-Oxford-University-Press-New-York-2010..pdf>>
- Pedro Moreira, 'Updated Landscape on Expedited Protection of "Green" Inventions in Brazil', 2021
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222112822/https://www3.wipo.int/wipogreen/en/news/2021/news_0016.html> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Pimenta, Marcela Valente, and Gisele Monteiro, 'The Production of Biopharmaceuticals in Brazil: Current Issues', *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 55 (2019), p. e17823, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/s2175-97902019000217823>
- PRC State Council, Translated by Ben Murphy, Etcetera Language Group, Inc, 'Translation: Notice of the State Council on the Publication of "Made in China 2025"', 2015
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250103171220/https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/t0432_made_in_china_2025_EN.pdf>
- PROF. VLADIMIR FERNANDES MACIEL, *The Status of Intellectual Property Rights in Brazil* (CENTRO MACKENZIE DE LIBERDADE ECONÔMICA, BRAZIL, 21 April 2024)
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20240421031410/https://pifazacontecer.com.br/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/IPRI_2021_CaseStudy_Brazil_v1_compressed.pdf> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Rana Gosain, 'Recent Reform on Brazilian Pharmaceutical Patents Showing Results | FICPI', 2022
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222115737/https://ficpi.org/blog/recent-reform-brazilian-pharmaceutical-patents-showing-results>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Rathore, Anurag S., and Ankita Bhargava, 'Regulatory Considerations in Biosimilars: Latin America Region', *Preparative Biochemistry & Biotechnology*, 51.2 (2021), pp. 201–6, doi:10.1080/10826068.2021.1876729
- 'R&D Tax Incentives', *OECD*
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240411162656/https://www.oecd.org/innovation/tax-incentives-rd-innovation/>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- read, Yahoo Finance, 'Biotimize Announces the Opening of a Fundraising Round to Build the First Biological CDMO in Brazil', 2022
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222145643/https://finance.yahoo.com/news/biotimize-announces-opening-fundraising-round-123000346.html>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'Regional Technology and Innovation Hubs (Tech Hubs) | U.S. Economic Development Administration'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155818/https://www.eda.gov/funding/programs/regional-technology-and-innovation-hubs>> [accessed 6 January 2025]

- Reingold, Julian, 'Argentinian Scientists Condemn Budget Cuts Ahead of Protests', *Climate Home News*, 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240826024947/https://www.climatechangenews.com/2024/04/22/argentinian-scientists-condemn-budget-cuts-ahead-of-university-protests/>> [accessed 12 December 2024]
- Rezende, Kellen, Maria Sueli Soares Felipe, and Carlos Augusto Grabois Gadelha, 'Challenges for Innovation in Health: The Brazilian Experience of Public-Private Partnerships for Productive Development in the Economic Industrial Health Complex and Universal Health Coverage Context', 2021, doi:10.21203/rs.3.rs-958902/v1
- Ricardo Campello, 'Brazilian Government Resurrects Its Partnership for Productive Development (PDP) Program. A New Threat to Pharma IP Rights?', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222144819/https://www.lickslegal.com/articles/brazilian-government-resurrects-its-partnership-for-productive-development-pdp-program-a-new-threat-to-pharma-ip-rights>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- Ritchie, Hannah, and Max Roser, 'Living Planet Index: What Does It Really Mean?', *Our World in Data*, 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241113100323/https://ourworldindata.org/living-planet-index-decline>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Robert Pocklington, 'New IP Law in Chile (I): Main Changes in the Patent System - European Commission', 2022
 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241211011332/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/new-ip-law-chile-i-main-changes-patent-system-2022-09-16_en> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, 'State of the World's Plants and Fungi 2023'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241204113019/https://www.kew.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/State%20of%20the%20World%27s%20Plants%20and%20Fungi%202023.pdf>>
- Rozas, Pablo, Eduardo I. Kessi-Pérez, Claudio Martínez, Pablo Rozas, Eduardo I. Kessi-Pérez, and Claudio Martínez, 'Genetically Modified Organisms: Adapting Regulatory Frameworks for Evolving Genome Editing Technologies', *Biological Research*, 55 (2022), doi:10.1186/s40659-022-00399-x
- Rubens Granja and Natássia Misae Ueno, 'Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) and Their Application in Brazilian Agriculture and Consumer Products', 2023
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155635/https://www.ibanet.org/gmo-brazilian-agriculture>> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- Sá, Creso M., 'The Rise and Fall of Brazil's Science Without Borders', *International Higher Education*, 85, 2016, pp. 17–18, doi:10.6017/ihe.2016.85.9241
- Sánchez, M.A., and H Campos, 'Coexistence of Genetically Modified Seed Production and Organic Farming in Chile', *GM Crops & Food*, 12.1, pp. 509–19, doi:10.1080/21645698.2021.2001242
- 'Secretaría de Coordinación de Producción | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222164112/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/produccion>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 'The Nagoya Protocol on Access and Benefit-Sharing' (Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity, 2024)
 <<https://www.cbd.int/abs/default.shtml>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Segretin, Maria Eugenia, Gabriela Cynthia Soto, and Christian Damian Lorenzo, 'Latin America: A Hub for Agrobiotechnological Innovations', *Annals of Botany*, 2024, p. mcae191, doi:10.1093/aob/mcae191
- SeTIC-UFSC, 'Science Without Borders, Secretaria de Relações Internacionais | Office of International Relations'
 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20211019083513/https://sinter.ufsc.br/programa-ciencia-sem-fronteiras/?lang=en>> [accessed 10 December 2024]
- Silva, Janaina Aparecida da, and Rejane Sartori, 'Motivations and Barriers of University-Industry Cooperation: A Comparison between Brazil and Ireland', *Journal of Technology Management & Innovation*, 17.2 (2022), pp. 49–58, doi:10.4067/S0718-27242022000200049

- 'Spotlight on South America', *Nature Ecology & Evolution*, 1.4 (2017), pp. 1–2,
doi:10.1038/s41559-017-0129
- Staff and students at Universities in Brazil, Argentina and Chile
Startup Genome, 'THE GLOBAL STARTUP ECOSYSTEM REPORT 2023 Insights,
Rankings & Ecosystem Pages', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240808035800/https://startupgenome.com/article/north-america-insights-rankings-and-ecosystem-pages-1>>
- Stolf, Rubismar, and Ana Paula Rodrigues de Oliveira, 'THE SUCCESS OF THE
BRAZILIAN ALCOHOL PROGRAM (PROÁLCOOL) - A DECADE-BY-DECADE
BRIEF HISTORY OF ETHANOL IN BRAZIL', *Engenharia Agrícola*, 40 (2020), pp.
243–48, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/1809-4430-Eng.Agric.v40n2p243-248/2020>
- 'Studying Abroad - Erasmus+'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241203045228/https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/opportunities/opportunities-for-individuals/students/studying-abroad>> [accessed 10
December 2024]
- Tarso Mesquita Machado, 'BPTO Now Orders Patent Examinations Based on Date of
Submission of Examination Request | FICPI', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222120803/https://ficpi.org/ip-news/bpto-now-orders-patent-examinations-based-submission-examination>> [accessed 3 January 2025]
- 'Teaching Chemistry Labs from a Distance | ACS Central Science'
<<https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acscentsci.1c00539>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Teixeira, Marcelo, 'Higher Brazil Ethanol Blend Would Take Extra 3.5% Sugar from Market
-Citi', *Reuters*, 19 July 2023, section Business
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20230720182419/https://www.reuters.com/article/idUSL8N3955ZH>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Terradas-Cobas, Liliana, Carlos Céspedes-Payret, and Estanislao Luis Calabuig, 'Expansion
of GM Crops, Antagonisms between MERCOSUR and the EU. The Role of R&D and
Intellectual Property Rights' Policy', *Environmental Development*, 19 (2016), pp.
49–58, doi:10.1016/j.envdev.2016.06.003
- The Atlas of Economic Complexity by @HarvardGrwthLab, Visualize global trade data and
economic growth opportunities for every country, 'Product: Diagnostic or Laboratory
Reagents (3822 HS92), in 2021'
<<https://atlas.hks.harvard.edu/explore/treemap?exporter=group-1&productClass=HS92&product=product-HS92-1092&year=2021&view=markets>> [accessed 8 January
2025]
- The White House, 'FACT SHEET: The United States Announces New Investments and
Resources to Advance President Biden's National Biotechnology and
Biomanufacturing Initiative', *The White House*, 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241130010032/https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2022/09/14/fact-sheet-the-united-states-announces-new-investments-and-resources-to-advance-president-bidens-national-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-initiative/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- THE WHITE HOUSE, 'FACT SHEET: The United States Announces New Investments and
Resources to Advance President Biden's National Biotechnology and
Biomanufacturing Initiative | The White House', 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103154650/https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2022/09/14/fact-sheet-the-united-states-announces-new-investments-and-resources-to-advance-president-bidens-national-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-initiative/>>
- , 'Federal Register :: Advancing Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Innovation for a
Sustainable, Safe, and Secure American Bioeconomy, FR Doc. 2022-20167', 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103154530/https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2022/09/15/2022-20167/advancing-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-innovation-for-a-sustainable-safe-and-secure-american>>
- The White House Office of Science and Technology Policy, U.S. Department of Energy, U.S.
Department of Agriculture, U.S. Department of Commerce, U.S. Department of
Health and Human Services, and U.S. National Science Foundation, 'BOLD GOALS

- FOR U.S. BIOTECHNOLOGY AND BIOMANUFACTURING: HARNESSING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT TO FURTHER SOCIETAL GOALS', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155233/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Bold-Goals-for-U.S.-Biotechnology-and-Biomanufacturing-Harnessing-Research-and-Development-To-Further-Societal-Goals-FINAL.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- Theory Wen, 'Chile to Start Initial Registration for Industrial Chemicals Soon | ChemLinked', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103151237/https://chemical.chemlinked.com/news/chemical-news/chile-opens-it-chemical-registration-system>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Tropical Forest Loss by Leading Country 2023', *Statista*
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240820120921/https://www.statista.com/statistics/1254554/tropical-forest-loss-global-by-country/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- UNESCO Global Education Monitoring Report, 'Latin America and the Caribbean - 2020 GEM Report'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240819001138/https://gem-report-2020.unesco.org/latin-america-and-the-caribbean/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 'Science, Technology and Innovation', 2024
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241203162142/http://data.uis.unesco.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SCN_DS&lang=en> [accessed 5 January 2025]
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). UIS.Stat Bulk Data Download Service. Accessed September 30, 2024., 'Research and Development Expenditure (% of GDP) - Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, United States, China, Korea, Rep. | Data | World Bank Group', 2025
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250109203431/https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/GB.XPD.RSDV.GD.ZS?end=2021&locations=AR-BR-CL-CO-EC-US-CN-KR&start=2008> ;
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241202100550/https://api.worldbank.org/v2/en/indicator/GB.XPD.RSDV.GD.ZS?downloadformat=csv>>
- United States Department of Agriculture, Foreign Agricultural Service, 'Biofuels Annual, Brazil', 2024
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240929011650/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Biofuels%20Annual_Sao%20Paulo%20ATO_Brazil_BR2022-0047.pdf> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- U.S. Department of Agriculture, 'Building a Resilient Biomass Supply: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241128023655/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>>
- U.S. Department of Commerce, Office of Public Affairs, 'Biden-Harris Administration Launches First Tech Hubs Funding Opportunity | U.S. Department of Commerce', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155636/https://www.commerce.gov/news/press-releases/2023/05/biden-harris-administration-launches-first-tech-hubs-funding>>
- USDA (U.S. Department of Agriculture), 'BUILDING A RESILIENT BIOMASS SUPPLY: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241217011343/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- , *Table 1: BUILDING A RESILIENT BIOMASS SUPPLY: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America*, March 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241217011343/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>>
- 'Value Share of Biotech Sector by Country Worldwide 2021 | Statista', 2021
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241126213049/https://www.statista.com/statistics/1246614/top-countries-share-of-global-biotech-value/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- 'Vencemos o Prêmio Brasil Bioeconomia! – Bioprocess Improvement'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241214192846/https://bioprocessimprovement.com/e>>

- n/vencemos-o-premio-brasil-bioeconomia/> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- Vergara, Germán, 'Where the Wild Things Aren't Species Loss and Capitalisms in Latin America Since 1800 | ReVista'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240616155954/https://revista.drclas.harvard.edu/where-the-wild-things-arent/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- Verónica Canton, 'The Main Challenges When Applying for a Patent in Argentina for EU SMEs - European Commission', 2021
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241021005142/https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/news-events/news/main-challenges-when-applying-patent-argentina-eu-smes-2021-11-23_en> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- 'What Do We Know About Latin America's Lowest-Performing Education Systems? - The Dialogue', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240830001729/https://www.thedialogue.org/blogs/2019/04/latin-americas-lowest-performing-education-systems/>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- 'Who We Are - Embrapii'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20230207153600/https://embrapii.org.br/en/institutional/who-we-are/>> [accessed 12 December 2024]
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), 'Patent Expert Issues: Biotechnology'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20230528095935/https://www.wipo.int/patents/en/topics/biotechnology.html>> [accessed 14 December 2024]
- World Population Review, Data from United Nations population estimates and projections, 'South America Population 2024'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241219052436/https://worldpopulationreview.com/continents/south-america>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- 'Worldwide Strategies | Bioökonomie.De', 2025
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152517/https://biooekonomie.de/en/topics/in-depth-reports-worldwide?term_node_tid_depth=185> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- WWF, 'About the Amazon'
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241203065447/https://wwf.panda.org/discover/knowledge_hub/where_we_work/amazon/about_the_amazon/> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- , 'Amazing Discoveries in the Amazon: New Species Found Every 3 Days Over Last Decade'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240519020534/https://wwf.panda.org/?196057/Amazing-Discoveries-in-the-Amazon-New-Species-Found-Every-Three-Days-Over-Last-Decade>> [accessed 9 December 2024]
- , *Living Planet Report 2022: Building a Nature-Positive Society*, 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241009222134/https://www.wwf.org.uk/sites/default/files/2023-05/WWF-Living-Planet-Report-2022.pdf>>
- 'Xeptiva Therapeutics - Home'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241118080115/https://www.xeptiva.com/>> [accessed 4 January 2025]
- Xinhua News Agency, Translated by Ben Murphy, Etcetera Language Group, Inc., 'Translation: Outline of the People's Republic of China 14th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development and Long-Range Objectives for 2035', 2021
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241226174942/https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/t0284_14th_Five_Year_Plan_EN.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025]
- xinlei, wang, 'Biotech Investment Trends in 2023', *Patsnap*, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250106142101/https://www.patsnap.com/resources/blog/biotech-investment-trends-in-2023/>> [accessed 6 January 2025]

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<https://pixabay.com/photos/tanks-brewery-fermentation-5055929/>; modified in title page, page 1.

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<https://pixabay.com/illustrations/dna-science-biology-research-718905/>; modified in Figure 2, page 14.

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OpenClipart-Vectors 2016; Justice Measure Scale royalty-free vector graphic. Free for use & download.; via Pixabay; <https://pixabay.com/vectors/justice-measure-scale-silhouette-1296381/>; used in Figure 9, page 51.

Appendix

Appendix I: Landscape of Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in South America

South America at a Glance

South America is a diverse region made up of Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Guyana, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Uruguay, and Venezuela. The Falkland Islands/Islands Malvinas, South Georgia, the South Sandwich Islands, and French Guiana, are also included within South America. South America had a population of over 442 million in 2024, with a median age of 32.4 years and a rate of population growth of 0.7% per annum. Five countries, Brazil, Colombia, Argentina, Peru and Venezuela, make up 90 percent of the population, with Brazil having almost half the population of the region (201 million), making it the fifth most populous country in the world.^{172,173}

The largest economies in South America in 2023 (USD current prices) were Brazil (2,126.8 Billion USD), Argentina (621.8 Billion USD), Colombia (363.8 Billion USD) and Chile (344.4 Billion USD).

After the covid19 pandemic, following overall good macroeconomic management in the region, interest rates are beginning to fall, with central banks in Brazil, Chile, Colombia, and Peru continuing to cut rates following reductions in inflation (notable exceptions to this include Argentina and Venezuela). Overall economic growth in the region however remains slow compared to other regions in the world, and foreign direct investment (FDI) remains below levels of 12 years ago, despite wages being competitive with other Asian regions. This has been attributed to structural concerns requiring reforms of infrastructure, education, regulation, and competition policy. Declining fertility rates and political and social instability are factors that were reported as having the potential to exacerbate the problem.¹⁷⁴

¹⁷² International Monetary Fund, World Economic Outlook Database, 'Report for Selected Countries and Subjects', 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222154457/https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/weo-database/2023/October/weo-report?c=213,218,223,228,233,248,336,288,293,366,298,299,&s=NGDPD,PPPGDP,&sy=2022&ey=2023&ssm=0&scsm=0&sc=0&ssd=1&ssc=0&sic=0&sort=country&ds=.&br=1>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁷³ World Population Review, Data from United Nations population estimates and projections, 'South America Population 2024'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241219052436/https://worldpopulationreview.com/continents/south-america>> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁷⁴ William Maloney and others, *Latin America and the Caribbean Economic Review, April 2024: Competition: The Missing Ingredient for Growth?* (The World Bank, 2024), doi:10.1596/978-1-4648-2111-0.

Whilst the landscape in biomanufacturing and biotechnology sectors is considerably different from that of the overall economy, the latter influences overall trends and investment, and several of the shortfalls identified do have parallels within the sector.

Overview of the Landscape of Biomanufacturing

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing is rapidly growing in South America and has in many areas been recognised as a key industry of which development is a priority. South America is an incredibly diverse region and therefore the landscape varies significantly from country to country.

Biotechnology and biomanufacturing have a strong foundation in South America, many countries in the region being strong and leading adopters of agricultural biotechnology in particular. Brazil and Argentina are the second and third largest producers of GM crops internationally, with Brazil planting circa 68 million Hectares in the 2022/2023 crop season, and both these countries having a regulatory framework for the approval of GM crops. Paraguay, Uruguay, Colombia and Chile (limited to propagation of seeds) are also countries expanding in the area. Similarly, strategic cooperation between countries in the region with regards to biotechnology is being developed with Brazil, Argentina, Paraguay and Uruguay creating an International Network for the biosafety of products derived from modern biotechnology in October 2023.^{175,176}

The legislative, regulatory and policy frameworks put in place for agricultural biotechnology and the use of GM crops have often been extended for other biotechnology and biomanufacturing including that utilising microbes. This together with the health and pharmaceutical sector, chemical sector, and food sector regulation and policy, generally come together to form the regulation and policy surrounding the field.^{177,178,179}

Innovation and research and development laws and technology transfer infrastructure and legislation are also key to the development of the field. Overall, while legislation,

¹⁷⁵ Carolina Castro, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Brazil, USDA', 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20240627224402/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Brasilia_Brazil_BR2023-0027.pdf> [accessed 4 January 2025].

¹⁷⁶ AgbioInvestor GM Monitor, 'Global GM Crop Area Review', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155147/https://fundacion-antama.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Global-GM-Crop-Area-Review.pdf>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁷⁷ Carolina Castro, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Brazil, USDA'.

¹⁷⁸ Marcela Valente Pimenta and Gisele Monteiro, 'The Production of Biopharmaceuticals in Brazil: Current Issues', *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 55 (2019), p. e17823, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1590/s2175-97902019000217823>.

¹⁷⁹ Rubens Granja and Natássia Misae Ueno, 'Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) and Their Application in Brazilian Agriculture and Consumer Products', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155635/https://www.ibanet.org/gmo-brazilian-agriculture>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

regulation, and policies have been put in place in various countries, the pace of this has not kept up with progress in the field, though there are considerable differences between countries in the region. It is key to ensure that any legislation put in place is effective and not overly restrictive, while maintaining safety and the environment as priorities. The other important factor is not to add a significant bureaucratic burden. Communication with stakeholders and developers in the field is key to implementing effective regulatory and legislative change. Modification of the innovation laws and policies in multiple countries in South America, have had a positive impact on the industry and continued progress on this front will further support the sector.

From a government strategic policy perspective, although biotechnology has been recognised as an industry of importance in many countries, there have been fewer policy documents, directives, and government funding initiatives aimed at biotechnology and biomanufacturing in South America when compared to regions like Europe and the US. Activity however is growing, with Brazil and Argentina leading the way. Policy directives and incentives have been produced in many countries, including in plant and agricultural biotechnology, biofuels and bioenergy, and health biotechnology sectors, and have had success in stimulating the sector. Strategic work to identify strengths and target bottlenecks and areas of weakness across biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors is key to the continued development of biomanufacturing and biotechnology in the region. In particular, integrated biotechnology and biomanufacturing strategies in countries in South America covering all aspects of the bioeconomy, as well as cross border partnerships could help provide well rounded support for the sector.¹⁸⁰

Government policy work, directives, and funding, in many South American countries has historically been fairly unstable with changes depending heavily on the political climate. It is important also for policies, directives and strategies to withstand political changes, as an unstable political and economic climate can result in the loss of benefits. Though it is often difficult to implement change, incremental positive changes using successful strategies from within the region as templates can result in long term benefits to the industry. The recent developments in Brazil, Argentina and Chile are outlined below.

Brazil

Brazil is the largest country in the region and also one of the leaders in biotechnology and biomanufacturing. The Brazilian biotechnology market was reported to have a revenue of 16.9 billion USD in 2022 and have grown with a compound annual growth

¹⁸⁰ Adrián G. Rodríguez, Mónica Rodrigues, and Octavio Sotomayor, *Towards a Sustainable Bioeconomy in Latin America and the Caribbean: Elements for a Regional Vision, Natural Resources and Development Series, N°193* (Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC), 2019) <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222155749/https://repositorio.cepal.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/a5bb120f-925a-4d8d-bcf4-68883a44d6b0/content>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

rate (CAGR) of 6.8% between 2017 and 2022. The growth in 2022 was reported to be strong at 15.5% and a forecasted CAGR between 2022 and 2027 of 8.7%. Medical and Healthcare related biotechnology was reported to be the largest sector accounting for 8.4 billion USD in revenue (49.9%).¹⁸¹ Brazil is also the second largest producer of GM crops internationally, behind the US. São Paulo in particular is also a significant startup ecosystem, ranked 26th globally in 2023 by startup genome, the highest in South America, with USP (Universidade de São Paulo) ranked the best university in South America by the Times Higher Education.¹⁸²

Though the Brazilian biotechnology sector is growing strongly, the CAGR of the sector within the country is reported to be significantly lower than that of the US and Europe, with the US having a reported CAGR of 17.2% between 2017 and 2022. There is therefore room for significant growth and development of the sector. Brazilian R&D expenditure is still significantly below that of the leading developed economies, at 1.3% of GDP according to Unesco. Comparatively, many developed countries spend over 2% of GDP on R&D.^{183,184} Out of this R&D expenditure, private investment is also a lower percentage, and industrial public collaboration remains low, though policy changes and directives have been implemented to start to address this.¹⁸⁵

From a policy perspective Brazil has also been one of the leaders in the region, producing multiple policies targeted at biomanufacturing. It has been a particularly strong player in the agriculture and biofuel sectors. The Brazilian Science Technology and Innovation action plan, released in 2016 for the period 2016-2022, consisted of specific plans both for 'Biotechnology' and for the Bioeconomy, demonstrating the key importance of these fields.¹⁸⁶ As well as this, plans for 'Brazilian Biomes', 'Climate', 'Food and Nutrition Security' and 'Health' which have potential links to biotechnology and biomanufacturing, as well as plans for social inclusion and dissemination of science and technology, present a holistic policy framework for the area. Differing government

¹⁸¹ Gale Business: Insights, 'Brazil - Biotechnology.' *Biotechnology in Brazil*, 29 Sept. 2023. *Gale Business: Insights*, 29 September 2023

<link.gale.com/apps/doc/A770793292/GBIB?u=cambuni&sid=bookmark-GBIB&xid=c617a474>.

¹⁸² Jorge Lima, 'Startup Genome, Brazil Sao Paulo'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152922/https://startupgenome.com/ecosystems/sao-paulo>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁸³ UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 'Science, Technology and Innovation', 2024

<https://web.archive.org/web/20241203162142/http://data.uis.unesco.org/Index.aspx?DataSetCode=SCN_DS&lang=en> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁸⁴ Cristiano M. Gomes and others, 'The Landscape of Biomedical Research Funding in Brazil: A Current Overview', *International Brazilian Journal of Urology: Official Journal of the Brazilian Society of Urology*, 50.2 (2024), pp. 209–22, doi:10.1590/S1677-5538.IBJU.2024.9905.

¹⁸⁵ Di Cross, Simon Thomson, and Alexandra Sinclair, 'Research in Brazil, A Report for CAPES by Clarivate Analytics', 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20230716164843/http://www.gov.br/capes/pt-br/centrais-de-conteudo/17012018-capes-incitesreport-final-pdf>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁸⁶ Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Brazil, 'Plano de Ação Em Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação', 2016

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222161739/https://antigo.mctic.gov.br/mctic/opencms/ciencia/SEPED/Publicacoes/ENCTI/PlanosDeAcao.html%20>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

political agendas however have resulted in different levels of progress in terms of policy and implementation of change from year to year.

Key federal agencies involved in the funding of biotechnology and biomanufacturing research and scholarships in Brazil include FINEP (Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos) and CNPq (Consejo Nacional de Desarrollo Científico y Tecnológico). FINEP funds both the public and private sectors with grants for basic and applied research, product innovations and development, services and processes, and infrastructure projects. In 2022, FINEP committed 50 million reais (~10 million USD) from the National Fund for Scientific and Technological Development (FNDCT) towards biotechnology, equally split between health, agriculture, environmental and marine, and industrial biotechnology research lines.^{187,188,189,190} CNPq also funds a range of projects and has formed partnerships with other international research funding agencies to run joint funding calls and foster collaboration including Horizon Europe and Italy's CNR.^{191,192}

Strong state level support for science in particular in wealthier states like Sao Paulo, whose funding body FAPESP has a budget of 1% of the State's tax revenue, have also helped support research and innovation especially while federal funding was reduced in the years between 2014 and 2022, providing resilience. Other states with similar strong support driven by strong local economies include FAPERJ (Rio de Janeiro) and FAPEMIG (Minas Gerais), however states with less tax revenue are impacted more severely by lack of federal funding. There is a need therefore for renewed federal support for research and new strategies for the development of the field.¹⁹³ Private investment and collaboration, challenges identified in Brazil, have been addressed through funding mechanisms like PDPs and organisations like EMBRAPII.¹⁹⁴

¹⁸⁷ Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos (Finep), Brazil, 'Sobre a Finep', 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222161927/http://www.finep.gov.br/a-finep-externo/sobre-a-finep>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁸⁸ Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovações, Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos, 'Subvenção Econômica à Inovação – 18/2022 Biotecnologia Aplicada Aos Temas Atuais de Saúde Humana, Agropecuária, Meio Ambiente e Indústria'

<https://web.archive.org/web/20240804110931/http://www.finep.gov.br/images/chamadas-publicas/2022/19_09_2022_Bio_Edital_Rerratificado.pdf> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁸⁹ Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos (Finep), Brazil, 'Our Programs', 2024

<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162221/http://finep.gov.br/aceso-a-informacao-externo/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=4723&Itemid=500> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁹⁰ Gomes and others, 'The Landscape of Biomedical Research Funding in Brazil'.

¹⁹¹ European Commission, 'Brazil (CNPq)-Italy (CNR) Call for Joint Projects | EURAXESS', 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162750/https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/worldwide/lac/news/brazil-cnpq-italy-cnr-call-joint-projects>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁹² 'How Brazil's Resilient Research Ecosystem Weathered Funding Cuts'

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222162941/https://www.nature.com/articles/d42473-023-00323-1>> [accessed 5 January 2025].

¹⁹³ Mercedes Maria da Cunha Bustamante and others, 'The Future of Brazilian Science', *Nature Human Behaviour*, 7.6 (2023), pp. 825–27, doi:10.1038/s41562-023-01597-7.

¹⁹⁴ 'Who We Are - Embrapii'.

Argentina

As the second largest economy in South America, despite economic troubles including fiscal deficits and chronic inflation rising rapidly in the last 5 years to reach 289% in April 2024, Argentina is a strong player in the field of biotechnology and biomanufacturing. The country has been active in supporting and promoting the bioeconomy as well as pushing green policies. A census carried out in 2023 identified more than 340 biotechnology companies with a turnover of more than 1.4 billion dollars providing over 20,000 jobs. This reportedly places Argentina in the top 10 countries globally for number of biotech companies with over 40 percent of these companies being founded since 2015. As the third highest global producer of GM crops with a historically strong pharmaceutical sector which is increasingly utilising biomanufacturing and biotechnology, Argentina has a strong foundation to support all biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors including health, food, agriculture and materials.^{195,196}

From a policy perspective, Argentina has also been active in the last decade in promoting biotechnology, biomanufacturing and the bioeconomy, in part in alignment with green policies and sustainable development goals. A 'Biotechnology Strategy to 2030' report was released in 2016 by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Productive Innovation (MINCYT) that analysed the biotechnology landscape and also considered multiple aspects and requirements including infrastructure and scale up, human resources and intellectual property, and gave recommendations for the development of the field.¹⁹⁷ Multiple ministries and commissions have been involved in supporting the biotechnology and biomanufacturing sectors and developing policy and regulation, which include the Ministry of Science, Technology and Productive Innovation (MINCYT) (dissolved in December 2023), Ministry of Economy Bioeconomy Secretariat, National Advisory Commission for Agricultural Biotechnology (CONABIA), National Food Commission (CONAL) and Ministry of Health, to name a few.^{198,199,200}

¹⁹⁵ Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Se Presentaron Los Resultados Del Primer Censo Biotecnológico y Nanotecnológico', 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163554/https://www.cabiotec.com.ar/post/se-presentaron-los-resultados-del-primer-censo-biotecnol%C3%B3gico-y-nanotecnol%C3%B3gico>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

¹⁹⁶ '1 ° Censo Argentino de Empresas y Startups Bio y Nano', 2023
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163705/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/presentacion_resu ltados_censo_bionano_28.11.23.pptx.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

¹⁹⁷ 'Biotecnología Argentina al Año 2030: Llave Estratégica Para Un Modelo de Desarrollo Tecno-Productivo.' (Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación Productiva, 2016)
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163754/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/sites/default/files/est_bio_biotecnologia-argentina-al-2030-documento-final.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

¹⁹⁸ 'Bioeconomía | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222163902/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura/bioeconomia>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

¹⁹⁹ 'Secretaría de Coordinación de Producción | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222164112/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/produccion>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁰⁰ 'CONABIA | Argentina.Gob.Ar', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241222164310/https://www.argentina.gob.ar/agricultura/bioeconomia/biotecnologia/conabia>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

Argentina has one of the most developed regulation frameworks for the field in the region and defined timeframes for approval of products of biotechnology has accelerated and supported improvement in the efficiency of processes, however challenges in this area still remain.²⁰¹ In addition Argentina along with Brazil continue to be leaders in development of international cooperation in the field, signing a 'Cooperation Agreement on Biosafety of Modern Biotechnology Products' which was joined by Paraguay and Uruguay in 2023. Argentina has also been a driving country behind creation of the 'Bio Innovation Group for South-South Cooperation' in 2023.²⁰² Organisations like the Argentine Chamber of Biotechnology (CAB) which brings together leading companies working in various sectors of biotechnology further support biomanufacturing and biotechnology in the region, through actively promoting the development of supportive public-private policy.²⁰³

From a financing perspective CONICET is the main organisation responsible for funding both academic research and industrial and academic cooperation with 46% of industry in the field engaged with CONICET for co-development of R&D activities.²⁰⁴ Supportive and targeted innovation and tax laws have also supported development of the field within Argentina.²⁰⁵ There is also a growing Venture Capital financing infrastructure.²⁰⁶

Challenges for the sector identified during the 2023 census include difficulties of access to imported inputs, financing for research and innovation, infrastructure for R&D and scaling, as well as regulatory difficulties.²⁰⁷ The links between public institutions and startups in the fields of biotechnology and biomanufacturing identified in the census demonstrate the way the fields still rely heavily on basic research and research at academic institutions. While reining in inflation must be a policy priority and contributes heavily to the current difficulties of conducting research in the country, deteriorating relationships and social divisions between academics and the government as well as significantly reduced funding further threaten the development of the biotechnology and biomanufacturing industries which have been identified as key potential contributors to the economy. While private investment can continue to support development of the field in the short term, this only applies to lower risk research with

²⁰¹ Andrea Yankelevich, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Argentina, USDA', 2023 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222153433/https://apps.fas.usda.gov/newgainapi/api/Report/DownloadReportByFileName?fileName=Agricultural%20Biotechnology%20Annual_Buenos%20Aires_Argentina_AR2023-0016> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁰² Andrea Yankelevich, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Argentina, USDA'; Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Se Presentaron Los Resultados Del Primer Censo Biotecnológico y Nanotecnológico'.

²⁰³ Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Acerca de Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103143936/https://www.cabiotec.com.ar/acerca-de-la-cab>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁰⁴ Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Se Presentaron Los Resultados Del Primer Censo Biotecnológico y Nanotecnológico'.

²⁰⁵ Baker McKenzie, 'Argentina'.

²⁰⁶ Andrés Engler, 'GRIDX: Argentina Is Leading Latin America's Bright Future in Biotech', 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240616093307/https://agfundernews.com/gridx-ceo-on-why-argentina-is-leading-latin-americas-boom-in-biotech-innovation>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁰⁷ Cámara Argentina de Biotecnología, 'Se Presentaron Los Resultados Del Primer Censo Biotecnológico y Nanotecnológico'.

direct benefits to the private sector. Therefore, in the long term without government support there is a risk that the currently promising development in the field may be left behind when compared to other countries both within the region and internationally who are heavily investing in developing the field.²⁰⁸

Chile

Chile is the fourth largest economy in the region, sixth in terms of population, and the most western country in South America. Though Chile does not invest heavily in research and development both in the public and private sector at only 0.4% of GDP, stable funding and politics, support for education, and policies that have promoted formation of startups have contributed to Chile's position in biotechnology and biomanufacturing in the region.

From a policy perspective there has been limited focus on biotechnology and biomanufacturing in Chile. From 2015-2018 the 'IFle of Biotechnology', a joint public-private-academic initiative funded by the FIE Strategic Investment Fund of the Ministry of Economy, aimed to promote innovation, entrepreneurship and investment in biotechnology. As a result in 2018, CORFO (La Corporación de Fomento de la Producción) released a biotechnology strategy to 2030. In this document, it was estimated that biotechnology represents 10 percent of licensing from Chilean universities and 1.2 percent of spinoffs with private investment, transfer of research to the market, scaling and validation capabilities as well as regulation identified as some of the challenges facing the sector. Proposed initiatives and policy recommendations were given, some of which have been implemented, however the progress in many is unclear and no targeted report towards biomanufacturing and biotechnology has been released since.²⁰⁹

In 2018, Chile established a new ministry for 'Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation', which is responsible for coordinating efforts and forming policy. This promising development resulted in the production of a first 'National Policy on Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation' in 2020 which does mention biotechnology as a transformative enabling technology alongside artificial intelligence. A 'Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation Strategy' was further produced in 2022 with directives targeted at transition towards a knowledge driven economy. This included many general components to promote innovation and technology transfer which will be

²⁰⁸ International Science Council, 'Support for the Integrity of Argentina's Science System - International Science Council', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103145812/https://council.science/blog/support-for-the-integrity-of-argentinas-science-system/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁰⁹ CORFO, 'CORFO - Corporación de Fomento de La Producción', 2018
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250106115853/https://corfo.cl/sites/cpp/sala_de_prensa/nacional/09-03-2017_es_trategia_de_biotechnologia> [accessed 6 January 2025].

positive for the biomanufacturing and biotechnology sectors.^{210,211} There has been a policy drive to increase investment in research and development with a target of growing to 0.8% of GDP by 2030 with a 50% public and 50% private funding composition.²¹² Chile is also in the process of updating Technology Transfer law with a Bill being developed in parliament.²¹³ Given Chile is rich in bioresources and is a globally important agricultural and food producer, as well as an important country for mining metals including copper, a targeted biotechnology and biomanufacturing strategy which also focuses on applications in these industries would be valuable for the country, ensuring the required infrastructure can be put in place.

From a regulatory perspective, in terms of agricultural biotechnology, Chile has regulation in place concerning the use of GMOs which supports only reproduction of seeds. This is controlled by the Agricultural and Livestock service. This policy is considerably stricter than other countries in the region. There also remains unfinished regulation. This includes there being no regulatory framework for animal and microbial biotechnology when not related to health. Chile does however have a far more robust Chemicals regulation than many other countries in the region and is starting registration for industrial chemicals in 2024.^{214,215,216}

From a financing perspective, the majority of the public financing for research in biotechnology and biomanufacturing comes from ANID (Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo) and CORFO (La Corporación de Fomento de la Producción). In 2017, 43% of projects awarded funding in the CORFO High Technology Instrument (Instrumento de Alta Tecnología Corfo) were in the biotechnology area.²¹⁷ ANID provides mainly basic research funding, but also provides translational research funding and has

²¹⁰ 'Government Presents the First National Policy on Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation - Gob.Cl', 2020
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240910085436/https://www.gob.cl/en/news/government-presents-first-national-policy-science-technology-knowledge-and-innovation/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹¹ CONSEJO NACIONAL DE CIENCIA, TECNOLOGÍA, CONOCIMIENTO E INNOVACIÓN, 'SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, KNOWLEDGE & INNOVATION NATIONAL STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILE - 2022', 2022
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103150423/https://docs.consejoctci.cl/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/CTCI_Estategia-2022-ingles.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹² Consejo Asesor Ministerial 2022, 'Documento de Trabajo N°1, Una Propuesta de Crecimiento Del Ecosistema de Ciencia, Tecnología, Conocimiento e Innovación En Chile', 2022
<https://web.archive.org/web/20220718160021/https://minciencia.gob.cl/uploads/filer_public/6b/af/6baf786c-44b6-4120-90a2-563bb3e3d53e/consejo_asesor_ministerial_dt01-crecimiento_del_sistema_ctci.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹³ Andrés Couve, 'Columna de Andrés Couve: Transferencia Tecnológica: Capturar Oportunidades Del Alto Impacto - La Tercera', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240816164620/https://www.latercera.com/opinion/noticia/columna-de-andres-couve-transferencia-tecnologica-capturar-oportunidades-del-alto-impacto/MUF5YEBO6VHZHIW6YTBLKA5TJM/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹⁴ Theory Wen, 'Chile to Start Initial Registration for Industrial Chemicals Soon | ChemLinked', 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103151237/https://chemical.chemlinked.com/news/chemical-news/chile-opens-it-chemical-registration-system>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹⁵ Nelson Ramirez, 'Agricultural Biotechnology Annual, Chile, USDA'.

²¹⁶ Pablo Rozas and others, 'Genetically Modified Organisms: Adapting Regulatory Frameworks for Evolving Genome Editing Technologies', *Biological Research*, 55 (2022), doi:10.1186/s40659-022-00399-x.

²¹⁷ CORFO, 'CORFO - Corporación de Fomento de La Producción'.

also released funding calls to support consolidation of transfer and licensing offices.^{218,219}

²¹⁸ Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo, 'Consolidación de Las Oficinas de Transferencia y Licenciamiento (OTL) 2024 - ANID'
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152329/https://anid.cl/concursos/consolidacion-de-las-oficinas-de-transferencia-y-licenciamiento-otl-2024/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²¹⁹ 'Worldwide Strategies | Bioökonomie.De', 2025
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103152517/https://biooekonomie.de/en/topics/in-depth-reports-worldwide?term_node_tid_depth=185> [accessed 6 January 2025].

Appendix II: Global Landscape of Biomanufacturing

Globally biotechnology and biomanufacturing have been recognised as disruptive technologies that have the potential to transform industry and society. Leading economies have implemented both policy and regulatory changes and directives, as well as seen growth and investment in the sector. The Covid19 pandemic in particular saw raised interest and investment in biomanufacturing worldwide, whilst also demonstrating the need for local biomanufacturing capabilities.

The global biotechnology sector has grown significantly in the past decade with the market valued by some estimates at above 1.5 trillion USD²²⁰ with annual revenue of the sector growing from 355.8 bn USD in 2010 to 477.1 bn USD in 2023 (34.1%) and forecasted to grow to 555.8 bn USD in 2028.²²¹ The annual profit of the sector was \$92.1bn in 2023, and the number of employees employed has risen to over 1 million in more than 11, 000 businesses.

Investment, in particular from private venture capital peaked in 2021 due to the spotlight on the sector as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, and whilst it has reduced since, investment remains strong.²²² Current challenges for private investment include macroeconomic factors like high interest rates, which are encouraging lower risk investments.

Below the biotechnology and biomanufacturing landscape and policy developments in some key regions are presented in brief. Many of the policy documents can be used as templates and resources for drafting biotechnology and biomanufacturing policy in South America.

The United States

The US is a global leader in biotechnology and biomanufacturing with a reported annual revenue in 2023 of \$183.1bn and over 430, 000 employees working in the sector. (Ibis world reports). The US also houses 13 of the top 30 start-up ecosystems globally which

²²⁰ Grand View Research, *Biotechnology Market Size, Share & Growth Report, 2030* <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250106141038/https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/biotechnology-market>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²²¹ IBIS World, 'Performance - L6724-GL Global Biotechnology - MyIBISWorld', 2024 <<https://my-ibisworld-com.cjbs.idm.oclc.org/gl/en/industry/l6724-gl/performance>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²²² wang xinlei, 'Biotech Investment Trends in 2023', *Patsnap*, 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250106142101/https://www.patsnap.com/resources/blog/biotech-investment-trends-in-2023/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

include Silicon Valley and New York City, and has strong universities which are leaders in biotechnology including Harvard, Yale, Stanford and MIT, with established technology transfer processes aiding the move of novel technologies from academic research to industry and real world application.²²³

The US government has identified biotechnology and biomanufacturing as a key target area and has implemented several key policy directives to support biotechnology and biomanufacturing, with a clear vision and long term targets to ensure America maintains its status as a global leader. In September 2022, President Biden issued an executive order titled “Advancing Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Innovation for a Sustainable, Safe, and Secure American Bioeconomy” which was followed later the same month by the announcement of new investments and resources to advance the initiative.^{224,225} This included \$40 million towards biomanufacturing for active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), antibiotics, and key starting materials from the The Department of Health and Human Services; \$270 million investment over five years from the Department of Defence towards for launching the ‘Tri-Service Biotechnology for a Resilient Supply Chain’ program as well as \$1 billion over 5 years towards bioindustrial domestic manufacturing infrastructure and \$200 million to support enhancements to biosecurity and cybersecurity posture for these facilities, to name a few. These investments were accompanied by large investments in regional infrastructure, training and education, measurements and standards, and data infrastructure. In December of 2022, PCAST(President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology) identified “insufficient manufacturing capacity, regulatory uncertainty, and an outdated national strategy” as three gaps slowing American development and recommended a “long-term, data-driven plan”.²²⁶ This was followed in 2023, by a report titled “Bold Goals for U.S. Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing” which outlined key 5 - 20 year targets for biomanufacturing and biotechnology in the areas of food and agriculture innovation, supply chain resilience, human health, and cross-cutting

²²³ Startup Genome, ‘THE GLOBAL STARTUP ECOSYSTEM REPORT 2023 Insights, Rankings & Ecosystem Pages’, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240808035800/https://startupgenome.com/article/north-america-insights-ranking-s-and-ecosystem-pages-1>>.

²²⁴ THE WHITE HOUSE, ‘Federal Register :: Advancing Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Innovation for a Sustainable, Safe, and Secure American Bioeconomy, FR Doc. 2022-20167’, 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103154530/https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2022/09/15/2022-20167/advancing-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-innovation-for-a-sustainable-safe-and-secure-american>>.

²²⁵ THE WHITE HOUSE, ‘FACT SHEET: The United States Announces New Investments and Resources to Advance President Biden’s National Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Initiative | The White House’, 2022
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103154650/https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2022/09/14/fact-sheet-the-united-states-announces-new-investments-and-resources-to-advance-president-bidens-national-biotechnology-and-biomanufacturing-initiative/>>.

²²⁶ Executive Office of the President, President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology, ‘REPORT TO THE PRESIDENT Biomanufacturing to Advance the Bioeconomy’, 2022
<https://web.archive.org/web/20241128021238/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/PCAST_Biomanufacturing-Report_Dec2022.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

advances, along with opportunities for public-private collaboration in each.²²⁷ A policy document focused on building the “bioworkforce” of the future was also released.²²⁸ In May 2023, the Regional Technology and Innovation hubs competition was launched, with \$10 billion for the program over five years. Of these hubs over 10 of the 31 inaugural tech hubs announced in October 2023 have a focus on biotechnology or biomanufacturing. In 2024 a further policy document was released concerning building a resilient biomass supply chain to support the bioeconomy.^{229,230,231}

Europe

The EU is also a strong player internationally in biotechnology and biomanufacturing and has recognised biotechnology as a critical technology to be prioritised in the Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP) regulation.²³² The size of the EU Biotechnology industry was reported to be 86.4 billion euros in 2021, employing 210,700 direct jobs in 2018, and growing more than twice as fast as the overall EU economy between 2008 and 2018.^{233,234} Further Europe is home to many world renowned universities and institutes including Institute Pasteur, EMBL, and Max Plank institutes.

In 2024, the European commission released a report on “Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU”. This report set out the challenges for the sector and

²²⁷ The White House Office of Science and Technology Policy and others, ‘BOLD GOALS FOR U.S. BIOTECHNOLOGY AND BIOMANUFACTURING: HARNESSING RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT TO FURTHER SOCIETAL GOALS’, 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155233/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/Bold-goals-for-U.S.-Biotechnology-and-Biomanufacturing-Harnessing-Research-and-Development-To-Further-Societal-Goals-FINAL.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²²⁸ Interagency Working Group and THE WHITE HOUSE, ‘Building the Bioworkforce of the Future Expanding Equitable Pathways into Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing Jobs’, 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241228020212/https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Building-the-Bioworkforce-of-the-Future.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²²⁹ U.S. Department of Commerce, Office of Public Affairs, ‘Biden-Harris Administration Launches First Tech Hubs Funding Opportunity | U.S. Department of Commerce’, 2023

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155636/https://www.commerce.gov/news/press-releases/2023/05/biden-harris-administration-launches-first-tech-hubs-funding>>.

²³⁰ ‘Regional Technology and Innovation Hubs (Tech Hubs) | U.S. Economic Development Administration’

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103155818/https://www.eda.gov/funding/programs/regional-technology-and-innovation-hubs>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²³¹ USDA (U.S. Department of Agriculture), ‘BUILDING A RESILIENT BIOMASS SUPPLY: A Plan to Enable the Bioeconomy in America’, 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241217011343/https://www.usda.gov/sites/default/files/documents/biomass-supply-chain-report.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²³² MILEUSNIC MARIN and RAGONNAUD Guillaume, ‘Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform (STEP), Briefing’, 2024

<[https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160136/https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/754547/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)754547_EN.pdf](https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160136/https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/754547/EPRS_BRI(2023)754547_EN.pdf)>.

²³³ European Commission, ‘Building the Future with Nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU’, 2024

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160243/https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52024DC0137>>.

²³⁴ ‘Value Share of Biotech Sector by Country Worldwide 2021 | Statista’, 2021

<<https://web.archive.org/web/20241126213049/https://www.statista.com/statistics/1246614/top-countries-share-of-global-biotech-value/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

indicated opportunities and policy changes required to further support the sector.²³⁵ Challenges for the EU identified within the 2024 report include technology transfer from research to industry and the regulatory complexity within the region. In 2022, a progress report titled “Bioeconomy Policy: Stocktaking and Future Developments”, evaluated progress based on the EU 2018 Bioeconomy Strategy.^{236,237}

Several EU financing instruments help support development of both academic research and industrial development of biotechnology and biomanufacturing including ‘Horizon Europe’, the ‘Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking’, the ‘Innovative Health Initiative Joint Undertaking’, ‘EU4Health’, the ‘Innovation Fund’, and the ‘Strategic Technologies for Europe Platform’ (STEP).²³⁸ ‘Horizon Europe’, with a budget of EUR 95.5 billion for the period from 2021-2027 has reportedly funded nearly 600 projects within the area of health totalling EUR 1.5 billion of funding so far, many of which contain biotechnology and biomanufacturing. 350 million euros have been reportedly used to fund biotechnology projects and start-ups and SMEs. There is also a current EIC call focused on “Food from Precision Fermentation and Algae”.²³⁹ The EU’s ‘Cohesion Policy’ has also reportedly funded about 3700 “close-to-market biotech research and innovation projects” since 2014.²⁴⁰

Many EU member countries each have their own biotechnology and biomanufacturing policies, initiatives and financing including France where in 2022 the government committed to spend 7.5 billion euros towards Healthcare innovation, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland, and the Netherlands.^{241,242}

The UK, though no longer a member of the EU, is also a leader in biomanufacturing and biotechnology, and has rejoined ‘Horizon Europe’ in 2023. London has been recognised

²³⁵ European Commission, ‘Building the Future with Nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU’.

²³⁶ ‘Bioeconomy Strategy - European Commission’ <https://web.archive.org/web/20250103160737/https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/environment/bioeconomy/bioeconomy-strategy_en> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²³⁷ Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), *European Bioeconomy Policy: Stocktaking and Future Developments: Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions* (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022) <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/997651>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²³⁸ European Commission, ‘Building the Future with Nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU’.

²³⁹ European Commission, ‘Questions and Answers on the Communication on Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing’, 2024 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250106163823/https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/qanda_24_1571/QANDA_24_1571_EN.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁰ European Commission, ‘Building the Future with Nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU’.

²⁴¹ Jonathan Smith, ‘France’s Grand Plan to Lead Europe’s Biotech Innovation Landscape | LABIOTECH’, 2022 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103162211/https://www.labiotech.eu/in-depth/france-biotech-innovation-2030/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴² European Council of Bioregions (CEBR) and European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), ‘Together for Tackling the Biomanufacturing & Breakthrough Technologies Challenges in Europe’, 2021 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241220142503/http://eithealth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Executive-summary-07102021.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

as joint second ranked start-up ecosystem in 2023, and the UK has multiple well known universities including Oxford, Cambridge, Imperial College, and University College London.²⁴³ Similarly bioengineering and biomanufacturing have been recognised as important sectors with a bioeconomy national strategy produced in 2018, and recent government consultations on “Engineering Biology”.²⁴⁴ The U.K.’s life sciences network OBN has been presented as a good example of the benefits of supporting and bringing together the U.K.’s life science companies, partners and investors.²⁴⁵

Asia

Asia has a rapidly strengthening biomanufacturing and biotechnology sector, which together has been reported to account for 36.6% of the global industry when combining India and Central Asia, North Asia, and South East Asia.^{246,247}

Japan’s ‘Bio Industry’ was reportedly worth 32 Billion USD in 2019, and the Japanese government formulated a bioeconomy strategy with the ambitious aim to grow the sector to 837 billion USD by 2030. In 2019, the government of Japan funded 56 million dollars to promote biomanufacturing technologies, and the strategy involved data infrastructure, policy developments, systems maintenance and ‘Bio community’ formation.^{248,249} There is also a plan for an 8 billion USD fund from the Japanese Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry to support biomanufacturing.²⁵⁰

²⁴³ ‘GSER 2023| Startup Genome’, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103162504/https://startupgenome.com/report/gser2023>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁴ ‘Engineering Biology - Committees - UK Parliament’
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240419082135/https://committees.parliament.uk/work/8377/engineering-biology/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁵ ‘Home| OBN’, OBN <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103013741/https://obn.org.uk/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁶ Marley Broucker, *L6724-GL ; Global Business Activities; Global Biotechnology - IBISWorld*, October 2024.

²⁴⁷ ‘Biomanufacturing Global Series: Europe’s Opportunity to Grow - Europabio’, 2024
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103172805/https://www.europabio.org/biomanufacturing-global-series/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁸ International Trade Administration, U.S. Department of Commerce, ‘Japan Bioeconomy Strategy’, 2021
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103165143/https://www.trade.gov/market-intelligence/japan-bioeconomy-strategy>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁴⁹ OHNO Takahiro, ‘Japan’s Bioeconomy Strategy’s Featuring Points, G20 OECD-BNCT WORKSHOP, Bioeconomy in the OECD Countries, Presidency of Council of Ministers, July 16, 2021’
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103165312/https://cnbbsv.palazzochigi.it/media/2419/ohno-japan-panel1.pdf>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁵⁰ Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI), Japan, ‘Investing in Biotech, From Plastics That Melt in the Sea to Cultured Foie Gras, Japan Is Pushing Innovative Technologies Forward with Government Support’, *The ACCJ Journal*, 2023
<<https://web.archive.org/web/20240921054552/https://journal.accj.or.jp/content/2023/1/investing-in-biotech>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

In India, the government has also produced a 'National Biotechnology Development Strategy' document for 2021-2025, which estimated the sector size to be 63 billion USD in 2019 and set expected size in 2025 to be 150 billion USD. There were estimated to be more than 3500 biotechnology start-ups in the fields of bio-pharma, bio-services, bio-agri, bio-industrial and bioinformatics, with growth primarily driven by vaccines and recombinant therapeutics.²⁵¹ The Serum Institute of India has been reported as the world's largest vaccine manufacturer, exporting to over 170 countries including the US and Europe, and India houses the highest number of USFDA approved manufacturing plants outside of the US. A key strength for biomanufacturing in India is therefore seen as the cost effective manufacturing capabilities.²⁵² Key areas identified for development in the 'National Biotechnology Development Strategy' document include building academic partnerships, enhancing venture capital, improving R&D spend by industry, strengthening the link between research and commercialisation, ensuring quality assurance for products, creating state of the art facilities, and improving education.

Similarly the Chinese government identified for the first time in its 14th five-year plan (2021-2025) biological innovation and biotechnology as major themes. China has aimed to strongly develop its academic sector with a number of globally recognised top "young universities" and two start-up ecosystems, Beijing and Shanghai have been globally ranked at 7th and 9th respectively.²⁵³ The 'made in China 2025' policy document also highlights biotechnology as a key field in which to "promote breakthrough development", and aims to reduce its reliance on foreign technology to make China a global leader in high-tech industries.^{254,255} China is also reported to have granted a similar number of health-biotechnology patents as Europe in the period 2014-2020 and to have 12% of the new biotechnology companies globally between 2018-2020.²⁵⁶

²⁵¹ Department of Biotechnology, Ministry of Science and Technology, Government of India, 'National Biotechnology Development Strategy Document for 2021-2025, Knowledge and Innovation Driven Bio-Economy' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20230811150255/https://dbtindia.gov.in/sites/default/files/National%20Biotechnology%20Development%20Strategy%202021-25.pdf>>.

²⁵² ANTONY SGUAZZIN, 'Top Vaccine Maker Seeks Growth by Selling Shots to Globetrotters - The Japan Times', 2023 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20240510185701/https://www.japantimes.co.jp/business/2023/10/05/companies/india-vaccine-maker-growth/>> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁵³ 'Global Startup Ecosystem Ranking 2023 (Top 30 + Runners-Up) | Startup Genome' <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250103170739/https://startupgenome.com/article/global-startup-ecosystem-ranking-2023-top-30-plus-runners-up>>.

²⁵⁴ Xinhua News Agency, Translated by Ben Murphy, Etcetera Language Group, Inc., 'Translation: Outline of the People's Republic of China 14th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development and Long-Range Objectives for 2035', 2021 <https://web.archive.org/web/20241226174942/https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/t0284_14th_Five_Year_Plan_EN.pdf> [accessed 6 January 2025].

²⁵⁵ PRC State Council, Translated by Ben Murphy, Etcetera Language Group, Inc., 'Translation: Notice of the State Council on the Publication of "Made in China 2025"', 2015 <https://web.archive.org/web/20250103171220/https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/t0432_made_in_china_2025_EN.pdf>.

²⁵⁶ 'Biomanufacturing Global Series'.

Other notable countries with strong presence in biotechnology and biomanufacturing include South Korea and Singapore.²⁵⁷

²⁵⁷ Ayesha Siddiqi, 'How Asia Is Emerging As Biomanufacturing Powerhouse | Biospectrum Asia Edition', 2024 <<https://web.archive.org/web/20241008062247/https://www.biospectrumasia.com/analysis/25/24981/how-asia-is-emerging-as-biomanufacturing-powerhouse-.html>> [accessed 6 January 2025].